

**An investigation of variation and impact of interest rate in commercial banks
after accession to the World Trade Organisation (WTO): The case study of
Republic of Tajikistan**

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ABSTRACT

Financial liberalisation has been extensively complex to measure due to frequent economic fluctuations in the financial institutions, which cannot be controlled. Hence, this issue has been taken into consideration within the banking sector because fluctuations of interest is complex to measure and monitor. In realisation of this, the aim of this research was to analyse the impact of the variation in the interest rate on commercial banks after accession to the WTO, with reference to the case study of Tajikistan. Some of the underlying objectives of the study were to determine the relationship between the interest rate and commercial banks' performance in Tajikistan, to examine theories, models and analyses in order to investigate the fluctuation in the interest rate after accession to the WTO, to analyse the impact of interest rate liberalisation on the financial system of Tajikistan and to compare the interest rate and liberalisation in Tajikistan with neighbouring countries.

The current research is based on comparative analysis with existing financial liberalisation approaches applied by numerous countries. A mix-method approach has been implemented with abductive logical approach. The research used both the qualitative and quantitative approaches that involved 150 bankers from Tajikistan for survey questionnaire and 8 bankers from Tajikistan from interviews. This research enriches the literature on the liberalisation of financial market of Tajikistan, as well as neighbourhood countries that implemented the WTO agreements on liberalisation of financial sector. Furthermore, McKinnon and Shaw's hypothesis research methodology is applied. Additionally, the data is analysed using SPSS and thematic analysis. Hypotheses are framed and tests are applied which are Chi-square, ANOVA, regression and correlation, along with categorising the responses in relevant themes.

Based on the obtained results, the findings suggest that vulnerability, asset liability management and safety factors do not have significant relationship between sales revenue in commercial banks and interest rates in Tajikistan. This suggests any of the independent variable either in the form of vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition, bank's asset liability management and safe while making transactional operations.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

WTO - World Trade Organization

IRP - Interest Rate Parity

IMF - International Monetary Fund

EBRD - European Bank for Reconstruction and Development

ITC - International Trade Centre

GDP - Gross domestic product

GFC - global financial crisis

ADB - Asian Development Bank

NBT- National Bank of Tajikistan

NPA - Non-Performing Asset

SME - Small-to-Medium Enterprise

NPV - Net Present Value

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.0 Chapter Introduction

Financial liberalisation is essential for the financial activities of the organisation. This introductory chapter provides the background and rationale of the study so that relevant aims and objectives can be developed. It also describes the research hypotheses and includes a brief analysis of the research methods that are used in this study.

1.1 Background to the Research Topic

Financial liberalisation should be understood as the removal of restrictions in the activities of banks in the provision of financial services, for example in the provision of loans and deposit registration, etc. This enables financial institutions to independently decide to whom and by what criteria to allocate loans, which allows them to set the price (interest rate) for loans and interest rates on received deposits, and enables them to determine where (aside from lending) to allocate the funds at their disposal (Bogdan and Biklen, 2003). There is a close connection between liberalisation and banking crises, which deserves thorough attention.

In the 1990s, in response to the impact of economic complications, a number of countries initiated fundamental changes to their monetary policy, institutional structures, and the overall performance of their economies, as well as changing the means of accomplishing those goals (Harrod, 2008). Due to the gradual economic backlog, many countries in Latin America and Asia, and countries with centralised planning, relatively quickly abandoned government intervention in their economies and liberalised economic activity. The process of liberalisation has been also applied to the financial sector, initially to banks in the most regulated areas of entrepreneurship, not only in developing countries, but also in many developed countries. (Mehrotra and Yetman, 2015). Leading specialists agree that financial liberalisation in itself is a progressive change, since it allows investments to be directed to where they can be used most effectively. Thus, liberalisation helps to accelerate economic progression (Sneider and Lerner, 2009). Nevertheless, the experience of numerous countries illustrates that under certain circumstances, it can produce a growth in rates and risks for some time.

According to Mogilevskii and Asadov (2018), financial liberalisation significantly changes the banking sector environment. With liberalisation, there is a risk of a disruption to the normal operation of the banking sector due to a combination of the consequences of banks' behaviour in a regulated environment that has accumulated unresolved problems, together with the incentives acting in the new liberal environment (Ponterotto, 2005). The environment, previously protected from external influences, together with strict regulation of financial and credit activities, have contributed to the development of negative phenomena in banking operations. In general, this means that decisions to place assets were made without taking into account the market criteria for maximising profits. Often, banks provided loans based on political requirements or the subjective desire of their owners, sometimes simultaneously acting as customers of the banking services. In such situations, the banks were not fully established and did not have the skills necessary to function successfully in an unprotected and poorly regulated environment, created because of financial liberalisation.

Previous lending activity created a risk of reducing the quality of the loan portfolio and, at the same time, did not enable bankers to rapidly track debtors and determine the degree of credit risk (Harrod, 2008). Usually, financial liberalisation is carried out within the framework of the global approach of macroeconomic balance, financial liberalisation and structural modification (Senhadji, 2000). Due to overall liberalisation, the economic situation of many enterprises has deteriorated, and the total amount of resources used to repay bank loans has reduced. In the course of reforms and the implementation of stabilisation plans that are often connected to financial liberalisation, banks have changed the way monetary policy is implemented. These policy changes have significantly affected the rate of interest change. In addition, the function of direct credit provision among banks has declined and the importance of indirect instruments for influencing economic fluidity, such as open money market operations, has increased. Therefore, banks also adjust their rate of interest in order to meet profitable goals.

In the progression of macroeconomic stabilisation, further restrictions on economic policy have also been introduced (Berg and Krueger, 2002). As a result, these modifications have decreased the possibility for banks to apply for other resources, such as primary loans from the central bank, and short-term financial resources purchased in the e-market. Moreover, the cost of

obtaining these assets is increasing. These factors are primarily associated with the changing interest rates and thus influence the profits and financing function of the economy.

At the same time, the situation is further complicated by the need to restrict economic and financial policies being felt by debtor companies themselves. As a consequence, a surge of non-payments could be triggered by the liquidity crisis, as debtors lose the incentive to meet their obligations (Cojocaru et al., 2016).

It has been reported by Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas (2017) that high level of market interest rates is a side effect of active stabilisation policies, which are dictated, in particular, by the increased inflation rate as opposed to the projected decline, as well as the appreciation of the exchange rate. In the above case, the condition of companies manufacturing products for export deteriorates as their competitiveness in the world market declines. Exporting companies in Tajikistan have been forced to adapt to the new conditions by increasing the efficiency and sales growth of goods within the country or else they could face financial difficulties, increasing the risk of lending to these companies by banks (Elsherif, 2016).

In the words of Chemutai and Escaith (2017), one of the major critical factors that foster the process of liberalisation within financial sector is interest rate. It contributes in increasing refinancing rate when interest rates are elevated. Hence, banks have to pay higher costs to maintain their resources. The increased interest rates also have a negative effect on debtors. In terms of Tajikistan, the investment projects that promised high income, despite rising interest rates, resort to commercial banks (Fletcher, 2017).

The study of Lee, Ning and Lee (2015) was based on examining the effect of bank capital on bank's risk and profitability. The aforementioned study concentrated their study on accession of WTO with commercial banks of China. The findings of prior study reflected that bank capital has a major effect on bank profitability and risk. However, after China joined the WTO in 2001, their influence was declined. The effect of capital on profitability exhibits a distinct pattern for different size categories. Depending on the risk variables used in the Chinese banking industry, the effects of capital on bank risk are different for large and small banks.

The negative impact of fluctuating economic policies and the refinancing rate in Tajikistan is changing the value of interest rates reliant on the loan reimbursement stage. In the course of liberalisation, the differentiation among the interest rates for both short- and long-term loans, which are of great significance for banks, usually decrease. In Tajikistan, interest rates are differentiated due to loan terms. Hence, commercial banks are able to generate profits by transferring short-term liabilities (deposits) to long-term assets (loans) (Lane, 2018). Deposit interest, primarily in the short term by administrative restrictions, is set at a far lower level than the interest rate on longer-term loans. Number of nations such as United States of America (USA) and United Kingdom (UK), have diminished their capacity to ease the possibility of making easy profit due to liberalisation of interest rate, as the cost of seeking financial resources have raised and it has become more difficult to set high interest rates with the use of credit (Macit, 2017). Banks find it difficult to counter the negative impact on interest rates. Typically, bank liabilities are liquid because they represent deposits that are not limited to a certain period, and banks can quickly lose them. In contrast, assets have significantly less liquidity. The credit obligations of borrowers, as a rule, can only be sold to other entities with large losses. The severance of contractual credit relations, in turn, is associated with additional costs in the form of penalties (Turk, 2016).

It has been highlighted by Chemutai and Escaith (2017) that financial liberalisation leads to increased competition between banks. Therefore, they are forced to both reduce the cost of finding resources and to resist competitors in their use, and as a result, profit decreases. The banks' liabilities are affected by competition from other financial institutions, both domestic and foreign, that have access to the banking market. The situation for banks is complicated by the fact that enterprises themselves can quickly inform others about their financial situation that allows them to establish links with the owners of financial resources without resorting to the help of banks. As a rule, enterprises that are able to seek non-bank financing sources are the best customers, and for banks, their loss means increasing the level of their credit portfolio risk.

As elucidated by Ahmed (2010); Desta (2009); Żołądkiewicz (2010), there has been varying impact of WTO accession on economies of multiple nations such as Belarus, Ethiopia,

China and more. As the indagation of Bienen (2017) comprehended that WTO accession in Ethiopia has been focused on eliminating poverty by promoting trade reforms within the nation. However, the findings of the aforementioned study reflected that trade reforms are inaccessible by poor community of Ethiopia, which does not contribute to eliminating poverty in a nation. In the words of Michalopoulos (2014), the trade reforms contributed to creating job opportunities for poor community of Ethiopia due to WTO accession.

1.2 Research Problem

The main research gap that exists is the idea that there is a high impact of interest rate on banking sector due to liberalisation. However, it has become complex to verify whether the research gap exists due to interest rate and liberalisation or not. As a result, there is extensive research that needs to be carried on the gap because the existing research is not sufficient to examine the fluctuations in the interest rate. As cited by Barrell, Karim and Ventouri (2017), financial liberalisation has been extensively complex to measure due to frequent economic fluctuations in the financial institutions, which cannot be controlled. Hence, this issue has been taken into consideration within the banking sector because fluctuations of interest is complex to measure and monitor. It has been identified by Durdyev and Ismail (2017) that it is important for national governments or finance ministries to keep a close eye on volatility in interest rates, as this is considered as a difficult job, which has a significant effect on the entire banking sector.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Research

Aim

The aim of this research is to analyse the impact of the variation in the interest rate on commercial banks after accession to the WTO, with reference to the case study of Tajikistan.

Objectives

- To determine the relationship between the interest rate and commercial banks' performance in Tajikistan.

- To examine theories, models and analyses in order to investigate the fluctuation in the

interest rate after accession to the WTO.

- To analyse the impact of interest rate liberalisation on the financial system of Tajikistan.
- To compare the interest rate and liberalisation in Tajikistan with neighbouring countries.

1.4 Research Questions

- Q1 - What is the ongoing concern regarding interest rate on the commercial banks in Tajikistan after accession to the WTO?
- Q2 - What are the relative factors causing the fluctuation in the interest rate?
- Q3 - How does interest rate liberalisation have an impact on the financial system?
- Q4 - What are the recommendations to guide banks after accession to the WTO to achieve interest rate stability?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

- H_0 - there is no mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue (performance) of commercial banks in Tajikistan.
- H_1 - there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan.

1.6 Justification for the Research

The focus of this study is on various prudential regulations in the financial sector. The primal emphasises is based on the level of fluctuation in interest rates and its effect on the entire financial sector. In addition, the study attempted to understand the factors, which have an impact

on the financial system of developing nations. This research also discussed how the interest rate is measured and how this affects the banking sector. The research also illustrates how the interest rate is regulated and how it contributes to enhancing economic growth. Furthermore, this study concentrates on examining different components of liberalisation that can assist in monetary regulation.

1.7 Brief Description of the Research Methodology

It is necessary to apply different research methods in order to gather relevant and precise data. In this research, econometric methodology is used and various statistical tests are applied to establish the mean, mode, median, etc. In addition, this research undertakes primary data collection by means of questionnaire and interview. Furthermore, the data is analysed using SPSS to extract correlation and different descriptive statistical results such as mean, standard deviation and variance. Moreover, the technique of thematic analysis has been used to analyse the qualitative data.

1.8 Outline of the Thesis

The thesis has been categorised in six chapters entitled as introduction, literature review, research methodology, findings, results and discussing and conclusion, contribution and recommendations.

The first chapter provides a detailed contextual background on the topic along with research problem that inspired the researcher for conducting this research. The fundamental emphasises of chapter one is on specifying research aim, objectives and questions. In addition, the first chapter discusses the rational, justification and brief description of chosen methodology. The second chapter revolves around critical argumentation of various authors pertaining to financial liberalisation and impact of interest rate in commercial banks after accession. Chapter two strongly focuses discussion various theories related to interest rate fluctuation such as interest rate parity, classical theory and more, which helps a reader in understanding the scenario or circumstances that lead to fluctuation of interest rate. In addition, the benefits and challenges associated with accession of WTO in commercial banks of Tajikistan have given thorough emphasises. Chapter three is based on an extensive discussion of research methodology that covers the philosophical

paradigm being considered by researcher and research approach that has been chosen for this investigation has been discussed. Additionally, the primal focus of third chapter is on discussing the research design and method of data collection considered by research. This section also provided justification for considering particular technique of data analysis for answering the research questions and proving the formulated hypothesis. The fourth chapter is based on findings that where the analysis of data has been presented in both quantitative and qualitative manner to generate objective as well as subjective results. All the details are presented in a systemic manner so that valid conclusions can be drawn. The fifth chapter is based on discussion in which the findings are evaluated as per research objectives. The final section of this investigation is based on the conclusion, where the recommendations and contributions of this study for future research are briefly discussed.

1.9 Definition of Terms Used in the Research

Interest rate: interest rate has been defined as the amount paid per period, which is the proportion of principal amount or the amount, which is borrowed, lent or deposited (Shaofeng, 2017).

Commercial banks: financial institutions that perform and regulate financial operations and accept deposits, manage lending and accounting services along with other transactional operations. Commercial banks also assign certificates of deposit and savings to individuals and organisations (Alotaibi, 2015).

Financial liberalisation: refers to the removal or elimination of government ceilings or regulation of interest rates, and all other attributes of financial intermediaries (Zhang, 2018).

Refinancing rate: the minimum bid rate and can be defined as the interest rate that is paid by commercial banks when they borrow money from the European Central Bank (Kothari, 2018).

Liquidity: can be described as the extent up to which an asset can be sold or purchased in the market at its intrinsic value. Thus, liquidity refers to the ease of converting an asset into cash (Bun, 2018).

Fluctuations in interest rate: rapid changes in interest rates are known as fluctuations. These fluctuations are the result of inflation, variation in supply and demand, and economic stability (Aid, 2019).

Interest rate stability: for the stability and better functioning of interest rates, it is necessary that changes in interest rates are smooth so that financial stability can be promoted. The reduced volatility of interest rates has a direct impact on the solvency of commercial banks (Lu, 2018).

Fiscal policies: these are known as the policies that describe the utilisation of government expenditure and revenue collection so that economy can be improved (Gonzalez, 2017).

World Trade Organization (WTO): an intergovernmental body that regulates international trade between countries (Smart, 2017).

Financial repression: the policies through which government and regulatory bodies can enhance domestically held debt and tax income (Siddiqui, 2019).

Foreign exchange trade: the global decentralised market for the trading of currencies. Through this procedure, currencies are bought, exchanged and sold at fixed prices (Verdiyeva, 2018).

Redistributive economy: defined as an economic system in which a substantial share of wealth is mobilised under centralised administrative control and out from the common population (Shaofeng, 2017).

Gross domestic product (GDP): the monetary measurement that describes the value of goods that are produced in a fixed time period in a given country (Alotaibi, 2015).

Marginal efficiency of capital: the discount rate, which equates the price or monetary value of the fixed capital asset with the present discounted price of, expected income (Kothari, 2018).

Depreciation: refers to the reduction or decline in the monetary value of an asset over a certain time period. The cost of the asset is allocated to the time period over which it was in use (Aid, 2019).

Amortisation: the process or method of paying off debts or loans through regular payments. It is used for both loans and assets (Bun, 2018).

Accumulated capital: defined as the increment in the value of assets by the means of profits or investments. It motivates profit so initial monetary value can be increased (Zhang, 2018).

1.10 Scope of the Research

The scope of the research is to examine financial market from a regional or national perspective and to assess the financial market of Republic of Tajikistan after WTO accession and the effects of financial reforms in economically similar nations. It also involves a collection of important internal and external relationships between the financial market segments that have a direct impact in reducing the deformation of economic position in financial market.

The scope of the research is devoted to the analysis of interest rate liberalisation and has been divided into four areas:

- A quantitative assessment of income from interest rate liberalisation
- The political and economic reasons for implementing interest rate liberalisation
- The impact of financial repression on the growth of the economy
- Optimality of interest rate liberalisation.

The study examines quantitative estimates of income from financial institutions and their significance for public finances. For example, Reinhart (2008) notes that even with moderate inflation, interest rate liberalisation often leads to maintaining the real interest rate at a negative level for a long period of time. De Melo (2002) also claims that the transition to financial liberalisation leads to significant losses in budget revenues and requires budgetary reforms. As far as modern developed countries are concerned, steps such as the nationalisation of the funded

section within pension system and the rise in the share of government bonds in the commercial bank balance have allowed them to avoid a public debt default.

As per the studies of Chemutai and Escaith (2017); Zhunusova and Herrmann (2018), one of the most comprehensive areas of research on bank interest rate liberalisation is an effective way to strengthen financial control of economic growth. Fry (1996) argues that such a policy guarantees financial stability and prevents the negative effects of financial shock on a country's development and economic conditions.

The main contribution of this work will be focused on the optimal policy of financial liberalisation. In the literature, this issue is considered in the sense of the government receiving inflationary tax and maximising budget revenues under income tax evasion conditions. The focus of this investigation is that developing countries are characterised by a low level of financial development, tax evasion and monetisation of budget deficits. It is not assumed that financial liberalisation is associated with inflationary financing of the budget deficit or a decrease in the efficiency of the financial system (Hördahl, Sobrun and Turner, 2016). The redistribution of financial resources between the private and public sectors does not make the work of financial intermediaries less effective (Agapova and McNulty, 2016). Thus, the model is more in line with the situation typical for developed countries, which have shifted from the financial crisis of 2007-2009 to fiscal stress. If financial reform is considered as an implicit tax on the financial sector, then the problem of optimal taxation arises. Among other things, this study answers two questions: firstly, whether financial liberalisation is an element of optimal taxation, and secondly, whether financial liberalisation and explicit taxes are perfect substitutes.

It is also necessary to consider the currency market of Tajikistan and the interrelations and interdependencies arising in the process of its functioning, taking into account interest rate liberalisation. Therefore, is the process of regulating the aggregate of economic relations regarding the formation and implementation of the monetary policy of Tajikistan taking into account financial liberalisation and strengthening the functional interrelationships of the currency sector of the financial market with other sectors?

1.11 Limitations of the Research

The study has been productive in looking at the role of interest rate volatility in financial systems. One of the major limitations that have been experienced during the process of research is related to data collection. Several commercial banks have different interest rates, so the effect of varying interest rates is very difficult and challenging to understand. Banking stability is seen as a major factor affecting their ability to control interest rates. However, the limitation exists inadequate implementation of primary and secondary sources to analyse the mentioned area of research.

Variations in the interest rate can be very abrupt and uncertain, so the use of sources over the past few years can affect the relevance of the results. In this investigation, primary data is obtained through questionnaires while interviews are also performed, but the sample size has been kept relatively limited due to budget constraints. The data are collected from various enterprises and thus, can subject to limitations in terms of accuracy and integrity of data collection process.

1.12 Theoretical Background

The study focuses on identifying whether financial liberalisation has an impact on banking sector. In addition, it analyses the economic conditions of Tajikistan and other economies. Here, much research has been carried out on finding out the relationship between financial liberalisation and the economy.

The theoretical basis of this research is based on the scientific works of foreign authors in the field financial and banking systems, their structure, functions and role in the economic system, as well as studies of the regulation of the interest rate, and the effective work on the successful implementation and reform of financial systems around the world.

Moreover, the combination of a market portfolio with a risk-free asset often offers less risk and less projected revenue for a product portfolio. This method is macroeconomic, since it is the main objective of the analysis. The difference between the Markowitz and Tobin theory is that

Markowitz emphasised the mathematical analysis of the consequences of the initial data and the development of algorithms for solving optimisation problems (Markowitz. 2010). Tobin also took as a basis the analysis of the factors that compel investors to form a portfolio of securities rather than keep them in one form (Grasselli, 2014).

However, the origin of the modern portfolio theory was developed by Markowitz (1952), whose theory states that the problem of portfolio optimisation is to minimise the risk at a given average profitability. Tobin (1958) also showed that the market portfolio is effective where there is a set of all securities that available to investor. In addition, the macroeconomic approach is considered as major aspect in terms of market portfolio, such as any combination of a market portfolio with a risk-free asset provides an efficient portfolio with less risk and less expected income.

1.13 Chapter Summary

From the overview of this introductory chapter, it can be concluded that there are many factors that influence the financial sector such as: financial liberalisation and an open economy that protects against the risks associated with the shock effect of cross-border short-term capital flows; an effective mechanism to prevent the adoption of undercapitalised financial institutions' (primarily banks') excessive risk can be created only through a system of control by the stock market. Moreover, financial liberalisation decides independently to whom to allocate loans and determines where to impact economic complications as well as in ways to accomplish goals with centralised planning and liberalised economic activity. Different commercial banks have an impact based on varying interest rates, volatile interest rate fluctuations from both primary and secondary sources may affect the relevancy. In addition, it is summarised that problems of financial liberalisation occur due to government and optimising budget revenues in conditions of evasion from paying income tax. It is also necessary to consider the currency market of Tajikistan, the interrelations and interdependencies arising in the process of its functioning when considering interest rate liberalisation.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This section furnishes a critical assessment of the major theoretical approaches, which are used to describe different themes in the literature review section. Therefore, this section provides an in-depth knowledge related to the current condition of interest rate in commercial banks in Tajikistan and then define different theories behind the fluctuation of interest rates in Tajikistan. Moreover, it also analyses the outcome of involvement rate liberalisation in the financial system and then define different factors behind the cause of fluctuation of interest rates. Lastly, by supporting different authors' point of views, researcher described the benefits and challenges of accession to WTO in the banking sector of Tajikistan.

2.1 Current condition of interest rate and associated theories with interest rate

2.1.1 Overview

As per viewpoints of Barrell, Karim and Ventouri, (2017), the term interest rate has been defined as the proportion of the debt or loan amount that has been charged in form of interest to the borrower. Authors also state that there is an affirmative relationship between economic growth and fiscal market, which occurs owing to the financial market being high and the economy of country increases, simultaneously. Barrell, Karim and Ventouri, (2017) further stated the relationship between an ability of financial market in order to redistribute capital and degree of development of the commercial enterprise, in turns, increases economic growth of country. This occurs owing to the financial development of the country having a ratio of size of securities market and credit market to Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

2.1.2 Theory related to interest rate fluctuation

As per the view of Holston (2017), interest rate parity (IRP) is the approach that works behind interest rate. The IRP plays a significant role in the foreign exchange markets that connects interest rates, spot exchange rates, and foreign exchange rates. It is a no-investing situation which represents a balanced state in which the capitalist will be different to interest rates. This theory also works on two assumption i.e. capital mobility and perfect substitutability from both home and abroad assets. Capital mobility is about having an easy and seamless approach to move the capital from one country to another (Du, Tepper & Verdelhan, 2018). The perfect substitute occurs when a situation where two goods are perceived as identical. Pinnington and Shamloo (2016) stated that

perfect substitutes are commodities in the sense that it is impossible to build a brand whereby customers prefer the chosen product. On the other side, Martin et al. (2018) explained the mechanism of profit making by such commercial banks. The authors asserted in their study that commercial banks hold the balance of their customers at some amount of interest which is evidently lower than the interest rate they charge from their customers, while lending money. Addition in the rate of interest rates widens this gap due to which banks become more able to enhance their profitability. The whole concept for the interest rate fluctuation occurs

2.1.3 International theory related to Interest rate fluctuation

Shokirov and Backhaus (2020) stated that neo-classical theory is the international theory in which the interest rate is stated through legislation of decreasing marginal utility. The interest is perceived to be a reward for the use of loanable funds and the rate of interest is set through the demand and supply for loanable funds. This theory explains two laws. The first law is about the intake of a good in high amount which creates an affirmative profit and has a contentment of extra ingestion not being good as compared to previous consumption. On the other hand, another law states that best status where the ratio of dealing of products is equal to ratio of minimum substitute of products (Akhtaruzzaman, 2019). The ultimate effect of such low interest rate results into higher productivity through which the total output of the economy increases. The theory is linked to the interest rate fluctuation in the sense that it reveals how the variation is taking place on an international level in interest rate. The demand and supply of loanable funds decides how the fluctuation will occur and have an impact on the commercial banks.

2.1.4 Comparison of both theories

According to Durdyev and Ismail (2017), interest rate parity theory is an approach, which differentiates the interest rate between two states and is equal to the difference between the progressive dealing rate and spot-dealing rate. This theory shows an important character in the international dealing markets and copulative interest rates and spot exchange rate. While on contrary, neo-classical theory mainly depend upon the classical demand for supply and demand of capital theory of interest (Akhtaruzzaman, 2019). This rate of interest theory also concludes all the monetary and non-monetary aspect of interest. The ultimate effect of such low interest rate is reflected on the higher output of the nation which in turn accelerates the profitable growth.

Xie and Han (2019) argued that the IRP model only anticipates that there is endless finances accessibility, which may be further used for monetary system investment, that is not practical. As a result, this theory also stated that when the future and forward contracts are not available to protection, then it does not hold in the real world. On comparing it with neo-classical theory, it has also been observed that if interest rates remain high for many months than it leads to slow growth rate of business present in the economy. In this manner, interest rate does not only affects economy but it also affects individual every individual entity present in an economy.

2.1.5 Condition of interest rate in commercial banks

In the views of Mehrotra and Yetman (2015), the system of banking of Tajikistan is relatively weak and under-developed. The banking sector of the nation experienced a setback in the year 2014 when economic crisis hit Russia due to which it faced many systemic challenges (Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas, 2017). The country consists of about 16 commercial banks and about 80 micro-finance companies operating and have just one western bank named as “Access Bank” which is a German bank (Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, 2018; Pond, 2018). It has been cited that due to lack of big and renowned banks across the world, the growth of banking system of the country is relatively lower as compared to other Central Asian countries (Du, Tepper and Verdelhan, 2018).

Essl et.al. (2019) specified that interest rates comprise of two types such as borrowing interest rate and lending interest rate. The fee at which commercial banks lend money to the public or organisations is referred to as the lending interest rate, while the fee at which commercial banks accept public deposits is referred to as the borrowing interest rate for banks (Gust et.al., 2017; Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas, 2017). Maxfield, Wang and de Sousa (2018) stipulates that interest is considered as cost for one person while income for the other person. It is basically taken as an opportunity cost wherein the borrower pay for grabbing the opportunity now instead of foregoing the same, which might costs it higher (Macit, 2017). Commercial banks receive deposits from the public on which they pay some interest in order to expand the scale of their investment-related operations and to gain higher profits for themselves (Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, 2018; Memmel, 2017).

Singh and Singh (2016); Guthmann and Fill, (2020) stated that alteration in the interest rates can affect the market in both favourable and unfavourable ways. In addition, interest is

basically taken as a reward for mitigating the risk, which is associated with the non-payment of the money borrowed by people (Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, 2016). When the interest rates at which banks charge low rate of interest, people are encouraged to take more loans and spend on big purchases like homes, cars etc. It means people who have to purchase house, cars, they are ready to take a loan from bank because of lower interest charge (Liu, Wang and Xu, 2017). This is because people have to pay less interest on the amount they have borrowed which increases their capacity of spending more money. The prior argument evaluated that interest rate have a positive impact in the economy as it creates a ripple effect on country's economy. Liquidity tends to increase and money is transferred from household sector to investment sector at a good pace (Anandan, 2018).

Kasenov (2017) highlighted that farmers and businesses are the major beneficiaries of lower interest rates as compare to other entities because low-interest rate allow the farmers and businesses in acquiring capital assets which have high costs that requires extensive financing. As elucidated by Igonina et al., (2016) Tajikistan witnessed high interest rate in May 2017 when the lending interest rate was 32.530 % that significantly affected the entire system. The aforementioned study added that the disposable outgo of the group in such condition decreases and they are discouraged from getting loans or spending more. Furthermore, it has been identified that the country has seen lending interest rate as low as possible in May 2002 when the rate of interest was just 13.097% (Waemustafa and Sukri, 2016; Barrell, Karim and Ventouri, 2017).

Donou-Adonsou and Sylwester (2017); Bech and Malkhozov (2016) argued that higher interest rates is an opportunity for the commercial banks to increase their profitability because financial sector such as retail or commercial banks, insurance companies, investment banks etc., possesses excessive cash in the form of customer balances and businesses transactions. Further, it has been explained that rise in interest rate results in increasing the profitability of such financial institutes due to high cash holdings (Wang and et.al., 2018).

Sheremenko, Escalante and Florkowski (2017) disagree with the view of above authors and critiqued that since gainfulness of the finance sector is one of the benefits of high-interest rates, it shall not be overlooked that high-interest rates decrease the capital which is needed by the banking sector and as a result, it reduces their productivity as well. It has been asserted by Wang, Tsai and Chen, (2019), that higher savings and lower consumption reduce the movement of liquidity and capital, which consequently slows down the growth rate of economy due to

fluctuations in the banking sector and for the fact that there is a direct link between the demand for commercial enterprises and growth of an economy.

As per the studies of Al-Harbi (2019); Bougatef (2015); Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, (2019), central bank plays a dominant role in affecting interest rates within an economy. In fact, it lays down a guiding rate around which commercial banks and their financial institutions have created their borrowing and lending interesting rates. Central Bank is the body in a country that is responsible for keeping the firmness of commercial enterprise system within a nation (Bruszt and Palestini, 2016). In the views of Mukanov and Begaliev (2018), when an economy is progressing at a rate, which might result into hyperinflation, the National Bank raises the interest rates. This is done to lower down the excessive demand of credit in an economy (Du, Tepper and Verdelhan 2018). The aforementioned authors explained the mechanism that when the discount rate is higher, it will be a costly for the borrowing banks to get funds from National Bank, which in turn will squeeze the demand from customer relating to the loans. Moreover, Wang, Tsai and Chen (2019) argued that lower demand would help the country in bringing down the inflation rate to the desired level so that economic growth of the nation cannot be hindered. In addition, this action is required for maintaining the stability of money credit and inflation rate in a country.

Khatat (2016) articulates that when the retail banks or commercial banks borrows from National Bank at cheaper rate, they are enabled of passing the savings to their customers by the way of lower interest rates imposed on personal or mortgage loans etc. This leads to development of such economic environment wherein the customers are encouraged to borrow which subsequently leads to rise in consumer spending. However, Bougatef (2015) argues that lessening in the interest rate have a neutral impact on the investment earnings of the customers. The author says that although reduction favours spending culture in the economy but it also lowers down the income, which the customers are earning from their investments in bank. This sometimes discourages the investors or household sector to put their money as investments in the bank.

2.1.6 Impact of Interest rate fluctuation in Tajikistan

According to Mogilevskii and Asadov (2018); Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, (2016), banking system in Tajikistan has been segregated into two parts namely; National Bank of Tajikistan and second one is commercial banks. The National Bank of the country is the body responsible for carrying out all the country's regulatory functions, while the second level of the banking system,

which is commercial banks, is required to comply with the regulation developed by the National Bank to grant loans or accept public deposits as a primary function (Barrell, Karim and Ventouri, 2017). Moreover, it was elucidated by Bahrami and et.al., (2019) that rate of interest at which commercial banks lends money to people has been decreased over the month that had a positive impact on the business and agriculture sector of Tajikistan, which are considered as two highly contributing sectors of the Tajikistan's economy. When the National Bank, which is Tajikistan's central bank, adjusts the interest rate at which commercial banks lend money, it has a negative effect on the financial status of a nation (Bech and Malkhozov, 2016; Du, Tepper and Verdelhan, 2018).

Shaofeng (2017) stated that the lending interest rate of Tajikistan has been highly fluctuating, as interest rate in June 2018 was 28.940, which increased to 30.210 in July 2018 and then went as low as 20.511 in November 2018, which was again increased to 25.351 in May 2017. This reflects the instability in the credit supply and demand in the country. For instance, Barrell, Karim and Ventouri (2017) stated that one of the commercial bank in Tajikistan has balance of about 50 million Tajikistani Somoni on which 1% interest is given by the banks to its customers. However, the same money have been invested in short-term notes or bills on which, bank is earning 3 %. This gap of 2 % is termed as the profitability for the company. The same thing was experienced by the Tajikistan when interest rates in the country crossed the mark of 30% wherein people limit their expenses and hold back their money as savings. As a result, high interest rate offered by banking sector negatively affected the citizens because people did not get currency from banks and the process of money supply began in an economy, which directly affected the overall economic growth in negative manner.

Mirazizov et.al., (2017) stated the discount rate is the cost that central bank has to pay for borrowing money. When mercantile banks borrow money from the National bank of Tajikistan, they have to pay interest at the discount rate for the intent of shoring up the short period fluidness needs of the banks (Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, 2018). For instance, the National Bank of the country may increase or decrease this rate depending upon the circumstances and condition related to economic pace and growth prevailing in the country. Ahunov (2018) stated that National Bank in Tajikistan is embedded with this responsibility in the country and it is considered as one of the most significant power held by National Bank, which is to increase or decrease the discount rate in the state. Shift in the gain or decrease in interest rate have a massive contact on the building

blocks of state macroeconomics, like spending and borrowing power of consumers (Guthmann and Fill, 2020). The authors added that as of March 2017, the discount rate of Tajikistan was 16%, which is lower as compared to 18 % in December 2016. The National Bank of Tajikistan exercised their power and lowered the discount rate in the year 2017 because of the stagnant or slow pace of country's economy. This decision was taken by the National Bank with an intention to make the borrowing of the funds affordable for the commercial banks so that economy does not get affected significantly.

The prior facts were supported in the study of Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi (2019), as authors asserted that this was the reason why National Bank of Tajikistan increased the discount rate in the year 2017 to 18 % from the previous year in which it was 17.5 % since the economy was growing at good rate wherein for taking control over the possibility of hyper-inflation. In order to stabilise the economy, the National Bank has decided to raise the rate so that demand for credit is reduced (Guthmann and Fill, 2020).

Geraets (2018) cited that, in good economic conditions, people tend to save less and spend more which in turn increases the demand for money credit in the system. The petition gets so high that commercial banks are unable to meet it and for controlling such situation, the National Bank of Tajikistan raise the interest rate so that people get discouraged in demanding excessive credit or borrowing from the commercial banks. The subsequent effect of such higher interest rate is that cost of products in the state is balanced which favour the banking system and system of the nation (Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas, 2017). Hernandez and Vadlamannati (2017) suggested that financial system of Tajikistan is quite shallow. This is because country does not have higher financial intermediation. The deposit and credit penetration rates of Tajikistan was lowered than other regional economies because of country's disturbed history of banking system and government's legacy of interfering in the operational decision making which has resulted into ineffective resource allocations throughout the country (Waemustafa and Sukri, 2016).

As per the views of Wu and Xia (2016), the policies related to the lending of funds are weak in Tajikistan, there is need of effective hazard direction in the banking system and weak corporate governance have altogether resulted into lower productivity from the financial sector in the country. Moreover, with the beginning of recession period in Russia 2014-2016 made the situation worse for Tajikistan wherein many of the commercial banks became insolvent (Wang, Tsai and Chen, 2019; Liu, Wang and Xu, 2017). World's major financial organisations such as

International Monetary Fund (IMF), ERBD and World Bank are offering all the possible assistance to the authorities of Tajikistan for resolving its problems and issues in the financial sector (Guthmann and Fill, 2020; Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, 2019).

2.2 Theory behind fluctuation of Interest Rates

2.2.1 Background

This section defined different theories and models that work behind the fluctuation of interest rates in Tajikistan such that it describes Interest rate parity and classical theory of interest rate. Moreover, it also describes the how the theories create a direct impact upon financial performance of state and reflect that there is a margin between rate provided by central bank and lending loans on certain rate by commercial banks is known as spread and it is also profit margin for commercial banks. Banks are generally free determine interest loans on deposits and on lending rates as based on fed funds rate and other policies prevailing in economy.

2.2.2 Interest Rate Parity

This theory is also work under two typical types such hat uncovered interest rate parity which means that state which influence to international dealing risk is unreserved. On the other side, another aspect is covered interest rate parity, which means to that status in which there is a progressive bid that is used to concealment the exchange rate. In the view of O'Connor (2020), Interest rate parity is the theory, which is a differential between two countries in an equal of the differential between the forward exchange rate as well as spot exchange rate. This also plays an important role in foreign exchange markets, connecting interest rates and foreign exchange rates. Therefore, it can be stated that IRP is a fundamental equation that shows the relationship between interest rates and currency exchange rates. In the same way, each parity represents the best relationship with an implication for future forecasting exchange rates. Then they will definitely lighten an association i.e. Real interest rate parity, which describes the real interest rates. This theory is generally used by many emerging countries to determine the fluctuation in market.

As per Anandan (2018), interest rate parity theory governs the association between interest rate and currency exchange rates. For instance, when one of the state provides high rate of return

in risk as compared to another. At that time, that state who offer high risk will be liable to increase their price in future. Hefeker (2018) said that the second force in determination of interest rates are Treasury Bills, which affects long-term rates. Longer-term loans are of 15 to 30 years fixed interest mortgage loans (Memmel, 2017). These loans are generally for customer loans who wants to borrow loans for purchasing automobiles, education, purchasing large furniture's etc. Interest rates on long-term loans are generally higher as compared to prime rate but decrease than rotate credit charge. These interest rates are not fed funds rate but rather they follow every time change in Treasury Notes Rates (Bougatef, 2015). In which they take highest yield rate and it depends on notes i.e. if notes are high in demand than yield can be low and vice-versa. By this way, treasury Notes Rates are been determined for long-term loans (Bech and Malkhozov, 2016). It has been identified by Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, (2018), that interest rate parity restrict the banks from making easy money as it prevents them from manipulating the differences in currency rate. In the words of Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas (2017), investor activity in asset markets that results in interest parity may also explain why, in reaction to market changes, the exchange rate can rise and fall. In other terms, a model of exchange rate determination can be established using interest parity. This is known as the asset approach or the mode of interest rate parity.

2.2.3 Classical theory

Cochrane (2016); Gust et al., (2017) stated that classical theory of interest rate is another theory, which is completely based upon the demand and supply for a capital. Further, under this theory, the demand side of capital comprises of demand for efficiency as well as for consumptive causes. Further, the efficiency of a capital is also subject to law of variable ration and on the other side, supply of the capital is based upon the savings and it somehow depends upon the determination to save the money for society (Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, 2016). Compared to supply savings, when the demand for an investment fund is immense, the interest rate immediately rises and this indicates the interest rate fluctuation within a nation (Pond, 2018). Stronski (2017) suggested when the demand of a money increases in market, the interest rate offered by the bank decreases because there is a negative relationship between the interest rate and demand. Therefore, this is somehow lower down the economic rate of country because fluctuation in interest rate means people do not invest to purchase product and this in turn not supported the economic power of a country.

On the other hand, Yiheyis (2018); Bech and Malkhozov (2016) comprehended that interest rates also affects economy and individual in that particular economy. There is a direct impact of interest rates on home loan mortgages as when interest rates are higher, the loan payment will also be higher. Moreover, it has been cited by Bougatef (2015) that interest rates and loan payments are directly related to each other as it has been evaluated that the interest rates decrease loan payments of house loans. Interest rates also affects inflation rates prevailing in economy. The citizens must be smart enough to examine situation and lock their money in fixed interest loan in order to stretch more amount of income for themselves (Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, 2019; Waemustafa and Sukri, 2016). It has been observed in the indagation of Bruszt and Palestini (2016) that if interest rates remains high for a considerable number of months than it leads to slow growth rate of business operating in an economy. Hence, it can be evaluated that interest rates do not only affect economy, but it also affects consumers in an economy.

2.2.4 How both theory affect country

Bodenstein (2017); Liu, Wang and Xu, (2017) identified that the banks are the main participants in setting up interest rates on loans taken by borrowers. Commercial Banks borrow some amount of loans from central bank on certain percentage and lend these loans to general public on the rate above than borrowed from central bank. In the same way, Zhao and Wang (2017) comprehended that these interest rates are been set by setting up certain rates as per reserve requirements and buying and selling “risk- free” rates. Interest rates are part of monetary policies and are designed to influence economic activities in a region. Other considerations which bank take at time of setting up interest rates are inflation rates, stock market levels etc. In this manner, bank decides interest rates, which are to be taken by bank on lending funds from individuals and businesses (Barrell, Karim and Ventouri, 2017).

Arteta et al., (2016) said that interest rates theory is generally related to an increase or decrease in percentage of inflation rates in any country. Any country whose inflation rate increases it is directly related to the prevailing inflation rates. As per Waemustafa and Sukri (2016), these terms are primarily related to macroeconomics because they are all major terms that impact the entire economy with the slightest change in any inflation rate or interest rate. Generally, it has been observed that when interest rate is increased, less number of people borrow money from banks, which leads to reduction of inflation rates, on the other hand, it decreases inflation rate within a

nation. The prior scenario has been considered as main issue of fluctuation in interest rates, which affected the economy of Tajikistan (Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, 2019). In any nation, when government wants to decrease the purchasing power of people, it reduces the interest rates and vice-versa (Du, Tepper and Verdelhan, 2018). As cited by Macit (2017), inflation rate was the only prominent reason, which affected the interest rate in Tajikistan.

On a contrary, Malkiel (2015) claimed that inflation is not the only reason for fluctuation of interest rates in any country. Increase in supply along with decrease in demand forces the market to decrease interest rates (Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, 2016). In the situation of decrease in supply combined with increase in demand leads market forces to gain in interest rates. Another cause, which affected interest rates in country, is negative relationship between interest rates and shared prices (Bougatef, 2015). The aforementioned author added that when interest rates increases, bond prices automatically decreases and when interest rates decreases, bond prices automatically increases. Stronski (2017) shows that other factors which affects interest rates is economic growth rate. There is minimum economic growth rate above that rate inflationary pressure starts to increase. The author added that in order to keep interest rates under control, economic growth rate has to be under control. Another factor, rising wage rate has been also contributing to interest rate earning in Tajikistan. This leads to a wage price spiral that inevitably raises interest rates due to shifts in wage rates (Bech and Malkhozov, 2016).

Holston, (2017) said that there are various issues in Tajikistan due to which interest rates fluctuates in any country. These various issues are Federal Funds rate which are been set up by Government. These are rates which are been applied by Government on short-term borrowings that are paid by lenders of short-term loans (Guthmann and Fill, 2020). Interest rates in this case are influenced by buying or selling of securities issued by Government. Government buys more of securities, which helps them to inject more money than lending, and this tends to decrease in interest rates. Djanibekov and Finger (2018) provided their views that when government sells off more securities it withdraws more amount of money from banks and ultimately leads to a decrease in price of interest rates. One factor affecting interest rates in Tajikistan is high unemployment rate, which led to high inflation rates in country that contributed in decreasing the interest rate (Anandan, 2018). The rise in commodity prices has led to an increase in inflation rates, which has resulted in increased interest rates to improve purchasing power across Tajikistan (Wang et al., 2018).

According to Zhang (2018), there is substantial rise in interest rates from year 2013 to 2017. Interest rates in country risen from 5.50% in year 2013 to 16.00% in year 2017. It is observed that there has been approximately increase of 190% in four years, which does not good sign for growth of any economy (Gust et al., 2017; Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, 2019). Economy is again leading to same position where country was having 21% of interest rates in year 2000. If the same increase occurs in Tajikistan, then it will again rise the interest rates up to 21%. O'Connor (2020) stated that Inflation report also shows that interest rates are not affecting inflation rates because it is under control. It also shows that inflation rates are not rising with rise of interest rates in Tajikistan. In year 2000 when interest rates were high than inflation rates were also affected. Thus, it can be analysed that the situation, which occurred in year 2000, can again occur in Year 2017 which means that rise in interest rates can also lead to rise in inflation rates. If same situation takes place then it is not good for Tajikistan because rise in inflation rates is a hint to destructive situation for a economy. Whole economy is affected if there is an increase in inflation rates because it creates problem not only for people living in economy but it also affects other economies, which are related to Tajikistan.

On the other hand, Wang et al., (2018); Bech and Malkhozov (2016); Guthmann and Fill, (2020) identified that not only inflation rates in Tajikistan will be risen but it will also affect other factors such as GDP, exports and imports of country. As per reports, GDP growth rate has been stagnant and not increasing as compare to inflation rate and interest rate in Tajikistan. Percentage of Public Debt has risen which shows that debt is rising leads to purchasing power of consumers (Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, 2019; Macit 2017). As per Shaofeng (2017); Guthmann and Fill (2020), balance of trade within a country has been gone negative and GDP per capita has been diminishing, which is unproductive for any nation. These are certain factors that are affected by increase in interest rates that tends to destructive situation for economy of Tajikistan. Government should try to increase more of exports against imports occurring in country that will help an economy to keep inflationary pressure under control (Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas, 2017; Du, Tepper and Verdelhan, 2018).

2.2.5 Model behind used in order to know fluctuation of Interest Rates

According to Cairns, 2018, there are different models used in calculation of fluctuation of interest rates occurring in economy. A theoretical model of interest rates is money market and

inflationary rates rising in market. In money market, inflation rises due to increase in money supply over real money demand prevailing in market. This approach was given by Milton Friedman where he has taken three assumptions (Cord and Hammond, 2016). The first assumption is that the velocity and demand of money in economy always remains same and never changes. The second assumption is that in lengthy score real results is affected by factors such as employment, capital, technology etc. Third assumption is that the supply of money can be controlled independently because it is determined by different set of factors. It was Milton who insisted that central bank has not increased interest rates with compulsion but it was rather the money because of which interest rates were increased (Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, 2016; Anandan, 2018). All interest rates are then adjusted according to market expectations.

Kuhrt and Buranelli (2019) argued that most of the payment in Tajikistan are made by the bank transfer and payment should be made between two corporates entities using a banking system. Further, due to continuous devaluation of the national currency the demand for loans is also going upward trend. That is why; high interest rate is considered to be one of the highest factor that further contributes to low financial inclusion. The prior argument has been supported by the theory of interest rate in which when the bank stop offering services to their customers, then the demand of the services got affected in negative way (Liu, Wang and Xu, 2017). As a result, it directly affect the economic growth of a country in negative way. Moreover, if the supply is high and then demand of the product is low and as a result, the financial market of the country will remain stable. Therefore, Khatat (2016) also supported with the statement and as a result, there should be inversely proportional relationship between supply and demand. However, bank may provide the financial services to their customers by analysing the financial market.

On the other hand, Keynes (2018) said that theory used by Paul Volker also created 1980-82 recession. Due to high- cost for raising inflation rates led to creation of inflation rates. This shows that Milton's assumptions were more relevant than Volker's shocker rule. Milton's assumptions were related to money supply and demand in long term. It warns that change in currency demand leads to temporary gain in employment but at last, it increases inflation. It assumes that monetary policies are powerful than fiscal policies because fiscal policies only puts main focus on taxation policies. Pond (2018) presented that high spending creates money supply but it creates a deficit, which leads to increase in interest rates of Tajikistan. It also assumes that central bank is more powerful than Government because they are ones who control money supply

in country. Real interest rates does affect inflation rates in economy while nominal rates do affects inflation rates. Real rates rather remove effects of inflation. Expansion of money supply leads to lowering in interest rates and vice versa (Barrell, Karim and Ventouri, 2017; Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, 2018).

2.2.6 Analysis of how fluctuation of interest rates took place

According to Avdjiev, and et al., (2016) the main role of fluctuation of interest rates took place because of banking sector and money in a country. It is mainly due to difference between interbank policy rate and other rates such as collateralised rates, uncollateralised rates. Treasury Bills rates, Pure inter temporal rates etc. Banks fails to recognize difference between interbank rates and other short-term rates and set them as minimum by 4% p.a. It affects the banking productivity in long run because it affects policy rates. Fluctuation of interest rates can also be analysed by petition and demand of money in activity. Shadikhodjaev (2018) shows that if money supply in market is high it means that interest rates will be lower because of which buying quality of public increases. If currency demand in money industry is lower, which means that interest rates are high which affects purchasing power of general public is decreased. There is a direct relation between money supply, interest rates and purchasing power factors, which leads to fluctuation of interest rates.

On the other hand, Jobst (2016) fluctuation in interest rates can also be analysed by investments done by general public in real estate business or share market. If investments in real estate or share market are increasing than it means that interest rates have been lowered. It is shown because if interest rates are lower than only public can borrow loans from banks which leads to ultimately increase in investments. While investment in these sectors are decreasing than it means that interest rates are been increased by central banks. Shadikhodjaev (2019) argued that it is also lead to decrease in borrow of loans by public because it shows that there is less investments in these sectors. Interest rates plays very important role in preparation of monetary policies and sets up whole equilibrium of savings and investments. Also. Lower investments leads to lower economic growth rate for Tajikistan and higher investments leads to higher economic growth rate in near future.

Arteta, and et.al., (2016) claimed that interest rates are fluctuated even because of high inflation rates occur in a country because higher inflation rates lead to high-interest rates. It shows that the buying power of the public is declining at high inflation rates, which reduces interest rates

to lower the borrowing of public loans to raise their savings (Wang, Tsai and Chen, 2019; Memmel, 2017). Lower inflation rates lead to enhance interest rates because if inflation rates are higher than there will be buying quality of public. In order to increase more buying quality of general public by central bank than it has to decrease interest rates (Bech and Malkhozov, 2016; Guthmann and Fill, 2020). In Tajikistan, interest rates have been increased which shows that inflation rates are also been decreased because of which interest rates were increased by central bank to maintain purchasing power of general public. Naifar (2016) stated other reasons for fluctuation of interest rates are demand and supply of money in Tajikistan. The above-mentioned arguments provided sufficient arguments on how the interest rates fluctuation took place in country and these arguments can help central bank of a country to improve their monetary policy in order to reduce fluctuation of interest rates.

2.2.7 Impact of Negative Interest Rates on implementation in different banks or financial institutions in Tajikistan

According to Brunnermeier (2016), negative interest rate is a policy in which value of interest rate is negative and is lower than theoretical price i.e. Zero percent. It is new concept introduced in order to remove financial crisis of country. Negative interest rates leads to high cost for commercial banks. Negative interest rates means that public has to pay for loans borrowed by them from banks on regular basis. These is done in order to keep minimum balance by depositors in their deposit account so that it will banks to lend loans more freely to individuals and businessperson. At the time of deflation, people hold money rather them investing or spending in various business. This leads to price falling due to decrease in demand by buyers and eventually leads to unemployment. Petrick and Pomfret (2016) presented that expansionary monetary policies are set by commercial banks at the time of stagnation in economy. It is further also observed that if deflationary forces are high in economy than interest rates lowered to Zero rates will not be enough. The third theory behind negative interest rates are in order to improve economic growth rate in Tajikistan. Basically, it is applied when all other factors are failed in order to improve economic growth of country. Reducing interest rates to Zero leads to reduction of costs for individuals and businesses to borrow more loans from banks.

Wu (2016) claimed that Zero interest rate percentage not always help in improving economic growth of a country. Many times, it has also been observed that economic output felled

due to Zero interest rates kept by central banks. At the time of financial crisis, it was observed that Zero coupon rates were introduced in order to improve economic growth but it happened opposite of it and there was fallen in growth of company. Lower interest rates than Zero Interest rates may lead to shrink in economy rather than growing in economy. Mogilevskii and Asadov (2018) presented that this impact on profitability of banks and banks is destroyed and almost those banks who especially depend too much on customers deposit to make loans. Negative interest rates is main problem for those financial institutions especially for those whose main aim is still to attract more number of customers on basis of high-interest rates in order to increase deposits

(Wang, Tsai and Chen, 2019; Memmel, 2017). It is simple phenomenon if a depositor is asking for interest rates he would be getting and banks tell him that interest rate is Zero or negative than it will lose interest of depositor to deposit their cash in various financial institutions. Main objective of banks to lower interest rates to Zero or negative is to attract more number of borrowers from financial institutions but in that case, they will lose depositors. In such case, negative interest rates lead to high cost for banks and several business establishment.

On the other hand, Claessens (2018) various other consequences of negative interest rates are that it curtails profit for banks. Main business of any bank is interest rate margins, which is most important source of business of revenue for banks. Negative interest rates means a nonstop decrease in interest rates margins, which decrease in profit of banks. Competition between individual clients and banks of negative interest rates is only profitable to banks that too in some cases while in other cases it is disadvantage to individual client. Naifar (2016) reflected that If individual clients are not satisfied with policies of clients than it will be problem for bank themselves because clients may remove their accounts from banks. At this point, banks not only face high costs of negative interest rates, but also have to face the issue of depositors withdrawing bank accounts (Gust et al., 2017; Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, 2019). Thus, there be a two loss for source to bring destructive interest rates in financial markets. The other reality of negative interest rates is creating uncertainty in financial markets. In such a situation insurance companies gets relatively advantage because mortgage lending business and scarcity of investment opportunities leads for investors leads to further problems in exacerbation.

The researches of Sutyryn et al (2019); Shadikhodjaev (2019) provided the forecast by World Trade Organisation (WTO) based on slowdown of global trade due to interest rate fluctuation. The aforementioned study revealed that global trade would rise more slowly than

anticipated in 2016, growing by just 1.7 percent, well below the April projection of 2.8 percent. The 2017 forecast has also been updated, with trade now projected to rise between 1.8% and 3.1%, down from 3.6% previously. This year would mark the slowest rate of trade and production growth since the 2009 financial crisis, with estimated global GDP growth of 2.2 percent in 2016 (Pogoretsky and Melnyk, 2016). The aforementioned authors added that the WTO specifically considered Brazil as a country in which foreign trade, especially imports, has decreased significantly in 2016. This indicates a correlation between the decline in the number of cross-border loans and the slowdown in global trade. Of course, it is not clear if the trade downturn triggered the fall in lending or vice versa.

Drechsler, (2018) said that when sometimes, there is a negative interest rates then in future it will definitely affect the banks also. The other profits in implementing negative interest rates are additional revenues in trading business. It means that lending loans lead to increase of profits by lending more loans to businesses and individuals. It also lead to increase in demand of hedging or a stronger sign for bringing stability in financial centre. It causes up heal in political parties because they need more amount funding for their parties. At this time bank, provide huge loans without even having authentication of accounts. It has been very diplomatic that low interest rates leads to system development or not. Djanibekov and Finger (2018) justifies that it has been observed even if low interest rates led to positive economic growth rate but then also it lead to very slow growth rate. One such successful example of negative interest rates is in year 2017 in US where Federal Reserve targets its interbank rates to increase and just expressing its intention to increase its rates. This policy of increase in interbank rates leads to increase rate at international level This was happened at time or elections held in US as he promised to improve fiscal policies in order to increase interest rates and inflation rates in country. In this way, negative interest rates also leads to some of positive aspects of bringing interest rates below zero rates.

On the negative side, Tan (2016) again claimed that negative interest rates are not best for country's financial performance and it does not lead to improve in economic growth of country. Banks profits shrinks and also it lowers down trust of public from banks or financial institutions. In addition, borrowing costs of banks have been increased due to penalties imposed by central banks to commercial banks (Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, 2016; Anandan 2018). Commercial banks responses by cross- subsidizing both losses and lowering profit margins for banks by charging high payment transactions fees from clients. This high payment transaction fees can be profitable

for banks but it is not beneficial for clients because they have to pay high charges on payment transactions.

Therefore, Sagynbekova (2017) explain that it may create problem for banks if clients start to lose their interest in banks and it may also lead to removal of bank accounts by customers. The other main reason for unsuccessful of implementation of negative interest rates is to lend loans to any person there who comes for borrowing loans. Banks even lend loans to person who might default in payment of principle and interests in nears future. This is also one of negative point that can affect banks working and may cause them huge loss because of default payments by clients. Thus, in such situation banks should duly take care about their payment that they would be paying back principle and interest rates or not. On the other side, Igonina and et.al., (2016) also state that steps should be taken by banks to keep proper adequate amount of capital in banks are BASEL norms which help in knowing capital requirements in proportion to risk weighted assets. Banks can also use these norms in order to know optimum requirement of capital that is to be required by banks for lending loans to general public.

Abdullah (2015) said that negative interest rates are having both positive and negative aspects in banks at the time of implementation of negative interest rates in banks. If negative interest rates are having numerous of advantages to banks by lending loans to public than on other side it is also having numerous of disadvantages such as increase in borrowing cost of banks, default payment risk etc. Other negative aspect of negative interest rates are that it lowers Government borrowings and it also lowers credit ratings of country. Quinlan and et.al., (2019) explain that Alteration in interest rates also enhance to threat in share market, real estate bubble because of less investment in such sectors. These leads to increase in more negative side of bringing negative interest in banks of Tajikistan in order to remove financial crisis of country because it may create a havoc. It may be possible that it may remove problem for banks but it is not suitable removing big problem of financial crisis for whole economy. Thus, Tajikistan should properly examine scenario of whole economy present in country and then only take decision that whether to implement negative interest rates or not and what will be its impact after implementation on whole economy.

2.3 To analyse the impact of interest rate liberalisation in the financial system of Tajikistan.

2.3.1 Briefing

Interest charge can be expressed either in form of annual percentage basis or as specified of the loan amount which has been outstanding. With the help of liberalisation and globalisation of the world economy, it has benefited many business organisation in gaining competitive advantages by expanding their business operations to the international market across the globe. As per the view of Kim, Sanaev and Babakholov (2018) liberalisation of interest rate is a method in which the monetary authority relinquishes or delegated some of its power or control related to setting or manipulating rate of interest thereby allowing the market forces the power to determine interest rates accordingly. Through Interest rate tool, it enables the financial market of the economy in making proper and effective allocation of its resources. In addition, it ensures measures to be undertaken related to controlling, monitoring, directing as well as managing of cash and capital flow thereby optimising the capital allocation process. It provides a balance between the financial allocation systems of the economy.

On the contradictory part of both Bruno and Shin, (2015), they argued that Interest rate is like a price rate, which is having the capability to perform rationing function thereby undertaking allocating process of the limited supply of all the financial resources in number of competing demands for such resources. Because of liberalisation made in Interest rate, many commercial banks of different economies has to face difficulties and adverse situation in managing their banking as well as financial activities. In case of political colour, commercial banks have to face problems including poor and ineffective management, lack of financial knowledge, lack of risk awareness, low environment related to excessive profits. Under such business or financial environment, there has been a high increase in the level of competition among all the banks. Cairns (2018) also argued that in such competitive environment, the bank competition has been mainly related with making limitation in respect of mastery of deposits, loans, competition in context of non-price it has created high negative impact on the performance of banking as well as financial institution. Due to such interest rate liberalisation, it has resulted in not so strong overall competitiveness of commercial bank along with the existing services phenomenal.

2.3.2 Interest rate relaxation relationship with the financial system

Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas, (2017), states that with the introduction of liberalisation in respect of interest rate mechanisms, its main objective is to provide commercial banks more freedom to perform or act in respect of pricing of their loans, deposits so as to compete with every commercial bank. Moreover, it has been aimed at bringing improvement in the overall efficiency of bank for promoting economic development and growth thus making economy more competitive and strong. As per the view of Jelilov, Waziri and Isik (2016) to maintain adequate as well as fine balance between the existing competitive environment, refuge and condition of the whole banking system, the regime has to adopt effective and cautious approach in relation with the interest rate liberalisation process. At the time of several different stages or methodology of such liberalization, all the mercantile banks were get complete quality to set down all the interest rates of a loan. After the process of relaxation of interest rate was realized, all the mercantile banks has the power to gain full authority.

Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, (2018) disagrees with the statement that though there are some benefits of liberalising interest rate in the economy, it has come up with some negative implications as well. Prior to the liberalization of interest rate, all the dominant and profit making banks are not able to exercise their market power so as to extract revenue in form of rental value as charged from their users because the interest rates were already resolute and specified. Pond (2018) shared their views that all the commercial banks are having thought of either raising or lowering down the amount or rate related to the retail deposit rate, lending rates. It has been set to almost the level same as considered when the change in the rate of policy has been announced. From this situation, it has been assessed that the banking system structure of Tajikistan is highly concentrated. All the dominant banks are having more power and full control over which has been used in negative manner for seeking more benefits out of it for own growth and profitability aspect (Liu, Wang and Xu, 2017; Du, Tepper and Verdelhan,2018).

As per the thoughts of Du, Tepper and Verdelhan (2018), the relationship among the interest rate liberalization, behaviour of banks and process related to the financing of business of small firms has been considered and studied from decades for analysing its impact on the financial system of Tajikistan. In contrast, Kasenov (2017) stated that banks and financial institution lends their capital resource amount to the bigger corporation as well as business firms with the objective

of gaining maximum interest amount out of it. Their main objective behind lending of capital amount to such big firms is that these firms are having good credit score i.e. their credit information is very much transparent as well as credit and trust worthy among the market place. Thus, banks finds such big firms as low information searching cost objectives with high trustworthy benefit (Bruszt and Palestini, 2016; Bougatef, 2015). Another reason for providing financial assistance to such big corporation is that their financial as well as liquidity position is sound and strong enough to repay the entire amount, which has been taken in form of debt or loan. In addition, on the other hand, the cash flow of such big business organisation is more stable and effective, which provides assurance to lenders or financial institutions that no credit default will arise on part of these firms.

As per the arguments made by Gust and et.al., (2017), it has been noticed that Interest rate liberalization may not be able to produce the expected benefits out of accounting as well as business transactions in case when the timing, pace and sequencing aspects are off or not in line with the set defined procedures. All such aspects needs to be determined with the help of degree of macroeconomic factors such as stability, the banking conditions and state enterprise sectors. Furthermore, Macit (2017) state that the capabilities of central banks should be evaluated for ascertaining all the benefits and limitations it has been facing. The impact which the interest rate liberalization process has brought to all the commercial as well as dominating banks can be defined under the category of the impact made on the seller side of the market with the objective such that all the impacts on small firms are defined and known as the impact in context of the buyer side.

As per the Memmel, (2017) study which has been conducted to determine the effects of reformation of such policy from the perspective of buyer sides. By narrowing down of the interest rate gap, it will force all the banks to lend or provide their money in positive manner to its customers so as to maintain their revenue. It is related especially to the targeted small firms, which are having capacity to provide high revenue amount to such banks and vice versa. This will provide affirmative contact on the needs of customers as well as the small firms as they will be better satisfied with such reforms and policy.

Guthmann and Fill, (2020) provides their statements in favour of liberalisation of interest rate and its effect on the financial system in Tajikistan. Investments in excess of domestic savings and economic and financial growth are projected to benefit from the interest rate liberalisation process, which focuses primarily on a liberalised capital account (Bruszt and Palestini, 2016). The

policy of its relaxation had come up with the positive effect on transmission of the monetary policy as followed by Tajikistan. On the other side, Maxfield, Wang and de Sousa (2018) stated that all the policies related to the monetary transmission has become more effective after adoption of policy of liberalization of the interest rate due to improvement methods as present by the government and tough market contest in the finance industrial sectors, newly formed home banks and non-banking business organisation of that economy. The procedure of interest rate alleviation is almost similar and related to the procedure of deregulation of the interest rules thereby having focus on both, and adopting gradual as well as cautious approach so as to hold the firmness and development of the business enterprise scheme of Tajikistan.

On the other hand Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, (2016), disagrees by saying that for determining adequate and relevant sequence of interest rate liberalisation, financial or banking institutions authorities are required to distinguish transactions taking place related to loan and deposit one but also has to make difference between retail and wholesale transactions. By adopting early liberalization of interest rates in respect of wholesale transactions has becomes critical aspect in case of reforming of the monetary policy for the economy. It thus facilitates the development of an interbank market economic indicators, which includes commodity prices, exchange rates, yield curves etc. thus studying impact which liberalisation of the interest rate system has made on the financial system of Tajikistan. Due to speedy liberalisation process in when banking institution faced an issue of lack of expertise at management level which leads to decrease the financial sector and affect the overall economy. Also Pond, (2018) stated that when the process of liberalisation is in smooth way then system of the state will not affected in affirmative manner. On the other side, when the process of liberalisation is increases, then it will definitely leads to reform the policies regarding to financial system of Tajikistan.

As per the ideas provided by Liu, Wang and Xu, (2017), related to Interest rate liberalisation is that bank which sell the services of different commercial as well as financial institution, thereby having significant effects on the medium of exchange argumentation sending. To maintain interest rate liberalisation on good tack it is very much important to have close and good cooperation among all the monetary authorities, government agencies, department who are responsible for bringing constitution changes in the real body of the Tajikistan. Tan, Ji and Huang, (2016) provides demonstrations related to both the theoretical as well as empirical aspects with the aim of depicting that the activity interest rates are more delicate to alteration the charge and

then the policy is decided and thus is less reactive to all the open market operations. The activity of interest rate liberalization as carried on by the financial institutions have power and full control in relation to charge or set different pricing options for their own financial products.

Moreover Anandan (2018) stated that the process of setting price of its deposit and loan by the commercial Banks. Commercial Banks having power only for making a reasonable pricing of the loan amount as an outcome of which the liberalization of the interest rate will be realized. In respect of which Waemustafa and Sukri, (2016) makes comments by stating that by adopting effective monetary transmission mechanism, the economy of Tajikistan can have effective monetary policy reforms for smooth functioning of its financial sector. The interest rate pass through is considered as the first communication performance which has to be modelled for better performance.

In addition, it has been found Nishikawa (2015) by that to be one of the strong transmission channel, which supports advanced economies and its development. To maintain and promote terms firmness, related to such policies have affected the aggregate demand and inflation thereby affecting the financial system of Tajikistan. For effectual running of monetary communication transmission it has be accompanying to the interest rate (Guthmann and Fill, 2020). Thus with increase in the interest rates, it can leads to appreciation in the value of local currency thereby creating effect on the exchange rate pass through. The dealing rate transmission of monetary transmittal has been found to be one of the major channel of monetary transmission in the whole transition economy of Tajikistan, which has provided beneficiary transaction to its financial sector.

However, Wang and et.al., (2018) argued that in the financial sector of the economy liberalizing interest rates is considered as most important cause. It helps financial system thus allowing all the banking as well as financial departments to set policies and reforms. On the other side Arteta and et.al., (2016) also stated that power has been allocated for developing the financial markets in better manner so that credit facility can be allocated which may be used by the users. Therefore, by developing a liberalisation policy, the foreign trade with other countries are also increases with a regular import and export facilities. This is used by the highly developed countries in order to maintain the competition within other countries and it may also leads to lower down the tax rates and less restriction on both domestic as well as foreign market as well. Even the liberalisation process also offer the opportunities for the sector in order to compete internationally and also contribute to the GDP growth to generate the foreign exchange as well. Further,

Barrell, Karim and Ventouri (2017) argues that there is an increase demand of e-banking in Tajikistan and by implementing the same, the country's economy will also increases and as a result, it may leads to provide better working as well as helps to sustain in the competition in a market as well. As per the explanation made by Wang, Tsai and Chen, (2019) related to macroeconomic environment and financial sector, it has been assessed that economy of Tajikistan is very small and vulnerable to shocks such poor business climates. The economy of Tajikistan heavily relies on import functions with its exports having a very narrow base. Tajikistan economy is commodity driven including aluminium, cotton, gold etc. on the large basis. When it comes to import and export functions of Tajikistan, liberalisation of interest rate transmission plays a vital role.

Bech and Malkhozov (2016) stated that the rate of interbank lending accurately reflects situation in context of both the short-term capital supply and demand, which depicts most representative interest rates among the financial markets of the economy of Tajikistan. Thus, it is the main part of interest rate liberalization that interbank lending rate has become criterion of interest rate liberalization for assessing its impact on the financial system of the economy. On the other side, Bougatef (2015) explained that the monetary authorities and agencies are having full control or power related to the interest rate in the indirect manner of which one cannot make use directly for making control over the market interest rate. The central bank on the other hand is having indirect effect on the interest rates that can use of three major policy tools broadly named as open market operations, legal deposit reserve, re discount rate. All these policy instruments are capable of indirectly making interest rate changes and further providing guidance on market interest rates.

On this part Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, (2019) argues that for avoiding or mitigating unstable flows of deposits between the financial institutions, it is essential to not to wait till all the lending rates becomes fully liberalized at the beginning so as to liberalize rates on different deposits types including large time deposits etc. By making early liberalization of rates on the large deposits, it can be justified with the help of fact that one can make efforts for competing on increasing basis with the money market instruments such as treasury bills or repurchase agreements. Also, it has been argued by Nwafor, (2018), that financial deregulation and liberalisation activities can have destructive outcome on the running of the financial system of Tajikistan. Thus it generates the direct relationship between banking sector and financial institutes.

This is done by setting the ceiling amount on the interest rate deposits, which the government has supported to make gain in the motive risk activities by making harmful choice. Moreover, it is supported by Bruszt and Palestini (2016), With the help of financial deregulation and liberalisation there can be a lessening in savings thus deed change in the investment amount. Also, with the decrease in the level of investments, it can bring a decline in the level of employment thus bringing economic stagnation in Tajikistan.

As per the statements provided by Gaddis and Pieters, (2017), increasing bank competition and use of different banking techniques and technology also helps to improve the efficiency to reduce the funding fees. Also, emphasis has been made on making more efficient and proper use of fiscal origin as preconditions for creating sustainable means for bringing in more economic growth and development of the country. Interest rates as set down in the economy is known as price of money which has direct impact on the costs as incurred or associated with the function of financing of the requirements of the working capital. Also, it lays indirect influence as well on the capital structure of many business organisations as well as business firms. Deregulation of interest rates viz. Sharpe and Suarez (2015) critic that To removing of the cap on the deposit interest rates as set down by the authorities can result in increasing tough and high competition among all the commercial banking industry. Also, it has impact in form of increase in both the deposits and loans interest rates.

On the other hand Gopalan and Rajan, (2017), all the problems arising are related to too many regulations as imposed by the higher authorities and high competition prevailing in the market place. As it is already mentioned by author that if economy has too many regulations imposed in it, then it can result in arising of conflict with the competition. Business firms facing constrained in form of regulations have to bear negative impact or disadvantage when compared to all the other business and market players. Regulations have also limited the scope and possibility of conducting operations of different types of financial institutions thereby making high interferences on directly basis with the free competition. As a result, Smart (2017) stated that this will also help to find the interest rate of liberalisation If there is an increase in the competitive forces on regular and at fast phase, then it can be considered as a source of risk which will have a direct impact on the financial system of Tajikistan.

As per the observation made by Nishikawa (2015), it can be said that in the process of financial transaction every participation is having full power as well as autonomy related to the choice in respect of number of structure, flexible manner for meeting needs. Also, it plays significant role in the formulation of market equilibrium interest rate. All the financial institutions which are having pricing power in respect of their financial products and tools mainly refers to the pricing done of deposit and loan by the commercial banks. All the Commercial Banks as well as dominating banks can only make reasonable pricing for the loans amount and will result in realisation of the interest rate liberalization on its own.

However, on the critical note, Alagidede and Ibrahim (2017) argued that the economy which has been characterized with the factor of business subjugation thus increasing minimal interest rates in relation to the rising prices would always focuses on increasing its saving and supply of investible resources in its own economy for the betterment as well as smooth functioning of its financial system. Also, it results in increase in the productivity of investment because such resources are channelled so as to protects and have higher rates of return. Furthermore, it has been argued that financial repression can arises in situation mostly when the economy imposes ceilings on the nominal deposit and lending interest rates at the rate which is much low level as compared to inflation level rate. Thus, such low real interest rates makes affect in form of discourage of savings and its mobilization through the fiscal scheme thereby having negative impact on both the measure and choice of investing and thus influences growth as well as development of the economy on a large extent.

2.3.3 Relative factors behind the cause of fluctuation of interest rate

Holston, Laubach and Williams (2017) say that fluctuation in the interest rate arises due to a factor called inflation. The term inflation means an environment in which the terms of goods and services are increased within in a specific system. This is associated with a concept that as the rate of inflation is increased or prices of services and goods increases, the purchasing power of the people decreases in the country. In short, it means cost of living. Inflation has a significant effect on the interest rates which are predominant in the state and has the capability of fluctuating it to a crucial level. Laubach and Williams (2016) through its studies states that interest rate is one of the way of through which the central bank of the country controls the continuous price rise in the economy. The authors claims that for controlling the high rate of inflation, the rate of interest in a

particular economy is increased. The mechanism of this increase in interest rate is explained by the author in its studies. For example, during high-interest rate, the cost of taking loans from banks will increase which in turn will make the borrowing expensive for the people as they will have to give high quantity as interest to the bank which will left them with lower disposable income. Due to such effect, the demand for such expensive borrowing will be reduced and demand for wealth in the system will also be declined. Kiley (2015) also specifies that a decrease in the money supply will result into lower expenditure on the goods and services by people. The immediate effect of such lower expenditure will be reflected in the lower supply for the goods and services. With the supply being constant and such lower demand, the prices of the available goods and work will fall in the state and through this lower demand, the inflation would be stabilised in Tajikistan. The author says that there is a complete cycle through which inflation is controlled by interest rates which is fixed by the central bank in the nation.

Hördahl, Sobrun and Turner (2016) is of the opinion that supply and demand of credit in an economy largely affects the interest rates. In the context of lending money, increase in the demand of credit or supply shortage results into rise in the interest rates. For example, commercial banks in Tajikistan, if facing higher demand for the credit from its customers, it is very likely that interest rates in the country would go up since the National Bank have to maintain the stability in money supply in the economy. Naifar (2016) argues with the above author and claims that demand and supply is not only the sole factor which fluctuates the interest rates in the state. The author says that national money rate is the factor which affects the variations in the interest rate. National stock rate is that rate which the business institutions imposes on other financial institution for short term borrowings and loans. This rate is fixed by the central bank of the country wherein this governing body may decrease the rate for the purpose of encouraging borrowing in the economy and may increase the rates for limiting the borrowing power of the institutions for stabilising the money supply.

Arteta and et.al., (2016) provides another factor that cause fluctuations in the interest rates of the commercial bank in a particular economy. This factor is saving rates. People have a tendency to save a significant portion of their income for the purpose of meeting their needs in the future. Such savings determine the interest rate in the nation. For example, when the saving rates are increased, people will tend to save more as they would be earning higher returns on their savings, and would borrow less. In such a scenario, interest rates have to be lowered down for the

purpose of compensating such imbalance. Dimic and et.al., (2016) states that saving rates has opposite impact on interest rates when they are reduced. Like when the saving rates are declined, borrowing becomes the necessity of the process of consumption in the economy and as a result interest rates are increased by the central bank for keeping the things reasonable.

Bond market is another reason which is cited by Agapova and McNulty (2016) that creates a fluctuation in the interest rates. It has been said by the author that bond market is considered as law of land when someone talks about debt. For example, countries like Tajikistan when issues higher debt in the name of government, the country has to often make more money for offsetting such debt. The immediate consequence of such higher debt is gain in the money demand which as a result, makes the interest rates to go higher. It is through this way that borrowing environment is kept rational in the country. However, Del Negro and et.al., (2017) disagrees with the opinion of above author and says that alteration in the cash reserve ratio causes fluctuations in the interest rates of the mercantile banks in Tajikistan. Cash reserve ratio means that amount of money which the commercial banks have to to keep with the National Bank. When this authority rises up this ratio, the actual funds available with the banks decreases. This action is taken by the central bank in order to extract out excessive money from the financial/ banking system. The author states that it is the tool through which National bank keep a check on increase in the prices and interest rates.

Economic growth of a nation significantly affects the interest rates as articulated by Gelos and Ustyugova (2017) in its studies. If the country is experiencing good economic time, demand of the credit will be increased. If the lenders i.e., banks does not have sufficient funds for lending it to the borrowers, it will have to increase the interest rates for maintaining the stability of forces which are demand and supply of money in the economy. For example, economic growth rate of Tajikistan in the year 2018 was 7.3 % which is considered as very good indicator of economic prosperity. In such a scenario, the interest rate has fluctuated, like it was 16% in the year 2017 which was higher than previous year i.e., 2016. As per the view of Chemutai and Escaith (2017) the interest rate was increased by the National Bank in order to decrease demand for the credit borrowing. When the demand falls, a stability in the money supply is achieved by the nation through which the inflation rate is also controlled. Such a move is necessary on the part of central authority so that a balance is maintained in the financial and banking system of Tajikistan.

Dong, Li and Yang (2016) argues with the view of above author and stipulates that it is the fiscal policy which is the reason behind fluctuation in the interest rates of the commercial

banks. Fiscal policy refers to the tool through which the government makes adjustments in its expenditure levels and tax rates for the purpose of monitoring and influencing country's economy. The author states that in growing economy, all the businesses requires funds for expanding their operations which makes them to get from commercial banks and fiscal organization. This results into higher demand for the credit in the economy and for meeting such higher demands, the interest rates are made higher for compensating such increased demand. Another author Batsaikhan and Dabrowski (2017) in its studies claims that monetary policy is the major factor that cause alteration in the interest rate. Monetary insurance is a tool of government through which it exercise its powers of controlling the money supply in the economy. It is the statement which comprises action plan taken by government, central bank and monetary system commission of a country in order to power the quantum of wealth that is required to be supplied in an economy and the channels through which such money is to supplied. The macro-economic objectives of a nation such as maintaining inflation rate, liquidity, consumption,, expenditure and economic growth, is achieved through appropriate monetary policy. For example, in Tajikistan, the National Bank modify the demand of currency in order to maintain the rising prices in the country. However, Tarr (2016), states that maintaining over the demand of wealth by the way of monetary policy is ineffective since nobody knows what quantity of money is actually required in an economy to facilitate smooth flow of economic activities at any time. Moreover, there is a confusion how banks use this moeny when it is accessible or changes in the supply and demands.

Chow (2016) provides that recession is the factor which causes alteration in the interest rate in the state. During the time of recession where the economy is stagnant, the central bank makes all the efforts for dealing with this situation. The author says that it is business community which is affected the most by the recession. Sharif, Purohit and Pillai (2015) presented that for restarting and reviving the business & economic activities, the federal bank lowers down the deduction rate, the charge at which banks borrows money from the central bank. The reason behind such low discount rate is to induce mercantile banks to get finances from central bank so that they can lend it to the business organizations. The lower interest rates facilitates the businesses in acquiring capital assets and makes their expenditure quite affordable. The discount rate is kept low by the central bank till the economy picks up and improve. Moreover, this directly shows that due to recession there is a fluctuation of interest rates and as a results, the demand got affected in negative manner and in turns, it may affect the overall economy as well.

However, Sagynbekova (2017) disagrees with the views of above author and claims that risk of default is the factor which determiners the increase or decrease in the commercial banks' interest rates. Whenever a bank lends a loan, it always undertakes a risk which is associated with the non-payment of loan money by the borrower. Those people who have poor history of repaying the loan are likely to show the inappropriate financial behaviour relating to a new loan. Thus, for mitigating such risk, commercial banks lend to gain the interest rates on the debt. Such higher interest rate compensate the hazard which the mercantile Banks takes by lending money to such people who have records of making defaults in payments. Müller (2018) argues that risk is the secondary factor which affects the interest rates, the major factors at macro level are inflation, recession and system development of the state which causes the fluctuations in the interest rates. For maintaining the balance in the economy, it is very essential to adjust the interest rates. Supply and activity of the money credit in the economy needs to be balanced so that economic conditions in the country does not disturbed. Therefore, it is clearly reflected that risk is consider as a factor which creates fluctuation in the interest rates and as a result, it may decreases or increase the interest rate, which impact the total economy of the country in just other manner.

2.4 Comparing the interest rate liberalization of Tajikistan with the neighbourhood countries

2.4.1 Prelude

As per the views of Zhunusova and Herrmann (2018) easing off the controlling measures of monetary policies and releasing a sort of control over the market forces. Further, on this Vercueil (2018) stated that liberalisation of the interest rate may result in becoming a critical step taken by the authorised monetary authorities. It may lead in increasing the amount of liquidity within the economy and that may result in highly anticipation of market within the country's economy. Thus, it may result in increasing the chances of increasing the amount of black money within the economy. Thus, it is required to study the actual position of the country's economy and formulate the policies regarding liberalization of interest rates accordingly.

2.4.2 Interest rate liberalisation of Tajikistan with neighbouring countries

Chemutai and Escaith (2017) has view that it is an essential task to be performed by the monetary authorities of a country to formulate effective monetary plans and policies for the country. An inefficient plan may result in inefficiently allocation of funds and other financial resources within the loan market across the country or availability of excessive amount of financial resources within the financial market of the country. Both the situation would lead in increasing the risk of financial uncertainties within the economy of the country. In addition, Verdiyeva (2018) said that a country's monetary policies need to be framed while taking into consideration current situations of the overall economy along with monetary policies of neighbourhood countries. Formulation of less effective monetary policies as compare to the policies of neighbourhood countries may result in transformation of financial resources of the country into neighbourhood country. It would have direct influence over the aligning of an economy in the global economic activity.

As per the study of Georgiev, Nagy-Mohacsi and Plekhanov (2017) In Tajikistan, the financial market of Tajikistan got affected due to financial crises 2008. At that time, as compared to other countries, many national and international government institutions raised the need of developing effective policies and plans regarding regulation of financial market. It helped in development of Tajikistan's financial market for multi-years. Further, the liberalisation of monetary policies also helped in improving the computers and informational technologies within all over the country by using the financial resources of the country's economy. On the other hand, as per the views of Gabdrakhmanov and et.al., (2016) as a result, if there is a strict monetary polices and higher interest rate, the government failed to raise a huge amount of foreign direct investment within the country. Further, in comparison to other neighbouring countries, the crisis affected the many neighbouring countries in just opposite way. Thus, it can be evaluated that monetary authorities of the country are required to maintain effective and balanced liberalization within the country. It has direct contact over the improvement and growth of the country.

Kuhrt and Buranelli (2019) says that recently Tajikistan have ,liberalised its interest rates for bank that resulted in increasing the assets held by commercial banks by 21.3 times as compare to previously held assets. Further, it also helped in increasing the capital of banks by 7.7 times. Although, due to excessive liberalised interest rate, the economy of the country influenced

in the negative dynamic, it resulted in reducing the GDP rate from 51.6% to 37%. In addition, share of banking sector in the aggregate capital also reduced from 10.8 % to 6.4 %. It lead in reducing the growth of finance body in the land. On the other hand, Shaofeng (2017) stated that by seeing the decrease in the overall economical development in the country, monetary authorities of Tajikistan improved their strategies and plans for the country. It resulted in substantial improvement in the overall economy. It resulted in increasing the amount of investments within the banking sector through which banks gained operational benefits and became able to improve their performance and increase their share in country's GDP. In addition to this, it also lead in reduction of the implicit risk of banks.

By studying the reports of World Bank Alotaibi (2015) said that Tajikistan's government decided to liberalise the economic and monetary policies. It helped in helped the country in increasing the amount of foreign direct investment within the country. It also helped the country in becoming one of the big system of the global. On the other hand, talking about the economy of China, Petrick and Pomfret (2016) said that China increased the controlling measures within the monetary policies. It caused in slowing down the overall profitable maturation of the country. Furthermore, due to lack of liberty in the country's economic policies, country also faced lack of foreign direct investment that slowed down the efficiency of overall monetary and financial market of the country. Thus, it resulted in making the monetary authorities realised that they are required to liberalise the overall monetary policies of the country.

Lee, Park and Shin (2015) realised that for the purpose of acceleration of development in the economy, and pursuing the national development agendas, it is required to formulate effective policies and standards relating to the monetary policies of country. For this purpose, developing countries like Nigeria, Mozambique, Bolivia, liberalised their interest rate with a view to improve the amount of public investments in their commodity market. Formulation of liberalised policies helped these countries in elimination of negative impact of their commodity market and rising up them from decline in their GDP as well. Liberalisation of policies of helped Nigeria, Bolivia, Mozambique, etc. in scaling up the amount of public investments that directly influenced their economic condition positively.

On this, Kim, Sanaev and Babakholov (2018) said that neighbourhood countries of Tajikistan like China, Russia, increases the interest rates over loan and credits. It resulted in reduction in the flow of funds and other financial resources within the country. All these policies

lead in strengthening executive's powers in the other institutions. It helped them in achievement of their strategic goals and objectives in relation to maintain employed dealings with helper. Zhang (2018) has view over liberalisation of interest rate that Russia is one among those economies that have a huge level of influence over economic condition and monetary policies of Tajikistan. Tajikistan keeps participate in the economy of Russia. It reduces its participant from \$ 3.8 billion to \$ 1.28 billion in the year 2015 as compare to the year 2014. Further, as per the reports of World Bank, this participant kept reduced further in the year 2016 as well. It also influenced the export and import market of Tajikistan.

Moreover, Sauvé and Soprana (2018) has a view that in late 1990's the China was one of the high economy country as compared to other Latin American countries. It also resumed its sustainable economic growth through advanced economic strategies and plans. Policies of China involved higher interest rate despite of it substantial capital inflows and demand of credits and loans remained high in the country. Major liberalisation policies of China were liberalisation of restrictions over foreign direct investors and external accounts, liberalisation of interest rate in order to improve the positioning of banking supervision, etc. All these policies resulted in improving quality of monetary policies and improving the impact of these policies over growth of economy of China.

As per the views of Kaya and Woo (2018) a country is required to maintain healthy relations with other countries. As Russia have a great influence over the Tajikistan's economic development, financial and monetary sector's development depends upon the effective monetary policies of the country formulated on the basis of monetary policies and plans of Russia. Banking sectors are one of major factor of Tajikistan having power over the profitable performance of the land. On this Kothari (2018) said that all major transactions of country's economy such as debt repayments, foreign direct investments, international payments, foreign exchange transactions, etc. depends upon the execution of finance body of the state. In order to improve the performance and positioning of banking sectors, the government is required to set the most appropriate interest rates to be applicable over the banks. Thus, it can be said that interest rates set by the monetary authorities of country.

In the view of Bun (2018) there is a good relationship of EU with Tajikistan such that they both developed a strategy for improving the welfare of population of the republic of Tajikistan. As there is a weak institutional reform process and by using efficient intellectual and financial

resources which makes it difficult to achieve equal access in all terms. In the meantime, the domestic financial market of Tajikistan suffered from higher amount of foreign investments in the market that resulted in exploitation of the domestic investors. Therefore, improving and getting best financial resources will help the country to get the results or outcomes in positive manner and the interest rate of Tajikistan also got affected. In this perceptive, Martin-Ortega and O'Brien (2019) said that Afghanistan is one of the neighbourhood country of Tajikistan that have a huge impact over the economic condition of it. Moreover, the monetary policy is also framed by the government of the country which also creates a direct impact upon the money or financial market of the Tajikistan in the term of foreign investment. Additionally, it also encourage the domestic investor so that they may invest their excess funds into Afghanistan. Overall, it is also analysed that as per the view of Cairns (2018) to reduce the negative contact of other country's monetary policy, there is a need to formulate own policies and plans with regards to stable the financial market of Tajikistan so that it may not impact the interest rates and overall economy of the country too.

Thus, it also have impact over the employment rate in Tajikistan. Study shows that liberalisation of interest rate has resulted in increasing the economic growth from 49.7 % to 55.1 % in 2015 as compare to the year 2000. It also resulted in increase in the contribution of banking sector in the from 31 % to 54.6 %. On this Aid (2019) said that with the help of liberalisation of interest rates, the individuals have been encouraged to make a large number of deposits and take loans as well. It has resulted in growth of individual deposits to 55.1 % along with increasing consumer loans to 41.8 %.

2.4.3 Benefits and challenges of accession to WTO in the banking sector of Tajikistan

As per the views of Xie and Han (2019) WTO is world trade organization which is an intergovernmental organisation that has been formulated in order to develop different regulations and laws for monitoring and controlling each type of international business transactions. The essential role of WTO is to act as a forum for negotiating international trade agreements and settle down all disputes among members. Further, Arveladze and Smeets (2017) says that in order to impose effective controlling measures over business transactions of a company made beyond the geographical boundaries, Tajikistan made a step forward towards accession to WTO within the country. Besides it, with the support of international trade centre (ITC) the Tajikistan the accession of WTO ensures smooth running and orderly processing of overall international business

transactions. It also results in positively impacting advancing the negotiation process of the international transactions made by the businesses of Tajikistan.

In the view of Buettner and Madzharova (2018) integrating with World Trade Organization (WTO) which allows the nations to entirely collaborate with other nations for reaping in the benefits of globalization. The author stipulates that entering into WTO would increase the external risks in the context of open market and would decrease social security. This means that when the economy is open, more of foreign businesses would mark their presence in the country as it will be an opportunity for them to explore the benefits of developing economy. In such a situation, the capital markets would be more prone to external risks, fraud and higher fluctuations in the interest rates prevailing in the country. However, Shadikhodjaev (2019) disagrees with the above author and says that becoming a member of World Trade Organisation would make the financial and banking sector highly competitive, which is one of the challenge for the home commercial banks. It is so because the foreign business organization would gain a substantial share in the market of Tajikistan and would lead to lead to a situation where less competitive banking firms would leave the field as they could not beat such highly effective and renowned banking companies.

Sutyryn, Trofimenko and Gubina (2019) articulates that becoming a member of World Trade Organization (WTO) would not rule out the possibility of disputes and conflicts relating to trade. The author provides that country would continue to have trade conflicts despite being the member of WTO. It also states that transfer the private sector into the accession to WTO. Moreover, as a member of international governing organisation, Tajikistan would have to adhere to enormous rules and regulations which would be a tedious task for the law making authorities of the country. This is because they would have to make their laws and legislation which are in line with the guidelines and framework provided by the World Trade Organisation. However, ANDERSON and MÜLLER (2017) disagree with the claims of above author and says that adhering to the rules and laws of WTO would help the country in enhancing its firm establishment in the financial & finance body. This in turn would assist the banking companies in attaining the confidence of investors which as a reason would desire to invest more of their money as an investments in the bank. Such higher amount of money available with the bank would aid in meeting the demand of the borrowers conveniently. Also, there will not any material fluctuations which could hurt the economy in any possible way.

In the opinion of Chemutai and Escaith (2017), accession to WTO or becoming a member

of WTO is that this organization has certain trade rules which does not favours the developing nations. The author states that rules and regulations of WTO may hamper the development and growth of infant industries in Tajikistan. For instance, Tajikistan being a developing economy desires of diversifying its economy by investing more in the financial and manufacturing sector but becoming a member of WTO restricts them in doing so. This is because a protected environment has to be facilitated to the infant industries to bloom which is possible only through tariff protection. Escaith and Chemutai (2017) argues with the opinion of above author and stipulates that free trade between the countries and reduced tariff rates across the members of WTO would make Tajikistan more efficient in the sense that more of exports would be encouraged in the country through which greater amount of foreign capital could be brought in the economy. The effect of such exports and international business transactions would result into higher economic growth in the country. The consequence of such economic growth would be seen in the lower interest rates, higher profitability for the commercial banks since people would have more disposable income for spending on goods and services. Higher expenditure by the household sector facilitates the banks in mobilizing the public deposits into capital investment that eventually leads to higher industrial output of the country. All these things collectively contributes to the GDP of the nation.

Laruelle and Peyrouse (2015) state that with an implementation of the World trade organization rules, every member of the country run in the systematic manner and as a result, it will leads to reduce the inequalities among each nation, though they have different economic conditions. This was considered as one of the challenge which the Tajikistan has faced by its accession to WTO. Also, the country has not still obeyed to the policies of WTO which are related to free trade. The nation has maintained a policy of providing protection to domestic industries without notifying any of its partners. Kuhrt and Costa Buranelli (2019) argues with the above author and claims that becoming a member of WTO has strengthened the economy of the country and has improved the financial system of the nation. Due to the good trade relations with the countries, the country has been able to stabilize the conditions in its economy in relation to inflation. Stabilized inflation has directly impacted the interest rates of the commercial banks which in turn has resulted into higher flow of household income into investment sector which has facilitated higher availability of funds for industrial development in the country.

In this view Chemutai and Escaith (2017) said that WTO provides guidelines and policies

through which appropriate amount of liberalization can be imposed within the financial and monetary market of the country. Moreover, it also leads in creation of appropriate competitive environment among the country along with maintenance of sufficient amount of financial resources. It also leads to spread the understanding of good practice of rules and regulations of financial sectors and different international trade practices. Therefore, it can be stated that accession of WTO in Tajikistan leads to improve the efficiencies of international trade practices within financial service sectors like banks and other corporations that provides financial services to their clients.

On the other hand, as per Sauvé and Soprana (2018) at the time of accession of WTO, a programme was organised in which a training session on “WTO Accessions and their Business Implications - Lessons from Other Countries” was organised. This session was having a major focus on the process of WTO accession. It also provide knowledge regarding various benefits and challenges that are needed to be analysed before implementation of accessions to WTO. Organisation of this session resulted in spreading appropriate knowledge among all commercial banks, through which they became able to implement and face all the challenges effectively and perform build their new policies and procedures in this context easily. Further, as per the views of Lu (2018) Tajikistan have a view that the accessions to WTO resulted in involvement of remittance to be transferred through the banking system that is important part in increasing the contribution of finance sector in the GDP growing rate of the land. Besides it, it also helped in increasing the productivity of banking sector as a whole that leads in improving the chances of potential growth of the banking sector.

The Georgiev, Nagy-Mohacsi and Plekhanov (2017) said that accession to Tajikistan was in the year 2013, ITC contributed in the implementation of all complex reforms of this accession and helped it in building the ability of banking sectors to gain further benefits from accessions to WTO. It also lead in enabling the banks in making effective contribution in the economical maturation of the land. Whereas, Gonzalez (2017) has a view that ITC played an essential role in assisting the banks in making active participation of the banks in performance of negotiation process of accessions. Along with this, it also helped the banks by providing appropriate guidelines regarding formations of their policies regarding maintenance of sufficient amount of foreign investment, domestic investment, commercial loans etc. It also help in improving the performance of overall banking sector of Tajikistan.

Further, as per the views of Figueiredo and Lima (2017) WTO accession in Tajikistan resulted in improving the quality of building effective plans and formulation of different regulations by banking sectors in order to improve the growth of country's economic and financial conditions as a whole. At the time of accession to WTO, the Tajikistan's government signed a memorandum contract. Del Negro and et.al., (2017) also states that this contractual agreement contains details that provides proper guidelines to implementation of economic reforms, trade development and investment along with technical assistance. Therefore, it can be analysed that with the help of analysing and evaluating each clause included in the memorandum of WTO accession and understand the guidelines regarding formulation of policies in context to setting different interest rates, export import policies, etc. It resulted in formulation of more effective strategies through which they can improve their workings.

As per the views of Pogoretsky and Melnyk (2016) accessions to WTO resulted in partnering of the country with Asian development banks. It helped them in taking all the necessary steps for developing coordination and co-hosting among the domestic banks with the Asian development banks. It helped banks in making rising the efficiencies of mercantile banks in formulation of policies and setting the rates with a view to spread sufficient amount of financial resources within the world. Further, Siddiqui (2019) also said that WTO realised that lower amount of investment is leading situation featured by Tajikistan's banking sector. Thus, WTO made the banks to develop their strategies and plans for the private, small and medium sized enterprise so that they can gain substantial amount of expansion.

Furthermore, as per the views of Smart (2017) with the help of accession to WTO by Tajikistan, the monetary authorities of country started developing their monetary policies, set plans regarding implementation of taxation system, judicial regulations regarding international transactions, etc. Further, with the help of guidelines mentioned in the memorandum of contract, Government of Tajikistan also became able to liberalize their monetary policies. Further, in this context, Grant and Boys (2015) has a view that with the accession of WTO, the overall businesses could become able to grow at the potential rate. On the other hand, as the development of different businesses have direct impact over the growth of financial and trading market of the country, it leads to drive up the trade and economic development and investment in all over the country. In this order, it can be said that the accession leads to improve the trade investment within the monetary and financial market of the country that positively influenced the banking sector of

Tajikistan.

Bruszt and Palestini (2016) also talked about the benefits gained by the banking sectors in lieu of accessions to WTO within the monetary system of the country. As per their views, partnering of Asian development bank with Tajikistan, resulted in improving the quality of its domestic banks in developing effective plans and procedures for controlling the flow of money within the country. Further, this partnership also make the banks to liberalise their policies for different types of businesses and individuals. This step helped the banks in increasing the amount of commercial and personal loans taken by different persons of the country. Thus, it can be evaluated that accession to WTO in Tajikistan leads in providing great benefits to overall banking sectors of the country. In this context, Shadikhodjaev (2018) said that the implementation of rules developed by the world trade organization within the operations of banking sector helps the banks in improving the knowledge of its managers, board of directors and other members of its management team in developing more effective plans to be implemented over the banks at the time of providing services to their customers. It results n increasing the attraction of population towards policies of bank. Thus, banks become able to increase their number of customers and amount of investment by this way. Hence, accessions to WTO results in development of effectiveness in the bank regarding attracting a large number of customers and improve their value of business as well.

On the other hand, Naseer (2017) also have view that implementation of WTO regulation within the trade regulations of international business of the country results in implementation of some rigid rules and regulations of the foreign companies. It affected the value of trades and amount of foreign direct investment within the country. In this order, due to involvement of trade policies upon several businesses of country resulted in increasing difficulties for different business organisation who either imports or exports their goods and services across the geographical boundaries. Thus, it negatively influenced the economic growth of Tajikistan.

In this context, Wignaraja and et.al., (2018) also said that through different policies of monetary authorities of the Tajikistan formulated on the basis of rules and regulation of WTO, resulted in reduction of tax rate over the cotton industry. As the Tajikistan is one of the largest manufacturer country of cotton, the banking sector have a huge impact of cotton industry. With reduction in tax rate, the prices of cotton also went down that helped the cotton traders in increasing their revenues from export of cotton. In this regard, Shaofeng (2017) shows that this accession to WTO in Tajikistan helped the cotton industry in improving their exports. Therefore, it can be said

that with the WTO helped the cotton industry in bringing more value of foreign currency within the country. In this regard, with the implementation of WTO Tajikistan leads to gain economic growth at a large level.

Del Negro and et.al., (2017) said that WTO accession contract sanctity and adequate intellectual property right protections remain elusive. Further government of Tajikistan also obligatory arbitrary trading policy in order to prevent the partners because they sell it without notifying their partners. As per the view of Escaith and Chemutai (2017) banking and financial authorities formulated effective strategies and plans, Tajikistan effectively faced recession and helped its banking sectors in improving its stabilization. The effective plans formulated on the basis of policies and guidelines of WTO resulted in increasing the nominal lending rates about 27 % for providing loans in national currency and 18 % for providing loans in other currencies such as dollar. On this Liu, Wang and Xu, (2017) said that the commercial banks were restricted by WTO to restrict the amount of to be borrowed. It resulted in increasing the inability among the small and medium sized business enterprise in borrowing loans for performing their normal business transactions or expand their business. It resulted in becoming a challenge for the commercial banks as reduction in their business operations and amount of profit to be gained by them in lieu of interest on loan taken by business.

Moreover, as per the view of Gust and et.al., (2017) Because of liberalisation made in Interest rate, many commercial banks of different economies has to face difficulties and adverse situation in managing ttheir banking as well as financial activities. Due to political reasons, banking sector have to face various problems including ineffective operational management and risk management. Further, due poor environment relating to generation of excessive profits. On this Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas, (2017) argued that WTO accession in Tajikistan resulted in imposition of liberalisation within the monetary policies of the country, leads to provide commercial banks more freedom to perform or act in respect of pricing of their loans, deposits so as to compete with every commercial bank. Also, it has been aimed at bringing improvement in the overall efficiency of bank for promoting economic development and growth thus making economy more competitive and strong. After the process of liberalization of interest rate was completed, all the commercial banks has the power to gain full authority. It helped commercial businesses in growing with a rapid rate as liberalisation resulted in increasing the number of borrowers. Besides, by charging appropriate rate of interest, they also become able to generate

appropriate amount of profit from it.

Arteta, and et.al., (2016) said that by implementing WTO within the Tajikistan will definitely help to increase the economy of the country because it will provide large amount of foreign investment and it will increase the supply as well. The effect of such exports and international business transactions would result into high development of state. It would result in a rapid growth of overall economy of the country through which banking sectors could grow themselves easily. In this context, Bruno and Shin, (2015), argued that WTO makes its each member state to formulate policies in uniform manner. It may provide negative effect over any specific economy whose condition may not be appropriate for the policies framed as per the regulations of World trade organisation. It may also have a direct impact over the business of commercial banks of a country.

Abdullah, (2015) has a view that being a member of world trade organisation, Tajikistan would have to adhere to enormous rules and regulations which would be a tedious task for the law making authorities of the country. It leads to ineffective rules and regulations of the country. It can be caused due to guidelines provided by world trade organisation on the basis of which each monetary policy of the country. Besides it, Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, (2019) argued that regulations and policies of WTO leads to improve the efficiency of banks and other financial and monetary institutions in formulation of laws and plans with the help of which they can gain a rapid growth. Also, it can also help in increasing the economic growth of the country as a whole.

2.5 Limitation of the review framework address by the study

As discussed above, the theoretical framework have their own limitation, such that the interest rate parity theory is criticized because of many assumptions which are further do not based upon the real market. As a result, it also consider the aspect when there is an gain petition for the prevalence with a high involvement charge results which has its hold against other medium of exchange which have low interest rates. Moreover, as theory is completely based upon the two currencies which have their different interest rates and there will a difference that further lead to discount and a premium exchange rates so that it may avoid arbitrage opportunities. On the other side, Liu, Wang and Xu, (2017) stated that the classical theory of interest has their own limitation such that the most difficult defect with the classical theory is to disregard of the influence of

alteration in outgo on saving and investment. Like, the balance charge of interest and the level of income is actually determined simultaneously and they are also interrelated.

2.5.1 Conceptual framework

2.5.2 Thematic Table of Literature

Sources	Main Themes	Sub-Themes	Description
<p>Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas (2017)</p> <p>Du, Tepper and Verdelhan (2018)</p> <p>Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, (2018)</p> <p>Gust et al., (2017)</p> <p>Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi, (2019)</p> <p>Liu, Wang and Xu, (2017)</p> <p>Holston (2017)</p> <p>Barrell, Karim and Ventouri (2017)</p> <p>Martin et al., (2018)</p> <p>Shokirov and Backhaus (2020)</p> <p>Durdyev and Ismail (2017)</p> <p>Xie and Han (2019)</p> <p>Mehrotra and Yetman (2015)</p> <p>Kasenov (2017)</p> <p>Igonina et al., (2016)</p>	<p>Impact of variation in Interest Rate in commercial banks</p>	<p>Condition of Interest Rate</p>	<p>The first and foremost theme of this literature was to examine the current condition of interest rate by highlighting the theories pertaining to interest rate which can aid the readers in identifying the direct impact of those conditions on interest rate. The interest rate parity theory has been referred to conceptualise the conditions that fluctuates interest rate in the market. While, the classical theory has been referred to identify the international perspective related to interest rate fluctuation.</p>
<p>Mogilevskii and Asadov (2018)</p>			

<p>Jelilov, Waziri and Isik (2016)</p> <p>Bahrami et al., (2019)</p> <p>Bech and Malkhozov (2016)</p> <p>Du, Tepper and Verdelhan (2018)</p> <p>Shaofeng (2017)</p> <p>Barrell, Karim and Ventouri (2017)</p> <p>Mirazizov et.al., (2017)</p> <p>Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl (2018)</p> <p>Ahunov (2018)</p> <p>Guthmann and Fill (2020)</p> <p>Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi (2019)</p> <p>Caballero, Farhi and Gourinchas, (2017)</p> <p>Waemustafa and Sukri (2016)</p> <p>Wang, Tsai and Chen (2019)</p> <p>Liu, Wang and Xu (2017)</p>		<p>Direct Impact upon interest rate</p>	<p>rate discussed in prior theme. After thorough examination of various studies, it has been identified that inflation rate, investment, savings rate and price of securities are major determinants that directly influences the interest rate.</p>
<p>Kim, Sanaev and Babakholov (2018)</p> <p>Bruno and Shin (2015)</p> <p>Cairns (2018)</p>		<p>Impact of Liberalisation</p>	<p>The third sub-theme discussed the impact of interest rate liberalisation on the financial system of Tajikistan. The major focus of this theme was on providing detailed argumentation on positive as well as negative impact of interest rate liberalisation. It has been found that Interest</p>

<p>Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl, (2018)</p> <p>Bruszt and Palestini (2016)</p> <p>Bougatef (2015)</p> <p>Macit (2017)</p> <p>Guthmann and Fill, (2020)</p> <p>Memmel, (2017)</p> <p>Jelilov, Waziri and Isik, (2016)</p>			<p>payments may be calculated either on an annual percentage basis or as the remaining amount of the loan has been outstanding. With the aid of global economic liberalisation and globalisation, many business companies have benefited from gaining competitive advantages by extending their business activities around the world to the international market.</p> <p>Additionally, it has been identified that interest rate liberalisation is a process by which the monetary authority delegates some of their powers or controls pertaining to fixing or fluctuation of interest rates, thus enabling market forces to decide interest rates accordingly. It helps the economy's financial market to make a proper and efficient allocation of its capital through the tool of interest rate.</p>
<p>Wang, Tsai and Chen (2019)</p> <p>Memmel (2017)</p> <p>Claessens (2018)</p> <p>Naifar (2016)</p> <p>Gust et al., (2017)</p> <p>Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi (2019)</p> <p>Xie and Han (2019)</p> <p>Mehrotra and Yetman (2015)</p> <p>Kasenov (2017)</p> <p>Igonina et al., (2016)</p> <p>Pogoretsky and Melnyk, (2016)</p> <p>Drechsler (2018)</p>	<p>Fluctuation in the interest rate</p>	<p>Fluctuate according to economic condition</p>	<p>The second theme debriefs the economic condition that encourages Tajikistan to fluctuate their interest rate. The primary rationale for discussing this theme was to explore the banking system of Tajikistan. Tajikistan's banking system is relatively small and under-developed. In the year 2014, when the economic crisis struck Russia, the nation's banking sector suffered a setback because it faced many structural challenges. The country consists of approximately 16 commercial banks and approximately 80 operating micro-finance companies and has only one Access Bank in the West, which is a German bank. The development of the country's banking system is comparatively lower than that of other Central Asian nations, given the lack of presence of large and renowned banks across Tajikistan.</p> <p>This theme discusses two kinds of interest rates, such as the borrowing interest rate and the lending interest rate. The fee at which commercial banks lend money to the public or organisations is referred to as the lending interest rate, while the fee at which commercial banks accept public deposits is referred to as the borrowing interest rate for banks. In terms of fluctuation of interest rate, the findings reflected</p>

<p>Djanibekov and Finger (2018)</p> <p>Tan (2016)</p>			<p>that fluctuation in interest rate affects the market in both favourable and unfavourable ways. Interest is simply taken as a reward for mitigating the risk associated with people's non-payment of the money lent.</p>
<p>Du, Tepper and Verdelhan (2018)</p> <p>Shaofeng (2017)</p> <p>Barrell, Karim and Ventouri (2017)</p> <p>Mirazizov et.al., (2017)</p> <p>Drechsler, Savov and Schnabl (2018)</p> <p>Ahunov (2018)</p> <p>Guthmann and Fill (2020)</p> <p>Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi (2019)</p> <p>Martin et al., (2018)</p> <p>Shokirov and Backhaus (2020)</p> <p>Durdyev and Ismail (2017)</p> <p>Xie and Han (2019)</p> <p>Mehrotra and Yetman (2015)</p> <p>Kasenov (2017)</p> <p>Igonina et al., (2016)</p>		<p>Theories behind fluctuation in interest rate</p>	<p>In order to comprehend the fluctuations in interest rate, two theories such as Interest Rate Parity and Classical theory were referred. By reviewing the relevant sources, it has been found that the theory of interest rate parity is a difference between two countries equal to the difference between the forward exchange rate and the spot exchange rate. This theory plays an important role in linking interest rates and foreign exchange rates to the foreign exchange markets. Moreover, it has been revealed that IRP is a fundamental equation that illustrates the relationship between interest rates and exchange rates.</p> <p>In addition, the classical theory is entirely based on demand and supply of capital. The production side of capital composed of production for efficiencies as well as for consumptive reasons. The productivity of a capital is also subject to the rule of variable ration; on the other hand, the supply of capital is dependent on savings, which relies on the willingness to save income for society. Therefore, when demand for an investment fund is enormous compared to supply savings, the interest rate rises immediately and this demonstrates the interest rate fluctuation within a region.</p> <p>To summarise, this theme expanded the process behind fluctuation of interest rate via referring two relevant theories such as interest rate parity and classical theory. In this theme, it has been specified that banks are the key actors in setting interest rates on borrowers' loans. Commercial banks borrow certain amount of loan from central bank and lend them to the general public at higher rates than those borrowed from central</p>

			banks. By referring to two theories and relevant studies, the reasons behind fluctuation of interest rate are the disparity between the interbank policy rate and other rates, such as collateralized rates and uncollateralized rates; high rise in inflation rates and investments done by general public in real estate business or share market.
<p>Petrick and Pomfret (2016)</p> <p>Brunnermeier (2016)</p> <p>Wu (2016)</p> <p>Mogilevskii and Asadov (2018)</p> <p>Wang, Tsai and Chen (2019)</p> <p>Memmel (2017)</p> <p>Claessens (2018)</p> <p>Naifar (2016)</p> <p>Gust et al., (2017)</p> <p>Khalid, Shehzad and Naqvi (2019)</p> <p>Sutyurin et al (2019)</p> <p>Shadikhodjaev (2019)</p> <p>Pogoretsky and Melnyk, (2016)</p> <p>Drechsler (2018)</p> <p>Djanibekov and Finger (2018)</p> <p>Tan (2016)</p>		Positive or Negative Impact	<p>After detailed analysis on the theories, models and reasons that causes fluctuation in interest rate, this theme highlighted the impact of negative interest rate on the financial institutions of Tajikistan.</p> <p>Negative interest rates are policies where the value of interest rates is negative and below the theoretical price, i.e. 0 percent. This idea was adopted to eradicate the country's financial crisis. For commercial banks, negative interest rates contribute to high costs. Negative interest rates means that the debtors has to pay on a daily basis for loans borrowed from banks.</p> <p>The percentage of zero interest rates does not always aid in boosting a country's economic development. It has been revealed that several times, economic performance has declined because of the zero interest rates held by central banks. At the time of financial crisis, the zero coupon rates were implemented to boost economic growth, but it had a negative impact on an economy of Tajikistan.</p>

Jelilov, Waziri and Isik (2016)			
Anandan (2018)			
Sagynbekova (2017)			
Igonina et al., (2016)			
Abdullah (2015)			
Quinlan et al., (2019)			

Table 1: Tabular Thematic Analysis of Literature Review

2.6 Summary

It can be concluded that financial liberalisation is prominent feature in both formed and underdeveloped state. This study aimed is to determine and examine quantitative and qualitative impact upon the financial institution and countries. Financial liberalisation is characterized as a gradual activity of liberalising financial economy of the land; there are different legislature activity, which secure business liberalisation occurring at various time period. Thus, with help of chief constituent investigation, identification of individual most essential factor serving as agent for business liberalisation and business improvement can be done. In this competitive world by using process of liberalisation and globalisation of world economy, it provides several benefits to many business organisation in form of competitive advantages, market share etc.

In addition, it provides supports to business firms thereby expanding their business operations to the international market across the globe. Unless and until financial institutions brings update in themselves as needed, it is difficult for them to last and vie in the global activity. In this context, the study provides an overview of how the banking industry is outsourcing its activities to different sectors in both domestic and international scenarios. The study gives information with knowledge of how financial sector can sustain in market and helps in developing suitable methods on outsourcing of financial services by bank (Heagney, 2016). The examination presents different model related to interest rate that show the effects of variation in interest rates on economic growth in developing countries especially Tajikistani case. The report has reflect the annual report related to Tajikistan's bank from 1990 to 2015 from the National Bank of Tajikistan, National Bureau of Statistics and World Trade Organisation.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

Methodology is defined as a process or method for conducting a research study. It is known as systematic description that provides foundation for successful execution of research project. The chapter will describe the different approaches used in consideration with explanation regarding process of collecting data and analysis for making study more effective and meaningful to others as well. Therefore, using research methodology helps to get a solution of the problem and using a specific technique would help the researcher in collecting information that is relevant to the topic. Moreover, this chapter includes philosophy, approaches, strategies, design, data collection and methods of analysing the data, along with highlighting the sampling method. The entire approach of collecting the data enables in conducting the research in more precise manner and researcher achieved the defined aim and the objectives in better manner. Therefore, to reach the aim and objectives, researcher specifies each and every term with proper justification.

3.1 Selection of research methods

For completing the research study, different method as well as procedures needs to be followed. Based on empirical literature and theoretical in respect of finance segment, hypothesis has been surveyed by keeping in view to provide a better knowledge of an empirical result that needs to be gathered. The next step involves compiling all data gathered as per requirement of research report. The annual data has been taken from 1999 to 2014 that are utilised for enabling empirical analysis for the long run. In addition, it is the time period that encompasses pre-reform era which depicts financial repression and involves post reform era which reflects as financial liberalisation indication. Prior to an application of formal type of econometric methodology, it seems as essential to assess the behaviour of data by use of correlation and different descriptive statistical tests (such as mean, standard deviation, variance etc.) which helps in making detailed analysis of data (Fletcher, 2017).

The empirical undertaking in validating this assertion would include co-integration analysis by using the co-integration approach. This approach of co-integration allows researcher in making proper analysis into an existence of a stable long-term relationship between different pertinent variables that is financial development proxies, liberalisation proxies, rate of interest, savings, investment and growth. Therefore, for generating financial liberalisation index, study adopts and makes use of the combination of variables relevant to internal financial liberalisation process of economy.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy refers to a notion through which scholar collects, assess and analyses relevant data required for completion of the study. It is mainly categorised into four parts which are interpretivism,

positivis, realism and pragmatism. Using the mixed approach in which both qualitative and quantitative research helps in finding out practical solutions for overcoming the limitations of the mono-method research that is discussed for last 50 years. By using this research philosophy, researcher may easily analyse the assumption of the selected respondents in order to achieve a defined aims & objectives in an appropriate manner. Further, through research philosophy, researcher may address all the issues which are involve in a dissertation and this also involve to being aware and formulating the beliefs as well as assumptions.

This research study is based on comparative analysis, positivism philosophy that adheres to particular research part subject having focus on surveys, statistical data collected and questionnaire. In addition, emphasis is made only on factual knowledge as gained through observation including measurement (Holston, Laubach and Williams, 2017). In comparative analysis study, role of an investigator limits to collection of data and an interpretation through the objective approach & research findings are seen as quantifiable and observable. Therefore, it clearly reflect that using assumption and beliefs, researcher may easily attain the defined aim and objectives in better manner and also conduct the research in better manner. Moreover, by using correct philosophy and using SPSS as a statistical tool will help the researcher to generate the best results.

The second type of research philosophy is realism, which is an idea of independence reality from a human mind and such philosophy is based on an assumption. However, interpretivism philosophy, which also includes a researcher for interpreting an element of the study and it also assume the access of a reality as well (Kumar, 2019). Moreover, this research philosophy also enables scholar to interpret the results based on questions so that researcher may easily reflect on the different aspects of the issue.

Cyr (2016) discussed the fourth type of research philosophy that is pragmatism. Pragmatism philosophy is a concept that is considered relevant if it is able to support the action. This particular philosophy understands that there are numerous different ways of interpreting and conducting the research. There is no one view that can provide the entire picture as every way has the aspect of providing multiple realities. Within pragmatism, there are positivism and interpretivism that provides the researcher with the freedom to integrate more than one research approaches and research strategies.

Researchers on choosing positivist approach in study define independent thoughts related to the subject matter which can be purely objective. Positivist approach of philosophy covers scientific part having its focus on collection of data via surveys, questionnaire and statistical means. Independent means as maintained minimal interaction with research participants at the time of carrying on research process. Interest rate tool enables financial market of the economy thereby helping in providing proper and effective allocation of available resources. Further measures to be undertaken in respect of cash and capital flow and its controlling, monitoring, & managing for having optimum capital allocation supporting smooth functioning of financial sector.

3.2.1 Justification for the research paradigm and methodology

Research paradigm refers to an approach that relates to framing of research project having need to cross-examined and verified from research commodity side. Positivism also refers as logical positivism defines scientific method for establishing truth and reality of objective (Bresler and Stake, 2017). Positivism is based upon view that science is only foundation for true knowledge as well as understanding that contains methods, techniques and procedures as used in natural sciences. It offers best framework for investigating the social world related to the topic. It reflects strict empirical approach providing knowledge that is based directly on experience, facts and causes of behaviour. Positivism approach is concerned with scientific method to study of human action, its meaning etc.

Shift from positivism to post-positivism has been observed in mid-20th century. Post-positivism as per the dogmatic view of positivism states that turning emphasis from absolute certainty to probability can constructs knowledge, better understanding rather than process of laws of nature noting (Ledford and Gast, 2018). As per Post-positivism approach, strict adherence to scientific method research is not enough, as research outcomes are neither objective nor unquestionably certain. Post-positivism process is influenced by philosophy known as critical realism as distinguished from positivism as per focus made on theory verification or falsification (Fletcher, 2017). As per critical realism, observations may involve error and mistakes resulting in modification in the theories.

Objectivity can nevertheless be achieved by using multiple measures, observations to gain clear understanding of what is happening. To maintain proper balance in between existing competitive environment, safety and soundness of the whole banking system, it is required on part of government to adopt effective and cautious approaches in line with liberalisation of interest rate (Kumar, 2019). In discussion below, two are treated as belonging to the same family. In mixed research process, researcher makes use of combination of quantitative and qualitative research methods, approaches in completing single research study. The qualitative and quantitative parts of a research study can be conducted concurrently i.e. conducting both parts at same time or in proper sequence so as to address a research question effectively & provides positive value to researcher.

Macroeconomic analysis before Keynes was limited to monetary theory under which neoclassical quantitative theory of money dominated. The initial prerequisite for neoclassical macroeconomic analysis was full employment of labour and other factors of production; the percentage was treated as a phenomenon of real economy, balancing supply and demand of capital effect of changes in money amount done to influence price level (Meredith, Mantel Jr and Shafer, 2017). Keynes considered savings and investments as a process, which is determined by different factors, whereas investment and savings does not, depends on ratio of interest rate and marginal efficiency of capital. Liberalization of interest rate cannot produce

expected benefits from accounting & business transactions with situation including timing, pace and sequencing are off or not in line with the set defined procedures.

As per modern portfolio theory, problem of portfolio optimisation aimed to minimise risk at a given average profitability level related to business as well as financial sector. In addition, the market portfolio is a set of all available forces present at the moment the investor securities is effective. By having combination of market portfolio along with risk-free asset provides efficient portfolio with less risk and less expected income (Litosseliti, 2018). This approach is related to macroeconomic, since its main object is distribution of aggregate capital in the economy into 2 forms viz. cash and non-cash i.e. in the form of securities.

The economic, monetary and fiscal policy impact on economy that is largely transferred with help of mechanism of money and securities markets. By creating solid and empirically applicable framework for research on the functioning of the money and securities markets it has been able to make improvement in overall efficiency of bank for development and growth of the economic sector thus making it more competitive and strong (Nwafor, 2018). Furthermore, emphasis is made on changes taking place in these markets affect consumption, investment, production, employment and the economic growth. During different stages of such liberalization, all commercial banks were given more and full power to set down all the interest rates of their deposits and loans as well. Therefore, to determine the exact situation, it is quite necessary to use pragmatism theory in which the statistical data as well as the non-statistical data has been analysed. For the statistical data, the SPSS tool has been used which would provide an insight related to the direct relationship between all the factors. For the non-statistical data, the thematic analysis has been used in which responses from participants have been analysed by categorising them in specific themes in light of the aim and objectives of the study.

3.3 Research approach

It is related with concept and procedure that consist of assumptions necessary for undertaking research process such gathering of data, analysis and interpretation for providing detailed conclusion of subject matter. Deductive approach helps researcher in framing new hypothesis, themes and concepts that are essential part in carrying on successful research project. On the other hand, an inductive approach is concerned with generation of new theory that has been emerged from the process of data collection. The abductive approach focuses on the weaknesses that are linked with the deductive and inductive approaches. The deductive approach lacks the clarity related to a selected theory that must be tested by formulating hypothesis. The inductive approach lacks the amount of empirical data that is vital for theory-building. The abductive approaches analyses these weaknesses by adopting a pragmatist philosophy. The research study having its basis on comparative analysis and on existing financial liberalisation approaches as applied by numerous countries (Meredith, Mantel Jr and Shafer, 2017). Thus for this research project, most appropriate approach for completion of whole study is abductive one.

Quinlan and et al. (2019) asserted that abductive approach focuses on the deductive and inductive aspect by ensuring that logical inferences and appropriate theories are constructed. It is imperative to note that the abductive research approach allows the research to opt for the best explanation in different alternative to explain any element that might seem surprising at the beginning of the research process. However, Macit (2017) elucidated that abductive reasoning in practical aspects can be challenging as at times, it can be difficult to judge what the researcher is trying to aim for through his study. The deductive or inductive approach can be used for the study; however, it would restrict the researcher to opt for a specific research strategy preventing the researcher from exploring different ways of analysing the topic.

3.4 Pilot Study

The term pilot study provides norms, standards & guidelines for complete scientific research work in any of the social or management research project study. Therefore, through effective guidelines, researcher may also making improvement in own research and meet the quality standards as well. Pilot study is used to improve the quality and efficiency so that they gather an information prior to larger study. This is a small experiment in which researcher gathers information to determine the feasibility of approaches that is used by researcher for generating results. Moreover, the study also specify that the data should be collected for the research project should be accurate and proper so that it will help to meet the deadlines as well. The pilot study was conducted by selecting 50 respondents from different banks to update questions and eliminate errors, mistakes that has become part of questionnaire; while for the interviews, 8 bankers from Tajikistan were chosen. For primary research, questionnaire is design in which the researcher, may also redesigned when senior ask for some corrections in order to remove errors.

3.5 Research design, Strategy and Procedures

According to Alavi and et al. (2018), research design refers to conceptual framework related to techniques and methods that has been adopted by the researcher for combining different research components in the project. It is an arrangement of condition that is undertaken for collection and analysis of data in manner which aims to combine relevance to research purpose with economy in procedure.

According to Bresler and Stake (2017), the term research design constitutes blue print of collection, measure and analysis of data and includes different methods of research such as survey, observation, experiment, content analysis or their combinations. Through research design, the researcher may easily understand and interpret results in more efficient way because it provides an insights about how the research is conducted using specific methodology, even the direction of how the research is to be conducted is further formed with the use of research design. Another reason of choosing the research design is such that it accurate the purpose statement of research design and measure analysis, further the outcome of research design are also applicable in order to attain the key objectives.

There is competition between public and private sector banks regarding better performance as well as productivity. Therefore, it is a keen need to study such matter having basis of secondary data obtained from selected banks' annual reports. The population of study consists of all type of Tajikistan banking industries and sector that successfully implemented financial liberalisation and its related process. Design of study indicates two things such as the size of sample and methodology used in selecting sample banks.

Banks and financial institution lends their capital to large business organisation with objective of gaining maximum interest amount. Their main objective behind such lending is that these business firms have good credit score as well as trust worthy among market place that provides ease for banks in getting their loan repayment easily.

3.6 Data Collection

This study is completed with help data to be collected from both secondary and primary sources as obtained from the annual report of selected public sector and private sector banks. Appropriate and relevant data has also been collected with the help of interviews and questionnaires as prepared. Different bank quest, books, periodicals, journals and different website related banking industries etc. was used for better reliability. Opinions expressed in business standard, accounting literature, annual review used in completion of study.

3.6.1 Process of data collection

To identify perception regarding providing financial services questionnaire has been designed and divided into 8 groups from Group A to Group G. It helps in identifying quality, satisfaction and transparency financial sector. Also it will help in determining whether there has been any negative or adverse impact on financial sector performance of Tajikistan. The final questionnaire has been prepared in line with aims, objectives and hypothesis.

Questionnaire Nature:

Group A: Demographic Information It contains personal information.

Group B: General Information

Group C: Service Quality

Group D: Level of satisfaction regarding transactions

Group E: Transparency

Group F: Pensioner Information

Group G: General Opinion

3.6.2 Primary Data Collection

The process of primary data collection refers to the data that is collected first time by researcher, to evaluate better outcomes out of it that includes observation, survey, interviews, etc. (Cyr, 2016). Researcher also uses the method of primary data collections in which researcher drafted the questionnaire that will be asked to the selected respondents and based on that, outcomes are generated. As primary data collection methods is the original documents, which is actually creates for particular event. The main advantage of using this method is such that the external parties have not misinterpreted it because direct information is collected from the audience. Further, the material are also generally be tracked and attributed back to the original creator that give much more weight to the points. The main disadvantage of using this method is such that the primary sources may be incomplete and unusable. Even the researchers also completely rely solely on their own knowledge as well as interpretation. The responses attained from interviews conducted with 8 bankers of Tajikistan was used for thematic analysis. The interview responses was assessed by coding of themes in which responses were categorised in specific themes to reflect the views of respondents. The interview questions are provided in Appendix B and responses are provided in Appendix C. It is imperative to note here that all of the 8 participants responded to all interview questions that were part of the study and their responses were categorised into specific themes.

3.6.2.1 Quantitative Questionnaire

In present research study, sample is divided into two sub-groups based on respondent's opinion regarding to the financial services sector on nationalised and private sector banks. For gathering data & informations relevant for quantitative research subject matter, respondents are selected randomly from the respective banks. Scales and measurement which has been used for such process includes: Five point Likert scale (1 to 5), such that 1 is for excellent, 2 for good, 3 for average, 4 for poor and 5 for very poor.

With questionnaire prepared related to different categories, researcher can easily acquire information pertaining to the subject matter of research topic. It will assist researcher in getting better understanding and interpretation about the subject matter that can be used by other researchers and scholars as well in the completion of their project. The main benefit of questionnaire is it helps the researcher to involve multiple numbers of subjects and enhancing generalization of the outcomes as well. Further, it also allow for the increased accuracy and objectivity of the results. The main disadvantage of questionnaire is findings related to the data are not generalised to the study population or community and it is more difficult to analyse because it is not generally fit to the standard categories as well. The questionnaire was linked to the aim and objectives of the study in the sense that the researcher prepared the statement considering the

research objectives. Each statement was linked to a specific theme of the topic to reflect that the survey is related to the study.

3.6.2.2 Qualitative Structure

For conducting qualitative research project, data has to be collected accordingly. Information on the basis of characteristic, features is gathered and further analysed. In addition, one of the source of collecting information is personal interview with concerned officials of Banks under study. A semi-structured interview that was conducted with 8 bankers of Tajikistan, and it comprised of open ended questions to meet the defined aim and conduct the entire research in more precise manner. The interview questions was attained from the literature review of the study, to reflect the topic in the questions asked from the respondents. Through this method, researcher was able to prepared and provide a reliable and comparable qualitative data. The interview only takes place voluntary and all personal data will be confidential. In addition, qualitative structure provides stronger conclusion as they are supported by relevant theories and concepts. The advantage of using qualitative structure is that it has less complexity in analysis of the data. The disadvantage of using qualitative interviews is that this method takes time and it is difficult for the researcher for maintaining and assessing or demonstrating. Further volume of the data makes the analysis and interpretation more time taking.

3.6.3 Secondary Data

It is a method of data collection in which data has been collected already from published sources with help of primary source. Secondary data has been collected from annual reports, magazines, booklets etc. of various commercial banks, financial institutions and National Bank of Tajikistan. In addition, sources has been taken from internet publications, books, published articles, financial and business journals (Quinlan and et al., 2019). Furthermore, data has been gathered from WTO and OECD publications available on the Financial Liberalisation reports. One of the benefits of using of secondary data is that it is easily available and thus researcher found strong as well as relevant support through work of previous scholars. All information provided in secondary sources are of reliable, accurate nature that can be used by researcher for completing activities of the research project. As compare to primary data, it is more reliable and validate one. For creating a brief thesis and understanding, collection of data was taken from the secondary sources like journals, books and articles related to subject matter. The benefit of using secondary research, researcher may get much more insight and taking an advantage of author expertise, experience. Secondary sources also aim is to expand the material in original sources so that it may provide more context and meaning as well. The disadvantage of using secondary data is that the researcher might have a difficulty

to obtain the specific information because due to lack of research skills may create obstacles to collect the relevant research data.

3.7 Sampling

Sampling is the process which is used in statistical analysis in which a pre-determine number of assumption are taken from an entire population (Lane, 2018). The methodology used sample from a larger population that depends upon the type of analysis. There are two types of sampling such that purposive and non- purposive. The scholar used simple random sampling method in which 50 bankers of Tajikistan are selected for survey questionnaire and 8 bankers of Tajikistan were chosen for interviews. By attaining information from both sets of people, the researcher was able to meet the defined aim and determine the impact of variation in interest rate in commercial banks in Tajikistan after accession to the WTO.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

3.8.1 Informed consent

All data collected related to subject matter is take from various websites and internet source (Silverman, 2016). All participants has willingly participated in questionnaire by giving their written consent. The purpose of having consent from the participants is it ensures that in future, the researcher is not accused with forcing the participants to be part of the study. The researcher also made sure that there should be no communication error because it may have effects on the overall outcomes in just reverse or opposite way. For this purpose, the researcher confirmed from participants twice about their availability and consent to be part of the study. The respect for dignity of the research participant should be prioritise because it may help a researcher to get accurate results. The researcher also made certain of ensuring that confidentiality aspect was maintained. Any private information related to participants was not shared with any third party.

3.7.2 Privacy and confidentiality

Researcher should ensure that proper confidentiality should be maintained and, before the interview, calls or mails were used. For seeking time and participatory consent of manager and owners. Further, data protection act should be followed for ensuring that privacy of all primary data has been maintained. Moreover, adequate level of confidentiality should be maintained. The researcher made use of secondary sources for the literature review, in which the researcher made

certain to cite appropriate references of each articles that was used. Any form of biasness or misinterpretation of information was prevented by the researcher.

3.9 Methodological Limitations

3.9.1 Reliability

To make sure consistency of all the selected data collection methods, the internal consistent approach is employed in order to inspect questionnaire for the reliability. It was considered one of the best methods for measuring the reliability of questionnaires. Moreover, due to limitation and time constraints, entire questionnaire is administrated only for one time to respondents and exercise is followed, as a pre-requisite for testing method count not be conducted.

3.9.2 Validity

The validity of research is entirely depend upon the collected data, such that researcher uses primary and secondary research methods both in which researcher chooses text books, journal articles in order to collect information that helps in identifying impact of the interest rates in commercial banks of Tajikistan. The validity also relies from the primary research in which the researcher used questionnaire in which topic related questions are asked so that it will be helping to answer research questions as well.

3.10 Limitations and Delimitation of Study

Outsourced financial services includes application and document processing, investment management, marketing and supervision of loans, data processing etc. Outsourcing brings in several risks that are nature strategic, reputation, operational, counterparty, systematic etc. Failure in maintaining confidentiality, non-compliance of legal regulatory norms can result in financial loss and reputation risk on part of bank as well.

The manner in which data is maintained, styled and its format has been changed which created lack of consistency, reliability etc. Out of different means of gathering primary data discussion, observation, personal interview, mail surveying are chosen (Lane, 2018). From perspective of accuracy of data, utmost care has been taken to minimize mistakes, errors in collection of primary data. Primary data has been compared and confirmed with the official banks statistics for checking its accuracy. Difficulty has been faced when bank officers undisclosed bank data due to confidentiality.

Banks become very much cautious in sharing their official as well as financial data with research scholars because of increasing competition in banking sector. For collecting secondary data, researcher has

to face some difficulties in collecting annual reports of some banks. Thus, the quality of this research totally depends on reliability and accuracy of data published in the banks' annual reports.

3.11 Summary

Research philosophy chosen is positivism approach as it is based on view that science is key aspect for gaining true knowledge. Current research is based on comparative analysis with existing financial liberalisation approach applied by numerous countries (Macit, 2017). Abductive approach was considered appropriate for both quantitative and qualitative type so as to identify deep assumptions thus giving mixed combination positive value. Further, researcher also opted abductive approach for attaining the aim i.e. “to analyse the impact of the interest rate on commercial banks of Tajikistan”. Through this method, the researcher also generated results without consuming extra time and reach to the outcomes as well.

Additionally, researcher also select both primary and secondary methods of data collection in which survey questionnaire and interview questions were used as primary method of method of data collection in which questions were asked from different respondents in order to generate the best outcomes. Further, using secondary sources such that books, articles and journals, researcher collect information related to topic and generate best results too. Researcher opted thematic data analysis method where responses were divided in to specific themes. The chosen research strategy is quantitative research method in which SPSS tool is used and chi- square test is applied that helps in checking the reliability of hypothesis. Lastly, random sampling method is also used for determining views of the respondent related to specific topic i.e. to determine the impacts of interest rates on the commercial bank of Tajikistan.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

The present chapter contains an examination and tests of the data set that was used to analysed the research issues. In particular, to ascertain and analyse the changes or influences commercial banks have in relation to changing interest rates and governmental regulation relevant to banking operations. It also analysed the impacts of changes in lending rates, which affects commercial banks' operations and growth. However, in relation to this, there will be determination of the main factors, which affect commercial banking operations as well as interest rate variation in Tajikistan. There has been some development of various plans and operational variation, which will help to make proper determination of the operations. In this process, there will be influences of various aspects and elements, which have been used to examine the factors such as descriptive statistics, ANOVA tests, Chi-square, correlation and regression. Therefore, such tests and statistical analysis will bring accurate information relevant to the data sets. In addition, as per analysing the appropriate outcomes, there will be preparation of several questions and interviews with professionals at commercial banks of Tajikistan, which in turn will be useful for making appropriate participation in this aspect.

4.1 Data Analysis

4.1.1 Test/ Retest Reliability

In respect of analysing the relationship between the two groups of variables which are considered by the researcher with approach to have adequate ascertainment of the database. Thus, in accordance with this, five industry-related original questions were prepared, which were not taken from any research paper or magazine. These questions were put to 50 employees of commercial banks in Tajikistan for survey questionnaire. Thus, this test will be helpful in analysing the reliability of the information, which have been used for the further tests and analysis. In accordance with designed data set, there have been implication of Cronbach's alpha coefficient over the 5 variables. Thus, there have presented information as follows:

4.1 Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	150	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	150	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

4.2 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.405	.412	5

Interpretation

Cronbach's alpha is the tool that is used to measure the reliability of the scale that is used to measure particular variables. A commonly used scale is the Likert scale, and Cronbach's alpha determines whether a variable can be measured in better way. In the present study, the Cronbach's alpha value is 0.405, or 40%. This demonstrates that the scale that is used failed to measure the variable.

As it is clear that the reliability of the test is not valid and that is why, in order to improve the same, scholar started using another reliable tool that helps to answer the research question, which is ANOVA. ANOVA was used to identify the difference between two variables that is used by investigator. Chi-square test is also applied in order to analyse the relationship between categorical variable. Moreover, scholar also uses correlation as a tool in order to address this limitation and generate the best and valid results as well.

ANOVA is appropriate to Likert Scales because the researcher is looking to analyse more than one statement. The intervalist position states that if the researcher is looking to analyse more than a single Likert item for which ANOVA can be used here. Pandis (2016) further asserted that analysing a single Likert item is a practice that should occur rarely. However, if the focus is on multiple items, than it is considered appropriate to summarise the ratings that are generated from

Likert scales through means and standard deviations. In such situations, it is completely appropriate to utilise the parametric testing in the form of ANOVA.

Descriptive

This method helps in bringing summary information about the variables that have been analysed to have accurate ascertainment of various activities. There will be influences of various statistical elements, such as mean, mode, median, standard deviation and range, etc. Therefore, it represents the summary statistics of the database that can be helpful in managing business operations. Moreover, there will be an analysis of various outcomes based on interest rate fluctuation and relevant changes in the operations of commercial banks in Tajikistan.

4.3 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	150	1	5	2.29	1.277	1.631
Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?	150	1	5	2.15	1.252	1.567
Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	150	1	5	2.33	1.251	1.566
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	150	1	5	2.48	1.283	1.647
Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	150	1	5	2.15	1.252	1.567
Valid N (listwise)	150					

Interpretation

The statistics revealed that most banks are facilitating appropriate interest rates on deposits, as the value of statistics is ($M = 2.29$, $SD = 1.277$). People are also quite satisfied with the online banking transaction facility provided by their bank in Tajikistan, as indicated by the statistics ($M = 2.15$, $SD = 1.252$). People feel safe while making banking transactions, as indicated by the value of the statistic ($M = 2.33$, $SD = 1.251$). Overall, it can be said that in the past couple of years, commercial banks in Tajikistan have made significant improvements to their technology base, due to which people do not face any particular problems with online transactions, and this shows they are highly satisfied. Respondents believed that asset and liability management is the one of the main factors that assist banks in paying due attention to addressing problems on time. This is indicated by the value of the statistics ($M = 2.48$, $SD = 1.283$). Respondents also believed that adverse market movements are greatly affecting banks financial conditions, as reflected by the statistics ($M = 2.15$, $SD = 1.252$).

In order to analyse the results at a more granular level, a detail discussion on results the obtained is provided below.

➤ Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

Professionals were asked if their bank facilitates the appropriate interest rates on deposits. 37.3% of professionals believe that there are appropriate interest rates on deposits of banks. Therefore, there are appropriate rates awarded to consumers on their savings account and deposits they make in banks. Moreover, due to charging such rates they will retain appropriate gains on such investments. There are various reviews attained from professionals in which majority were in favour. It can be said that commercial banks in Tajikistan are charging satisfactory interest rates on deposits. In accordance with pension scheme that has been offered by the government to its employees based on their job and level of remuneration retained by them. There have been influences of government policy development that in turn has a negative and positive impact on schemes and offered by banking industries. Thus, the motive of the government in bringing appropriate revenue gains to citizens based on their performed duties and jobs in a particular sector. It depends on the level of operations performed by a bank as well as the number of consumers

associated with banking activities. Thus, it can be said that, governmental plans and policies are less affecting the banking sector in Tajikistan which are in turn have facilitating proper wealth to society. It will be based on changing effective rates of interest among consumers in saving their implied funds.

➤ **Are the online operations performed by your bank quite satisfactory?**

The next question considers the transactional activities performed by banks for accelerate banking activities and respondents were asked about levels of satisfaction when making online operations. The majority presented their reviews in favour and 41.35% strongly agree with this statement, 25.3% agree, 16.75% are neutral, while the same percentage disagree with this statement. As per analysing the variations in the outcome on which it can be said that, currently, banking operations have been enhanced in Tajikistan resulting in higher levels of customer satisfaction. Moreover, in relation to these findings, it can be said that online financial transactions are comparatively secure, and the confidentiality of data is managed well in the Tajikistan's commercial banks. A separate risk management system is needed in the banking industry. This helps to save time as well as perfectly executing business operations. It ensures issues are addressed with proper consideration of all causes and impacts. Currently, this technique is used by banks to make appropriate operational analysis and efficiency of the issues, which in turn will be useful and linking for attaining favourable banking operations. On the other hand, considering the above findings, it can be said that there are significantly positive reviews obtained from professionals in commercial banks. Thus, in respect of this, maximum positive reviews have been given by the professionals, which emphasizes that the findings demonstrate that there are satisfactory risk management systems in the organization.

➤ **Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?**

Professionals were asked whether the securities of the transactional activities they perform in the banking operations make them feel safe, on which it can be said that 33.3% professionals strongly agree with the statements, 26.7% only agree, while 20% are neutral. The majority of opinions are in agreement with the statement on which it can be said that they are well confident

in terms of having appropriate analysis over the database and appropriate determination of practices. In this case, it can be said that the banking firms have to be more focused in terms of improving security at a transactional level. The details relevant with accounts, amount as well as destination needed to be kept confidential as it will not affect the wealth of any individual. Thus, the inter-banking operations have been analysed and determined by the researcher on which banks lend money to each other with a fixed interest rate to be charged. It helps them in operating activities as well as improving banking functions in the environment. In analysing, the outcomes there are approx. However, it has been analysed that the borrowing interest rates are needed to be reformulated which will bring the positive rise to the income generation as well as operational performance of the bank. There will be development of various policies and changes in activities that can make suitable development in the operational practices. It creates opportunities to banking firms in terms of retaining appropriate amount of revenue as well as make proper changes in operations.

➤ **Do your bank's asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?**

Professionals in commercial banks of Tajikistan were asked whether their bank is capable of facilitating adequate asset-liability management to address the financial issues. Thus, the question arises after considering the issues in the operations that have been faced by society after impacts of the global financial crisis. The findings show that a majority of respondents are in favour, which states that their bank is capable of facilitating the most adequate services to them. The main role of the asset-liability department is mainly associated with facilitating the institution's strength in terms of meeting debt challenges in the environment. There can be a rise in operational gains and business motives that will help in meeting the targets at the right time. Moreover, the commercial banks in Tajikistan have the most convenient and appropriate asset liability management. In relation to making additional gains, banks usually offer term deposits. This is based on different rates for several terms of borrowed amount. There will be revenue generation and adequate increment in the profitability of the banking sector in Tajikistan. The long-term loans will have less rates, while short period loans have higher interest rates. From a psychological perspective, it can be said that there is higher number of short-term loan borrowers

stated in the market. They usually take out loans for specific purposes, such as purchasing a home, vehicle or education. These loans are for a short period, and this helps banks to retain higher gains. In relation to the above listed analysis, the researchers have addressed various favourable outcomes. Professionals in commercial banks responded that the majority of them are charging rates with respect to variations. Thus, again there are positive reviews from banks that they are adopting such techniques, which will benefit them in getting higher revenue through banking operations.

➤ **Do you believe that vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition is same in adverse market movements?**

In analysing influences of credit union are in context with helping each other in the financial operations. They facilitate loans or borrowing services to each other, which in turn provides appropriate operational gains at lower interest rates. In analysing such outcomes, it can be said that, such factors will affect economy and which results changes in interest rates. On the other hand, the above listed analysis show that 41.3% of respondents strongly believe that a credit union's financial condition fluctuates in relation to the changes incurred in market conditions. Therefore, it can be said that to retain higher profits and securing capital funds in business. Moreover, such variations had been done in accordance with making changes in the operational activities and business activities that has have led to the organisation retaining higher returns. Thus, these factors influence interest rates risk of such industries by way of reducing the level of sales and operational activities performed by them. Various obstacles and issues affect operations of the firm that helps in managing certain activities for adequate operational analysis. Therefore, these are the banking operations that need to be considered seriously, administratively which will bring certain changes in the operations of the firm, and that will help them in making adequate operational changes.

Therefore, in respect of the banking professionals that allows them to meet the obstacles have made various strategic operations and decisions. Addressing such issues will be beneficial in retaining higher amount of profits through operations as well as gathering large number of consumers. In a formal process, there will be analysis based on making proper auditing of all accounts and analysis over causes that have affected the operational practices of banking firm.

4.1.2 Univariate Statistics

This concept will help to analyse the types of data and observations to single attribute or characteristic. However, by analysing the univariate data, the researcher denoted the independent variable as ‘interest rates’ and dependent variable as ‘revenue in banking industries.’ In addition, there will be use of various data sets that will be analysed, collected and measured for accurate data analysis.

Hypothesis

- **Null hypothesis:** there is no mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan

- **Alternative hypothesis:** there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan

Univariate Analysis of Variance

4.4 Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

Mean	Std. Deviation	N
2.29	1.277	150

The mean value is 2.29, which means that sample respondents agree with the fact that the bank is facilitating appropriate interest rate on deposits.

4.5 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.000 ^a	0	.	.	.
Intercept	788.907	1	788.907	483.547	.000
Error	243.093	149	1.631		
Total	1032.000	150			
Corrected Total	243.093	149			

a. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = .000)

Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

Model: Intercept

Figure 1 - Diagram 1

Interpretation

Diagram 1 reflect that there is one variable which impact another variable and that is why, there is a significant difference between these variables which is further analysed through results generated by using tool. The diagram 1 illustrates a univariate analysis of the data set relating to the question regarding whether interest rates presented by their banks are appropriate or not. The responses show that the majority of respondents are in favour with the services and interest rates charged by their banks on the services. The F value shows 483.547 which means that the value is high showing that the model can be considered for carrying out an analysis. Similarly, the analysis shows that the significance value is 0.000, which is lower than P-value of 0.05. This demonstrates that there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan. Moreover, it also shows that the model is reliable and fit for analysis.

4.6 Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Are the online operations performed by your bank quite satisfactory?

Mean	Std. Deviation	N
2.15	1.252	150

4.7 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Are the online operations performed by your bank quite satisfactory?

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.000 ^a	0	.	.	.
Intercept	695.527	1	695.527	443.877	.000
Error	233.473	149	1.567		
Total	929.000	150			
Corrected Total	233.473	149			

a. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = .000)

Dependent Variable: Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?

Figure 2 - Diagram 2

Interpretation

Diagram 2 reflected that one variable is directly depend upon the another variable and that is why, this result clearly shows that there is a difference between interest rate and revenue of commercial. Hence, there is a no direct relationship between one variable such as when interest increases, the revenue of banks is also decreases. This question is in respect of online operations of the banking firm on which professionals have presented their views. The online operations performed by commercial banks in Tajikistan are judged on company services. The F value is 443.877 which is high, and it shows the model is fit for the regression model. The significance value of the data set is 0.000, which is lower than the significance value of 0.05. Thus, it provides strong evidence against the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis, such that

there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan. Moreover, the model is reliable and fit for analysis.

4.8 Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?

Mean	Std. Deviation	N
2.33	1.251	150

4.9 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.000 ^a	0	.	.	.
Intercept	816.667	1	816.667	521.500	.000
Error	233.333	149	1.566		
Total	1050.000	150			
Corrected Total	233.333	149			

a. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = .000)

Dependent Variable: Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?

Figure 3 - Diagram 3

Interpretation

Diagram 3 of the study clearly reflected that significant relationship between two variables and thus, with the help of result generated, it is identify that null hypothesis is rejected and that is why, there is an inversely proportional relationship between these variables. In this diagram 3, professionals were asked about the security offered by their bank when undertaking transactional activities. The F value is 521.500 which is high, and it shows the model is fit for the regression model. The significance value has been determined as 0.000, which is also lower than the P value of 0.05. Thus, it suggests acceptance of the alternative hypothesis and rejection of the null hypothesis, as there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan. Moreover, the model is reliable and fit for analysis.

4.10 Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Do your bank's asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?

Mean	Std. Deviation	N
2.48	1.283	150

4.11 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Do your bank's asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.000 ^a	0	.	.	.
Intercept	922.560	1	922.560	560.061	.000
Error	245.440	149	1.647		
Total	1168.000	150			
Corrected Total	245.440	149			

a. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = .000)

Dependent Variable: Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?

Figure 4 - Diagram 4

Interpretation

Diagram 4 of the study clearly reflected the interdependency of both the variables and that is why, it is analysed that there is no relationship between the variables and so, alternative hypothesis is accepted. Such as there is no role of assets and liability management system for banks. The diagram 4 illustrated above and the table that presents the findings demonstrate that the asset liability management system of the organisation has been helpful in analysing the issues and making adequate changes in the operational practices. The F value is 560.061 which is high, and it shows the model is fit for the regression model. The significance value of the data set is 0.000, lower than 0.05. Thus, it suggests acceptance of the alternative hypothesis that there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan. Moreover, it also shows that the model is reliable and fit for analysis. The changes in assets and

liability management system for banks will affect the revenue and revenue generation of commercial banks in Tajikistan.

4.12 Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Do you accept the weakness in adverse market movements of the financial condition of a credit union?

Mean	Std. Deviation	N
2.15	1.252	150

4.13 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Do you accept the weakness in adverse market movements of the financial condition of a credit union?

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.000 ^a	0	.	.	.
Intercept	695.527	1	695.527	443.877	.000
Error	233.473	149	1.567		
Total	929.000	150			
Corrected Total	233.473	149			

a. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = .000)

Dependent Variable: Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?

Figure 5 - Diagram 5

Interpretation

Diagram 5 reflected how one variable is dependent upon another, also it shows a direct relationship between both variables. Like with changes in the interest rates, commercial banks also change their interest rate. In this question, respondents were asked whether they believed the credit union's financial condition would have an impact as per adverse market movements. The F value is 560.061 which is high, and it shows the model is fit for the regression model. The significance value of .000 suggests acceptance of the alternative hypothesis, which states that there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan. This means that the central bank or reserve bank changes interest rate from time to time, such as changes determine how many loans people will take in the upcoming period. Thus, revenue is affected by

the interest rate and because of this, a significant difference is found. Similarly, the changes incurred in credit unions' financial condition may affect the banks in adverse market situations.

Based on the above univariate analysis of the data set, professionals of various commercial banks in Tajikistan were asked to make appropriate determination of operational practices. The relationship between interest rate variations and the revenue of the organisation has been examined to have appropriate outcomes. Thus, with respect to the measurement criteria, it can be said that there is a relationship between these variables. The rise in interest rates will affect term deposit revenue of banks. Additionally, suggests acceptance of the alternative hypothesis, which states that there is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan.

4.1.3 Bivariate Statistics

This is the statistical analysis carried out by testing the variables stated in rows and columns. Thus, this test will help to define the appropriate relationship between the variables. A chi-square test has also been carried out to measure the outcomes.

Shih and Fay (2017) stated that a chi-square (χ^2) statistic is a test that emphasises on measuring how a model is compared to the actual observed data. The data that is used in calculating a chi-square statistic has to be random, raw, mutually exclusive, drawn from independent variables and drawn from a large enough sample. Supporting the notion, Panids (2016) demonstrated that chi-square tests are usually used in hypothesis testing. The chi-square statistic compares the size of any discrepancies between the expected results and the actual results, emphasising on the size of the sample and the number of variables in the relationship.

The chi-square tests in this study are valid because it helps to determine the relationship between two categories i.e. online transaction and impact of interest rate upon banks. The chi-square would help in assessing how the relationship between the two categories affects the overall outcomes. In each of the test conducted below, the focus has been to assess which hypothesis is accepted and which hypothesis is rejected.

Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits? * Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?

4.14 Crosstab

Count

		Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	1	23	13	8	8	4	56
	2	12	9	8	2	3	34
	3	11	10	4	4	1	30
	4	9	5	3	1	2	20
	5	7	1	2	0	0	10

Total	62	38	25	15	10	150
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4.15 Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.962 ^a	16	.812
Likelihood Ratio	12.535	16	.706
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.878	1	.171
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 13 cells (52.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .67.

Interpretation

Based on above analysed database, which have presented the outcomes for chi square test states relationship between interest rates and online operations of the banks. The value of the level of significance is $p = 0.812 > 0.05$ in the Pearson chi-square test. On other hand, in terms of the likelihood ratio, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.706 > 0.05$. In the linear-by-linear association test, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.171 > 0.05$. Based on all these three statistics, it can be said that there is no significant relationship between the variables. Consequently, the alternative hypothesis is rejected, and the null hypothesis is not rejected. This states that there is no significant mean relationship between these variables.

➤ **Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits? * Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?**

4.16 Crosstab

Count

		Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	1	19	17	11	8	1	56
	2	7	8	10	3	6	34
	3	14	8	4	4	0	30
	4	6	4	4	4	2	20
	5	4	3	1	1	1	10
Total		50	40	30	20	10	150

4.17 Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.882 ^a	16	.275
Likelihood Ratio	19.814	16	.229
Linear-by-Linear Association	.014	1	.905
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 13 cells (52.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .67.

Interpretation

The value of the level of significance is $p = 0.275 > 0.05$ for the Pearson chi-square test. For the likelihood ratio, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.229 > 0.05$, and in the linear-by-linear association test, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.905 > 0.05$. On basis of all these three statistics, it can be said that there is no significant relationship between variables. Thus, it confirms the null hypothesis is not rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

- **Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits? * Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?**

4.18 Crosstab

Count

		Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	1	23	13	8	8	4	56
	2	12	9	8	2	3	34
	3	11	10	4	4	1	30
	4	9	5	3	1	2	20
	5	7	1	2	0	0	10
Total		62	38	25	15	10	150

4.19 Crosstab

Count

		Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	1	28	6	8	0	4	46
	2	8	12	5	5	4	34
	3	6	10	7	7	2	32
	4	13	8	4	3	0	28
	5	7	2	1	0	0	10
Total		62	38	25	15	10	150

4.20 Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	33.719 ^a	16	.006
Likelihood Ratio	41.365	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.095	1	.758
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 14 cells (56.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .67.

Interpretation

In this case, there are two variables that are analysed, namely the satisfaction level of individuals on operations performed, and the role of asset and liability management in addressing issues. For the Pearson chi-square test, the value of level of significance is $p = 0.006 > 0.05$. On other hand, in the case of the likelihood ratio, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.00 > 0.05$, and for the linear-by-linear association test, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.758 > 0.05$. On basis of all these three statistics, namely it can be said that there is no significant relationship between variables and the null hypothesis is not rejected.

- **Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues? * Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?**

4.21 Crosstab

Count

		Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	1	18	13	6	4	5	46
	2	7	10	8	8	1	34
	3	12	7	8	4	1	32
	4	8	9	8	3	0	28
	5	5	1	0	1	3	10
Total		50	40	30	20	10	150

4.22 Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	26.036 ^a	16	.054
Likelihood Ratio	26.312	16	.050
Linear-by-Linear Association	.010	1	.919
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 12 cells (48.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .67.

➤ **Interpretation**

From table above, it can be observed that there are two variables, namely the safety people feel in online transactions, and the role of asset and liability management in addressing issues. The value of the level of significance Pearson chi-square is $p = 0.054 > 0.05$. On the other hand, in the case of likelihood ratio, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.050 > 0.05$. For the linear-by-linear association, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.919 > 0.05$. Based on all these three

statistics, it can be said that there is no significant relationship between variables the null hypothesis is not rejected.

➤ **Do your bank's asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues? * Do you believe that vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?**

4.23 Crosstab

Count

		Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	1	28	6	8	0	4	46
	2	8	12	5	5	4	34
	3	6	10	7	7	2	32
	4	13	8	4	3	0	28
	5	7	2	1	0	0	10
Total		62	38	25	15	10	150

4.24 Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	33.719 ^a	16	.006
Likelihood Ratio	41.365	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.095	1	.758
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 14 cells (56.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .67.

➤ **Interpretation**

The two variables analysed above are the impact of adverse market condition on the credit union financial conditions, and the role of asset and liability management in addressing issues. For the Pearson chi-square test the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.006 > 0.05$. In the likelihood ratio test, the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.00 > 0.05$. For the linear-by-linear association the value of the level of significance is $p = 0.758 > 0.05$. Based on all these three statistics it can be said that there is no significant relationship between the variables. The null hypothesis is not rejected.

4.25 Multivariate Statistics Descriptive

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?	1	56	2.23	1.321	.177	1.88	2.59	1	5
	2	34	2.26	1.263	.217	1.82	2.71	1	5
	3	30	2.13	1.167	.213	1.70	2.57	1	5
	4	20	2.10	1.334	.298	1.48	2.72	1	5
	5	10	1.50	.850	.269	.89	2.11	1	3
	Total	150	2.15	1.252	.102	1.95	2.36	1	5
Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	1	56	2.20	1.119	.150	1.90	2.50	1	5
	2	34	2.79	1.366	.234	2.32	3.27	1	5
	3	30	1.93	1.081	.197	1.53	2.34	1	4
	4	20	2.60	1.392	.311	1.95	3.25	1	5
	5	10	2.20	1.398	.442	1.20	3.20	1	5
	Total	150	2.33	1.251	.102	2.13	2.54	1	5
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	1	56	2.73	1.213	.162	2.41	3.06	1	5
	2	34	2.35	1.300	.223	1.90	2.81	1	5
	3	30	2.43	1.194	.218	1.99	2.88	1	5
	4	20	2.10	1.334	.298	1.48	2.72	1	5
	5	10	2.40	1.713	.542	1.17	3.63	1	5

	Total	150	2.48	1.283	.105	2.27	2.69	1	5
Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	1	56	2.23	1.321	.177	1.88	2.59	1	5
	2	34	2.26	1.263	.217	1.82	2.71	1	5
	3	30	2.13	1.167	.213	1.70	2.57	1	5
	4	20	2.10	1.334	.298	1.48	2.72	1	5
	5	10	1.50	.850	.269	.89	2.11	1	3
	Total	150	2.15	1.252	.102	1.95	2.36	1	5

4.26 ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?	Between Groups	5.107	4	1.277	.811	.520
	Within Groups	228.366	145	1.575		
	Total	233.473	149			
Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	Between Groups	14.669	4	3.667	2.432	.050
	Within Groups	218.665	145	1.508		
	Total	233.333	149			
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	Between Groups	7.126	4	1.782	1.084	.367
	Within Groups	238.314	145	1.644		
	Total	245.440	149			
Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	Between Groups	5.107	4	1.277	.811	.520
	Within Groups	228.366	145	1.575		
	Total	233.473	149			

Correlations

Hypothesis

- **Null hypothesis:** There is no mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan.
- **Alternative hypothesis:** There is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan.

4.27 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	2.29	1.277	150
Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?	2.15	1.252	150
Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	2.33	1.251	150
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	2.48	1.283	150
Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	2.15	1.252	150

4.28 Correlations

		Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?	Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	Do you believe that vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?
Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	Pearson Correlation	1	-.112	.010	-.136	-.112
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.171	.905	.098	.171
	N	150	150	150	150	150
Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?	Pearson Correlation	-.112	1	.113	-.025	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.171		.169	.759	.000
	N	150	150	150	150	150
Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	Pearson Correlation	.010	.113	1	.008	.113
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.905	.169		.919	.169
	N	150	150	150	150	150
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	Pearson Correlation	-.136	-.025	.008	1	-.025
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.098	.759	.919		.759
	N	150	150	150	150	150

Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	Pearson Correlation	-.112	1.000**	.113	-.025	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.171	.000	.169	.759	
	N	150	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation

The correlation value in the case of the variables '*online operation performed by the bank is quite satisfactory*' and '*safety that people feel while making online transaction*' is 0.113, which is quite low. This means that online operations performed by the bank do not play any role in making people safe. The correlation value in the case of the variables '*asset and liability management role in addressing issues*' and '*interest rate given by the banks*' is -0.25, which means that there is no correlation between the two variables.

Regression

Hypothesis

- **Null hypothesis:** There is no mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan.
- **Alternative Hypothesis:** There is a mean significant difference between interest rates and revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan.

4.29 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.180 ^a	.032	.012	1.269	.032	1.628	3	146	.186

a. Predictors: (Constant) Do you believe that vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements? Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues? Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?

4.30 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.867	3	2.622	1.628	.186 ^b
	Residual	235.226	146	1.611		
	Total	243.093	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements? Do your bank's asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?, Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?

4.31 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standard ized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero - order	Partial	Part	Toleranc e	VIF
(Constant)	2.838	.339		8.379	.000	2.169	3.508					
Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	.025	.084	.024	.297	.767	-.140	.190	.010	.025	.024	.987	1.013
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	-.138	.081	-.139	-1.704	.090	-.298	.022	-.136	-.140	-.139	.999	1.001
Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	-.121	.084	-.119	-1.446	.150	-.286	.044	-.112	-.119	-.118	.987	1.014

a. Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

4.32 Excluded Variables^a

Model	Beta In	T	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics		
					Tolerance	VIF	Minimum Tolerance
1 Are the online operations performed by your bank is quite satisfactory?	. ^b000	.	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements? Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?, Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?

4.33 Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions			
				(Constant)	Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	Do you believe that vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?
1	1	3.489	1.000	.01	.02	.01	.02
	2	.238	3.826	.00	.01	.44	.51
	3	.204	4.136	.00	.71	.13	.26
	4	.068	7.150	.99	.26	.42	.22

a. Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

From the table 4.29 above, it can be observed that value of R is 0.180 and value of R-squared is 0.032. This means that there is less correlation between the variables, and only 3% of variation of the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable. The value of the level of significance is $0.186 > 0.05$, which means that there is no significant correlation between the variables. It can be said that the interest rate given by the commercial bank is not affected by the vulnerability of the financial condition of the banks, asset liability management or safety that people observe while making transactional operations. The null hypothesis is not rejected.

4.2 Themes

4.2.1 Theme 1: Impact of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates

Liberalisation is a term where most of the private industries or sectors are allowed by the government to do business in the nation. Liberalisation leads to the removal of obstacles to establishing their business. The impact of governmental plans and policies are significantly affecting the banking sector in the country. Changes in taxation, exchange rates of as well as interest rates in the operations significantly affect operational practices of private banks. All interviewees agreed with this statement. It has also been proved by the regression analysis and other approaches that interest rates have a direct impact on bank revenues.

As stated by a CEO,

“I have analysed that the main motive of these banks is based on retaining higher profitability as well as higher consumer satisfaction index. If customer will be satisfied, it will promote positive word of mouth marketing of the company name. This will help them in appropriate growth in sales or revenue. The deregulatory authorities stated in country have made huge impacts on changing operational variations as well as development of various aspects.” (Appendix C, Interview 3)

Moreover, in considering the banking preferences, there will be higher concerns relevant to generating profits as well as reducing the costs implied in each banking activity. It has been analysed that in October 2008, there was a total debt of US\$700 million in the cotton sector that

was funded in consideration of pledges and guarantees by the National Bank of Tajikistan. Thus, these initiatives were taken by banks in the context of promoting the agricultural sector in the country, on which the creditors ought to have received marketable securities as compensation. In this case, investors in financing the cotton sector in the economy owned debts. Thus, in 2009, government of Tajikistan continued to facilitate funds in the agricultural sector with the help of commercial banks without restricting or limiting the borrowings to cotton growers. Moreover, there have been various steps taken by NBT in respect of liberalising the export of cotton.

There are impacts of raising competition in the nation that will affect operational policies for banks. In terms of the scenario during the global financial crisis, enhancing the sales in banks for meeting market competition, bankers have facilitated loans with lower interest rates. Thus, due to these impacts, there was no money left in the banks or in circulation (Ramlall, 2017). Moreover, people at that time made investment in real estate, which resulted in a reduction of the monetary circulation. Therefore, it led to a rise in the inflation rate, a reduction in GDP as well as an impact on GFC in the economy. Tajikistan has witnessed various financial obstacles, as there is higher competition and a rise in inflation resulting in higher interest rates.

On the other hand, competition in the banking sector has also affected poor mechanisms in management and operations of firm. The impact of such increasing competition in operational activities of the banking industry have negatively affected the operations of firms. In addition, the rise in competition in the banking sector results in a reduction in interest, but on the other hand, it leads to poor monetary circulation in the environment (Kwan, 2018).

“I believe that countries like Tajikistan will have various issues or obstacles which will result in inappropriate internal management which will affect the economic activities in country, by manager” (Appendix C, Interview 7)

4.2.2 Theme 2: Bank influences due to commercial bank lending rates

An analysis of respondents’ answers relating to their views and information regarding lending rates fluctuations in banks was carried out. In this case, there have been various influences of which distract banking operations that affect the overall operational activities. This mainly affects the sales growth, efficiency, as well as preference of the industry. In addition, there are

various plans and policies, which were issued by the government, such as monetary policies, taxation, economic changes, etc.

As was stated by a supervisor,

“I think the operational aspect of commercial banks is mainly relevant with providing better banking services to investors. Thus, changing rates will affect a loan sum granted by banks as well as terms for borrowing the amount.” (Appendix C, interview 4)

Banks borrow funds from other financial institutions, and this result in it uplifting its operational aspects. The variations in inter-banking transactions brings gains or losses (Maxfield et al., 2018). There are various kinds of financing activities, which need to be undertaken with the motive of making appropriate changes and operations that will contribute to the organisational review being managed. There are generally simple and compound interest rates, which are charged against the amount of the loan, granted to a person.

Thus, based on such interest rates, they have higher earnings and revenues for the development of various operational practices. In particular, due to the accelerated inflation rate indicates an expected decrease or appreciation in exchange rates (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). In other cases, the situation for enterprises that produce goods for export deteriorates and they have reduced competitiveness in the world market.

A CEO stated that,

“, Exporting enterprises are forced to adjust the changed global economic condition which increases efficiency as well as sales growth of products inside a country.” (Appendix C, Interview 5)

In relation to the inter-bank clearing or credit settlements, there are several processes. This includes principle of reliability, acceleration of settlement transmission, and expediency (Sharofiddin et al., 2018). Therefore, such analysis helps banking organisations in terms of having adequate operational analysis and management of various approaches.

However, the advantages of such transnational process are that banks charge lower rates in clearing any account or making a profitable rise in the operational aspects. Along with this, there will be a rise in operational efficiencies of banks, which in turn will be helpful for managing the transactional obstacles (Martin et al., 2018).

4.2.3 Theme 3: The cost factors affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan

As per analysing factors that affects lending rates in banks are usually relevant with expenses incurred during a period. However, there have been various determinants, which create obstacles in analysing the data set and team with banking operations as well as affecting lending rates. In addition, there are influences of various cost factors and economic elements that affect the lending rates. These include monetary policies, relationships with other nations, GDP, and inflation rates.

These factors have negative as well as positive impact on the country, which bounds economists for analysing the current scenario and planning for improving the internal environment. This is due to the dependency of this nation on other nations. Domestic strength is not evident in retaining appropriate development in the economy of Tajikistan. Instability in the current account of country will be managed through balancing payments and trades.

As stated by a manager,

“I believe that, raising volume of exports in comparison with imports will be profitable in balancing trade practices and current account of economy. These are the accounting factors which are affecting the economy, and which will reversely affect the interest rates of the nation.” (Appendix C, Interview 7)

There are a number of various factors that have an impact on identifying interest rates in Tajikistan. It comprises of various classification policies, which are based on several activities, such as the classification of banks and Tajikistan's classification theory (Ramlall, 2017). It is also based on the current interest rate structure, which helps to carry out a proper analysis of activities.

CEO stated that,

“There has been administration over controlling the interest rates as well as appropriate wealth management with respect to manage operational demands in capital market. Thus, in analysing the obstacles, there can be influences for adjusting the terms and risks associated with business operations” (Appendix C, Interview 3)

4.2.4 Theme 4: General factors relevant to the cost of loans

It has been analysed here that there are various general factors, which affect the cost of loans in an industry. If a bank borrows funds, which are not capable of meeting costs in the future, it creates obstacles in the banking operations of commercial banks. Thus, these are debts, which create issues in the survival of such financial institutions. The viability and capacity of firms in terms of their financial structure define effective cost-efficient factors to improve business operations (Maxfield et al., 2018). In respect of granting loans to corporation as well as individuals, charging a specific interest rate will bring profitable returns for a commercial bank.

However, controlling costs for issuing loans includes several factors such as executing interest rates, preparedness for emergency, economic stability and fiscal performance of the nation, as well as ascertaining debts. Thus, these are factors, which need to be considered by the government and professionals in banks in order to devise fruitful policies and operational development in work culture (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). On the other hand, it will have improve borrowing tendency as well as lending capacity of bank.

4.2.5 Theme 5: Influence of the national inflation rate on the central bank’s interest rate policy and lending rate of commercial banks

Various factors that influences interest rate fluctuations in an economy need to be investigated and ascertained. Therefore, impacts of inflation rate fluctuation in a nation have a positive and negative impact on the lending proportion. Inflation in general terms is known as a rise in the price of commodities, which is related to issues such as dependency and the poor currency rate of a nation (Sharofiddin et al., 2018). Thus, in this approach, there are various issues such as the dependency of Tajikistan on other nations in terms of obtaining natural resources, etc.

These create a reduction in the value of the currency compared to other nations, which in turn raises the rate of inflation.

Consequently, it results in rising interest or lending rates in commercial banks. It comprises of various factors such as fractional-reserve banking, quantity theory of money, interest rates, loan, inflation and savings, quantity theory of money and federal open market committee (Martin et al., 2018). Thus,

“I believe that, ascertainment of the national growth with considering such factors will help in uplifting economic conditions as well as bringing favourable gains to nation, by supervisor” (Appendix C, Interview 6)

The government of Tajikistan has huge gap of economic policies, which create obstacles in the banking industry. The main motive of economists in a country is to determine appropriate resources to raise the value of the currency and reduce the rate of inflation. The government mainly creates policies related to interest rates, taxation, and export and import duties which are analysed for balancing the current operations of the country. Therefore, frequent changes in the operations of banking firms have also affected industrial policies. These changes create hurdles to making efficient efforts in the banking operations. Moreover, in terms of the impacts of GFC, there has been increase in inflation rates, unemployment and several unfavourable economic rates which have affected the downfall of the economy.

“Employees of commercial bank stated that, there have been various reforms and changes in the operational analysis and determination of accurate interest rates.” (Appendix C, Interview 5)

4.3 Conclusion

This chapter has provided an analysis of the various findings related to the impact of interest rate fluctuations in the commercial banks of Tajikistan. Thus, there have been impacts of various techniques and operational practices, which have helped in analysing several operations. Moreover, of the research findings have generated various information, which have represented mixed reviews on outcomes such as the idea that interest rates in commercial banks will reflect

positively in rising revenue. Therefore, if banks charge higher interest rates for buyers on their savings, it will enhance revenue retention in the industry. On the other hand, considering the changes incurred in revenue, it can be said that interest rates will result in a reduction in revenue of banking businesses. Borrowers of loans will not be interested in making any investment in operations that affect negatively in terms of reducing the revenue of the industry. On the basis the analysed data from the findings of the questionnaire and interviews with various professionals, it can be concluded that commercial banks in Tajikistan have influence on the operational practices, which is through changing interest rates. Therefore, the analysis has determined the various factors and opinions of professionals regarding their banking practices and operational approaches made by their bank in the same aspect.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

5.0 Introduction

This chapter consists of all the relevant information regarding the outcomes determined in the previous chapter. The method used to analyse findings was mix methods approach comprising of both, quantitative and qualitative research design. For the purpose of quantitative research design, a survey questionnaire was conducted with 150 bankers of Tajikistan in relation to the topic of the study. The data analysis carried out for the survey questionnaire was in the form of Chi-square and ANOVA, along with correlation and regression. The researcher made certain to analyse each of the statement of the Likert Scale through the ANOVA method. For the purpose of qualitative research design, interviews were carried out with 8 bankers of Tajikistan in relation to the topic of the study. The data analysis carried out for interviews were in the form of thematic analysis. The thematic analysis was conducted through the categorisation of themes in relation to the topic of the study. There is a discussion of reviews and opinion of professionals regarding their banking operations. To analyse the impacts of interest rate fluctuation in the commercial banks of Tajikistan which determines of above listed outcomes and reviews. Thus, it can be said that, there are various reviews and opinions of professionals regarding banking activities and organisational culture. In this aspect, it can be said that there are various reasons for which a commercial bank makes changes in its lending interest rates. This will be due to retaining higher earnings and operational gains on the collected amount of funds (Mandilaras, 2015). Similarly, there can be a rise in the operational gains and motives of business with respect to retaining appropriate revenue for operational practices. The findings reflect that there is close relationship between asset liability management in commercial banks and the level of safety of transactions provided by the bank. The reason is if asset and liability management is proper, then in that case the bank will be in good condition and on that basis, it earns substantial profit. Earning a higher amount of profit leads to making considerable investment in technology, which ultimately provides benefit to the people. This is also evident from the literature review, where it was identified that there are large number of people who believe that if bank is in profit, it will make huge investment in its technology base, which ultimately provides safety to bank customers.

Additionally, competition in the environment is also an indicative term for enhancing the interest rates. It motivates professionals operating in commercial banks to have higher operational gains and large sales volume. Moreover, there have been influences of governmental schemes and policies for citizens in terms of enhancing lending rates, on which they have influenced changes in the rates on subsidised financial companies, which are mainly financial institutions and operational units (Taguchi et al., 2015). These motives of governmental authorities are in respect of balancing the inflation rate and exchange rate in the economy. Thus, if there is a strong currency value in respect to USD, then there will be less inflation in the nation. The dependency on other nations will be reduced, as it will enhance the per capita income as well as the purchasing power of individuals. According to Dash and Pathak (2016), asset and liability management must exist in the company because if there is good management of both, then the condition of the bank remains good in the volatile market. This is also indicated by the findings, where it is identified that if any bank asset and liability management is good, then in that case people feel safe to make transactions through a commercial bank. Thus, both studies on this point have consensus.

If a bank offers customers higher interest rates, there will be an increased chance of having appropriate profits in return. Considering such an approach, will invite more and potential investors that will help bank in generating appropriate capital gains. In commercial banks of Tajikistan, to improve commercial activities and monetary circulation, this approach will help personnel in the favourable accumulation of capital funds. The status and condition of banks have an impact on consumers, as they opt for banks that have higher revenue and turnover in a period. On the other hand, the status and image of banks raise consumer expectations. There can be various tactics and strategic development in terms of improving the currency risk management of firms. They also seek the returns they will receive through such investment. Thus, banks have to offer consumers an adequate interest rate that will attract them in investment terms. There has been a rise in the operational motives and level of gains in businesses. There have been impacts of operational practices, which are performed by banks. The motive of WTO is to develop fair-trade practices and norms among the nation, which will be adequate and efficient in making proper operational development. Therefore, the main support of the WTO had been based on making adequate increments in the economic condition of the nation.

5.1 Theme 1: Facilities provided by bank with relations to interest rate in deposits

In financial liberalisation, various financial institutions have made modifications to their lending rates in a particular location of the economy (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). This affects the aspect of retaining higher revenue through borrowed funds. Moreover, it helps the banks to reduce their repayment amount and enhances monetary circulation in a positive way, which is helpful and adequate in uplifting operational gains and motives in the economy. Usually, financial liberalisation is granted within the framework of the global approach of macroeconomic balance, financial liberalisation and structural modifications. As a result of overall liberalisation, the economic situation of many enterprises deteriorates, and the total amount resources used to repay bank loans is reduced (Bayat et al., 2015). In addition, various analyses have been made on the theories presented by Keynes that point out that as an entity in investment markets improves; there is an increase in the level of danger in the prevalence of speculative transactions in business operations. Moreover, there will be development of the market for derivative securities (Tabit and Moussir, 2016). The derivatives market allows financial institutions to redistribute various types of risks, creating new instruments, thereby attracting new customers. According to the responses to the survey, it can be said that there are various techniques, which are being implicated by small financial banks, which helps them to mitigate the challenges incurred due to changing interest rates. The results indicate that the interest rate on the commercial banks is 3.80%, which is lower than in countries such as India, where the interest rate on deposits is 7% to 8%. The lending rate in Tajikistan is 13% and so, it can be said that there is huge difference in the interest rate in respect of deposits and loans. Such a huge difference greatly affects people, as they receive less on deposits and have to pay more on loans. It can be said that this situation in Tajikistan is not good.

Newly entered banks into the market have charged higher interest rates. Such approaches will help to integrate the large numbers of consumers or investors in the banks. They have increased to retain higher profits from investment in banks. Thus, if the bank offers them higher interest rates, there will be a chance of generating appropriate profits in return. Considering such an approach will invite more and more potential investors that helps bank to generate appropriate capital gains (Kwan, 2018).

In accordance with the safety concerns, there will be consideration of proper banking laws and regulation, which are being governed in Tajikistan (Maxfield et al., 2018). The management of operational practices will help in upgrade security in the banks. Thus, investors will rely on the

banking operations and have trust in making investments in the banks. There will be consideration of the methods of making transactional activities such as online and offline. Thus, mostly, in the online transactional process there will be chances of having manipulation and cyber-crime because of improper funding and operational administration (Sharofiddin et al., 2018). While, the banks make necessary increments in the operational practices, which will help them in governing the transactional, approaches and make reliable changes in work practices. The interest rates charged among inter-bank transactions, on the other hand, impacts consumers. Thus, the higher inter-bank charges will also have an effect in a parallel manner by increasing the interest rates offered to buyers. There will be negative impacts on people for having ineffective increments in the financial conditions and operations.

The impact of banking status and condition have an impact on consumers as they usually go for the banks which have higher revenue and turnover in a period (Taguchi et al., 2015). This suggests that it would be profitable to invest in such banks. On the other hand, the status and image of banks will have raised expectations among consumers. Therefore, they have to be effective in terms of offering the relevant services among professionals, which in turn will be useful for generating appropriate capital gains.

Moreover, financial inclusion will set the small banking units to expand their business in the market. This is because their terms and consideration for operating the banking practices are appropriate and liberal for borrowers. Attracting consumers by offering them higher interest on their invested amount of funds in the banks will help the banks in generating appropriate equity (Bobokhonov et al., 2017). Consequently, it will affect the number of borrowers in the firm. Thus, the higher rates will also affect their capacity for making returns to the bank. Moreover. In that manner there will reduction in the number of consumers to entity. On the other side, the challenges and competition among banking businesses have been a challenging aspect, which will affect the lending operations of the firm. Therefore, the rise in competition levels also increase interest rates (Khordehfrosh Dilmaghani and Tehranchian, 2015). This encourages banking professionals for retaining the higher earnings and revenue from the external professionals which in turn attentive towards generating higher profits.

There have been various other operations, which are being provided to senior citizens such as term deposits, fixed deposits, borrowing schemes and special interest rates on their invested funds in the organisation (Kwan, 2018). There are benefits and adequate rises in the gains, which

can make beneficiary improvements to the business. In addition, people with respect to their applied bonds, funds, and the finance ministry central treasury bonds have made various social insurance claims. However, this will be the main aim of banks in terms of bringing the satisfactory services to the senior citizens, as they have appropriate amount of retirement monetary and are willing to make investments in the banks to secure their uncertain future (Sharofiddin et al., 2018). Thus, the beneficiary rates and schemes need to be awarded to them, which will bring them higher satisfaction, and operational gains that are incurred in managing the operational activities.

Moreover, analysing the outcomes with statistical tools to identify the relationship between interest rate and sales of commercial banks gave a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.405 and 0.412. Thus, this demonstrates that the data has less reliability. It can be ascertained between 0.60 to 0.70. Thus, less than 0.60 is treated as less reliable information.

5.2 Theme 2: Satisfaction through online services provided by bank

To provide active structural reforms and implementing major projects in the framework of financial policy. In the absence of other financial institutions, the main tasks of banks were, first, allocation of public funds in form of centralised loans, and secondly, protecting domestic producers, including new emerging industries, from external competitors by maintaining a high level of preferential credit (Khordehfrosh Dilmaghani and Tehranchian, 2015). The solution to these problems assumed administrative management of credit resources and a high share of quasi-fiscal operations of the government in the banking sector. Moreover, enhancing credit terms and term deposits in banks will be helpful in to attraction the debt management in operational activities.

In respect of introducing reforms in economic activities, the financial market and the capital market as synonyms need to imply a market for financial institutions that provide movement of savings from those households and firms whose revenue exceeds expenses to those firms and households that want to spend more than current income allows (Schnabl, 2017). The result of functioning of the financial market at the turn of the 21st century was the deformation of its economic role, the cause of which lies in the inherent volatility of the capital market, that makes it possible to profit through speculation and not through use of financial resources in the production process (Sharofiddin et al., 2018). The Tajikistan financial market belongs to an emerging environment, as it only originated around twenty years ago. Operational aspects in every bank depends on the level of consumers generated and facilitated with borrowing services. There can

be an increment in and development of operational tasks that will help in managing activities, as well as analysing the cultural needs of business.

Despite this, it was also affected by crisis shocks, which led to the intensification of government actions to revise the financial market regulation system. In addition, it is necessary to solve such problems. By creating conditions for attracting domestic and foreign investments, increasing this activity and developing small and medium-sized businesses with solving the problem of credit availability for the real sector. Liberalisation is one of several steps taken to develop the financial market in Tajikistan. Moreover, there will be a positive rise in Tajikistan's GDP rate of as if the government makes supportive plans and schemes in the banking sector, and it will enhance growth in economy (Bobokhonov et al., 2017). These banks have been approached to facilitating the appropriate loans and advances to small-scale industries which gives them appropriate loan advantage. This is inversely benefiting the nation by making qualitative increments in the operational efficiency and generating employment opportunities in society (Ahmed, 2018). There can be growth in the domestic production of the nation, which in turn has a positive impact on the level of business activities.

To consider the operational gains in business which has led to a positive rise in banking efficiencies, of various techniques and methods have been used to present an adequate analysis of the data set (Thanh et al., 2017). In this process, there are influences of various aspects and elements, which have been used to examine the factors such as descriptive statistics, ANOVA tests, Chi-square, regression and correlation. Therefore, such tests and statistical analysis will bring accurate information relevant to the data set. Using such techniques has resulted in reliable and valid information regarding the changes in lending rates by commercial banks.

Therefore, the main support of the WTO has been based on making adequate increment in the economic condition of the nation (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). Therefore, economic development will be related to appropriate trade practices among multiple nations, which will financially assist the operations and make appropriate application for improving domestic revenue (Thanh et al., 2017). Thus, financial support will help the country to have proper GDP rates, which can help to improve small-scale industries. The development of small business will rise the value of the currency and respectively control the interest rates in the market. The impacts of financial development will be reflected in positive changes to all the segmentation. The government will have enough funds to make appropriate development and analysis of the issues.

Operating the banking services through online segmentation is a most convenient and new approach which helps the organisation to retain adequate gains and facilitates management of operational analysis. This is one of the key finding of the research. There can be manipulation or fraud in the banking practices in relation to online transactional activities (Bobokhonov et al., 2017). There are various areas which of main concern to the organisation in respect of banking transactional practices, such as crime crimes and security related to transacting funds from one location to another (Martin et al., 2018). There can be several issues and obstacles, which can have a negative impact due to uncertain and inadequate online operational management. Professionals have presented their reviews based on their satisfaction regarding the online operation performed by the banks (Mandilaras, 2015). Thus, on reviewing the findings, it can be determined that the majority of professionals are in favour of online services facilitated by their banks. Thus, in Tajikistan the rise in digitalization has also had a positive effect in terms of improving the banking operations in economy.

In addition, there are various benefits of involving digital influences in the banking and transactional practices. It helps to administer transactions at any time and from any location (Tabit and Moussir, 2016). There might be increments and growth in business efficiency, which in turn have impacts on raising business efficiency. It will positively affect bringing the appropriate auditing practices, which can be useful identifying the loopholes of risks associated with the operations. Risks are related to the banking operations, economical consideration, changes in the governmental plans, and polices towards taxation, current exchange rates and interest rates (Ahmed, 2018). Thus, this directly affects banking operations in terms of short- and long-term policies. However, protecting banks from the direct influences of such market risks on which they create separate risk management systems will protect the banking operation from external impacts. Thus, the creation of this shield will help investors to secure their money invested by them in banks (Ramlall, 2017). If the bank become insolvent before declaring insolvency, they will first make payments to their consumers on their invested money. Thus, with such an approach to operational activities there will be separate risks, which will protect and prevent the banking operations from such external influences. There are various risk management techniques, which are practiced in banks, such as basis risk, yield risk and several material risks.

The research also uncovered that management of such issues and obstacles will help the firm to retain an adequate amount of gains and profitability. Thus, it will also help in managing effective consumer relationships and improve the efficiency of banks in terms of meeting appropriate growth by having effective financial control and management of various practices that can assist professionals to attract consumers with profitable interest rates. However, the prices only fall as per rise in yields, which are particularly in, bonds that have a long maturity and low coupon rates. Thus, long-term bonds of futures will have lower interest rates due to the longer duration a firm has to make payment to an individual. Thus, this time duration advantage will help investors to retain their profits for a longer period. The charges will help to improve revenue moreover, affects operational issues. Mitigating the risks will result in higher revenue generation and better operational administration, which will lead to the organisation being more successful.

There are several risks and issues, which creates obstacles in the banking system, which will be helpful in governing and operating the banking tasks. Thus, there are transactional risks are on the prime concerns. The security of funds invested by consumers in banks are safe and customers can relay and trust on it. Therefore, the responsibilities of bankers and banking professionals are to make appropriate increments in the revenue and growth of the firm's operational efficiency. Therefore, it is necessary for every banking institution to have separate risk management systems, which will be helpful to them in managing the obstacles as well as analysing the risks, associated in the banking business and to facilitate the disclosure of financial health of the business on which such requirements will be helpful to manage and operate the banking activities.

5.3 Theme 3: Securities with making transactional operations

In concerning, the techniques, which have been implicated by the banking organisation on which they usually use value at, risk which bring them uniformity in measuring the risks as well as bringing the accurate analysis over the profit generated by the industry. Risk management units have been enacting the techniques and methods for establishing the supervision of risk management operations that will include responsibilities of managerial units regarding transactional aspects and the security of the invested funds by the consumers in banking units. Tajikistan usually has lower interest rates charges among the loan and borrowings taken by the professionals. Thus, in consideration with such aspect people are less interested in investing the funds in the banks. They are highly attracted towards investing the funds in the real estate and

shares, which will bring them long-term benefits. Therefore, to encourage the people in making investment in the banking firm it is required to redevelop the policies as well as ensuring higher security to their invested funds.

There are various banking operations in a firm on which various kinds of risks are being associated with each department and piece of work. It can be said that. All the financial risks which are being associated with the banking business such as credit risk, liquidity risks, operational risks, market risks, computer system risk, legal risk and reputational risk. However, in terms of credit risks there are several significant issues seen in the banking industries, such as not becoming able to recover loans, restoration of business conditions, and circumstances incurred with the counterparty and with the credit risks. Thus, in order to ensure there will be no problem of cash management, commercial banks have to maintain assets and liabilities. This is also evident from this research, where it is identified that asset and liability management matters a lot for commercial banks. Banks have earning through facilitating the loan and lending money among consumers and corporations, which will bring them earnings from interest. Therefore, banks sometimes fail to recover the granted money to such individuals for various reasons such as the person is dead or insolvent. Similarly, the organisation has become insolvent and therefore, there is no chance of recovering the loan amount. To overcome such risks, banks take out guarantees to acquire the fixed assets of the respective concern, which will bring them, support and techniques to overcome the credit risks associated with such operations.

In terms of market risks, there are various obstacles and issues incurred in market functions. The fluctuation of the interest rates, currency values, stock prices, etc. all affect the economic stability of the nation and also require banks to make changes in their operational policies. Therefore, it can be said that as market risk is inherent in the banks' operations, there will be involvement of interest risk, which affects the banking account, savings and loans, by individuals. Similarly, there will be a risk of fluctuation in the stock that is held by the banks in consideration of the long-term investment. Thus, these are the market risks, which affect a banking business. To overcome such risks, there have been various obstacles and issues, which need to be considered by the banking professionals, which are in motive for enhancing the techniques and methods to overcome with such obstacles.

In relation to liquidity risks, there are various obstacles, which affect the business operations, such as managing the liquidity of the firm. Failure of banking professionals in managing the short-

term solvency and the ability to balance the current asset and current liabilities affect the operational and management practices in a required period. In addition, banks offer short-term loans to buyers, which are somehow effective in retaining the higher returns and quickly recovering the lent amount within a specific period.

In the context of operating risks involved in the banking business, there are usually errors incurred while making transactional entries. This can be through banking professionals or by the errors incurred in computer devices. These technical errors will be resolved and overcome by the banking professionals, which can have impacts on managing the issues. Our research also indicated in the literature review that banks develop their own in-house technology infrastructure, but its maintenance is also very important, otherwise, technical errors can occur in the service and ultimately, customer encounter problems with online transactions. In addition, there are obstacles connected with unethical conduct and relevant circumstances, which affect the banking operations. Therefore, assessing the operational risks in the banking transaction will help professionals to have appropriate ascertainment of transactional processes. Similarly, there are risks related to computer devices used by the banking professionals in making inter-banking transactions and facilitating internet banking for consumers, since they also consist of errors in the system, and unethical conduct such as fraud, manipulation of funds, etc. These technical errors are the prime concerns, which affect operations and take time to resolve. To overcome such issues, there will be requirement of having regular auditing of the system software. A regular upgrade and installation of new software rise the level of performance and provide a quick response to mitigating such technical risks.

Legal obstacles and influence of governmental plans and policies also affect the banking operation in terms of inviting uncertainties for resolving problems. Influences of laws, rules and reforms in the governmental policies are affecting banking operations. In Tajikistan the influence of government and legal authorities are related to resolving financial issues and obstacles, which will be helpful in governing the business tasks. To bring stability to the banking operational practices and preventing the firm from such risks, there is a need to be up to date with current affairs and issues incurred in banks.

The installation of effective technical software and regular auditing of the accounts will benefit the banking professionals in resolving the issues and mitigating the risks. Thus, in this case, the alternative hypothesis is accepted, and there is strong evidence against the null hypothesis.

Therefore, it can be stated that there is a mean significant difference between the interest rate and the sales revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan. Additionally, it can be concluded that the changes incurred in the interest rates of Tajikistan will eventually affect the sales revenue of the banking industry.

5.4 Theme 4: Role of banks' assets and liability management for addressing financial issues

In accordance with analysing the concept there have been security system, which are being presented in the bank software that will protect the information from spams and external hackers. There is an anti-virus software and malwares, which protect the official site just to create a shield over the network and the users of the sites. In addition, there is an implication of various self-generated pin numbers that create password of each individual with respect to make appropriate operational analysis (Khordehfrush Dilmaghani and Tehranchian, 2015). Therefore, as per the epitomes there are mostly positive reviews which were retained by the researcher that professionals believe that their banks are offering appropriate security in terms of monetary transactions (Bayat et al., 2015). However, according to the literature was discussed that, buyers or investors in any financial institution are seeking for proper security on their invested money as well as desired of having higher returns against it. The influences of appropriate cyber security will help in uplifting the business activities as well as management of several operations.

Improving the transactional operations with proper influences of the cyber securities. It consists that there must be regular auditing of accounts which can be important and adequate in terms of enhancing the operational activities as well as managing the business operations (Martin et al., 2018). It is essential that the banks must keep proper cyber administration with regular audit and management through technical professionals. The data are needed to be kept confidential which is belongs to the funds of buyers. To retain the large number of investors for long-term operational support there will be requirement of bringing them appropriate satisfaction through securities.

The development of various economic policies and plans will be based on considering the monetary system in the nation. Thus, the impacts of such factors will be reflected in the determining the appropriate techniques to control credit policies (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). However, with the operational influences of principle guidelines of credit monetary and foreign exchange policies of Tajikistan and which was formed in 2000 have facilitated various guidelines

to present the appropriate monetary as well as credit policies (Taguchi et al., 2015). Thus, such monetary policy have been include various plans and approaches in terms of managing the various factors. However, other than this, NBT have presented the interest of creditors and investors for having appropriate financial stability and balance of banking system functions. Implementation of various software, which will help the banking firm in keeping the confidentiality in the database, which will be adequate in managing the operational practices as well as administrating the circulation of funds (Bayat et al., 2015). Along with this, there will be less influences and interaction of external parties in the banking operations. Thus, the confidentiality of records will help in managing the appropriate consumer relationship. There can be growth and profitability in the firm in terms of having smooth banking operations, which will, assists the workforce in making qualitative efforts.

On review of literature, it is identified that in order to provide more security to the mobile app users and net banking users there must be secured log-in and accessing system which will bring security cover to the investors. Every consumer has to be facilitated with the unique and different PIN no, which must be based on their opinion and choices for the passcode. Therefore, the confidentiality of such information will bring appropriate execution and control over the manipulation and reliability of database, which will be useful for the banking business. Moreover, it will be suggested to the professionals that they must keep the records of all online transaction and banking transaction performed each day. To bring the revolutionary changes in the banking operations it is required that the professionals needed to be attentive towards transactional details and confidentiality associated with it. The email addresses, mobile number, account number and pin code etc. are to be kept secure and only in the reaches of the consumer so they can easily modify and change as per their convenience. Implementation of anti-virus software is mandatory as it prevents the network system and computers from phishing, malware as well as from several other security concerns. Along with this, preventing the organisation system from spyware, which will help in protecting the data and ensures complete security. There must be proper updates and notification to consumers based on changes made in banking system and in the system software on which they access through computer of mobile phones.

However, bringing online banking operations will be more of a conveyancing technique, as it will help professionals to analysing the financial position of the business in a required period. Cloud systems will help them to work from any place and access all the required information in a

limited time span. The conveyancing of such a system is for professionals and consumers too. Making online payments and any banking operation becomes quick and easy, which prevents theft, manipulation and fraud in financial activities. People will have all results such as their account statement, remaining balance and interest in their accounts each time they operate any banking activities. On the other hand, the inter-bank transactional activities with which each computer devices are connected represent the appropriate overview over business transactional activities. The payments made by professionals as well as in executional consideration have reliable and profitable control over activities made in the firm. It requires the appropriate execution by technical experts enrolled in the business, and they should be assigned duties to analyse and detect any unethical issues incurred between banking operational practices. The detection will help in governing practices and ensure satisfactory operational services for consumers.

If banking organisations consider these appropriate transactional aspects, the chances of encountering theft and manipulation will be reduced. The banking or financial risks in the economy are consequently controlled, as the banks have appropriate operational analysis and due care regarding activities. There should be records of past transactions, which will help them to govern the targets and meet the operational gains in a limited period. Every bank must deliver site security, policies and disclosure to the consumers to communicate better terms and conditions in the transactional process. E-banking is based on various laws, regulations, and terms and condition to make the process smooth and convenient for the individual. Therefore, to deliver adequate information to buyers, it is necessary to keep proper records of each transaction. All the consumers, which are enrolled in online business transactions, should be given appropriate information regarding the terms to help in reduce the risks of any financial obstacles. One can easily make a claim in court and take advantages, such as refunds, discounts and allowances.

The rules and guidelines are facilitated by the financial services authorities which govern all the transaction processes, as well as interest rates charged by bank on savings account, current accounts and on loans borrowed by individuals. Professionals at commercial banks were asked for their views regarding the interest rates charged by their banks on borrowed funds. However, in relation to such aspects, the majority of respondents are in favour of their interest rates that are charged by their banks on loans (Schnabl, 2017). This can be helpful to them in terms of meeting business objectives. Therefore, banks have to be more reliable among their consumers in terms of charging interest rates on their borrowed money. This is the main source for them in generating

the appropriate amount of revenue (Bayat et al., 2015). Tajikistan is one of the leading Muslim nations, so there is a challenge that people belong to religion that does not consider charging interest as a good thing. Moreover, there will be challenges, which are faced by both Islamic banks and the conventional banking system.

Additionally, these challenges will be met if the commercial banks were to offer appropriate interest charges on borrowed funds. Revenue generation and collection of appropriate funds will result in stability in the capital structure and the management of the liquidity of funds. However, the prices only fall in relation to a rise in yields, are particularly in bonds that have a long maturity and low coupon rates. Thus, long-term bonds of futures will have lower interest rates due to the longer duration a firm has to make payments to an individual. This time duration advantage will help investors to retain profits for a longer period. To preventing the cause of financial crisis or any uncertain risks, banks need to have satisfactory policies that govern and make appropriate administrative analysis (Khordehfrush Dilmaghani and Tehranchian, 2015). The amount of funds borrowed by consumers in a particular period will be helpful to the professionals in acquiring adequate gains and managing operational analysis (Mandilaras, 2015). Gains from operational practices will be helpful in managing the financial stability of the operational functions.

The influence of the revenue-earning policies and techniques imposed by the government in any economy consists of adequate changes in the operational administration. Thus, there are several aspects, which govern the transactional analysis and management of practices. However, implementing adequate security among the consumers in relation to their invested money in banks necessitates appropriate execution of the funds invested by them. Banks usually make investment in various other aspects, such as investing in other banks or in the security market, which ensures higher revenue generation. Thus, with the same aspects there can be a change of retaining higher revenue along with highlighting the responsibilities of bankers in terms of making payments of the revenue acquired through such operations. Thus, satisfaction of an individual or a corporation with the banking services and interest is based on information provided by them. Thus, investors seek for higher returns, lower risks and appropriate security on their invested funds. If the bank declares themselves bankrupt, payment would need to be made to the investors based on their investment in the banks.

The review of the literature indicated that in order to maintain asset liability, many banks start charging higher interest rates so that losses caused by NPA can be covered. To meet the

internal banking competition, there is a higher chance of encountering tough competition in a manner that banks charge higher interest rates on their services. These higher interest rates will bring them higher revenue and increase their market value in the security markets. On the other hand, as per considering the consequences incurred while the period of global financial crisis when bankers used to charge lower interest to the consumer which results in them having a large number of consumers, higher monetary circulation and higher trade practices. Therefore, after such effects there is no money left in the banks for their operational activities and which caused the global financial crisis, higher inflation and economic recession. Various nations were directly and indirectly affected through such impacts, and consequently Tajikistan was indirectly impacted.

Consumer satisfaction resulting from interest rates imposed by the government will be helpful and adequate if they meet the operational targets at the right time. Borrowers seeking banking institutions that offer lower interest rates for lending. Investment security is a prime concern that will help to retain potential consumers on a long-term basis. Thus, according to the responses from bankers, it can be said that the majority are satisfied with the interest rates charged by their banks on borrowed funds by the investors. Thus, the stock market is based on assessing the risks and managing the operational analysis.

There have been analysis over the bank's assets liability management system in meeting the financial obstacles of banks in an appropriate timeframe (Bobokhonov et al., 2017). Thus, managing the current ratio is the prime requirement of every financial industry, who insist that there must be appropriate funds management and administration of business requirements. Therefore, such operations have been denoted as risk management as well as strategic planning for the business. Tajikistan is an underdeveloped economy and has higher influences of rising inflation rates (Taguchi et al., 2015). The causes are affecting operational phenomenon, which do not present appropriate information regarding the liquidity, interest rates, capital market risk and appropriate funds management. According to the findings relating to this issue, professionals responded that their banks' assets and liability management systems are capable of meeting the financial problems.

In addressing, the facts there have been implementation of various techniques and operational establishment, which are affecting the operational goals, and managing business issues have been considered to meet all the relevant risks (Khordehfrush Dilmaghani and Tehranchian, 2015). The main risks that are associated with banking businesses are related to the fluctuation in

the current rates, interest rates and changes in financial funding (Bayat et al., 2015). Therefore, these are generally the obligations that the banks are incapable of meeting. Consequently, this will challenge the bank's financial conditions and will affect the benchmark prices in the market (Maxfield et al., 2018). Moreover, liquidity is related to the short solvency of the business. Thus, if the business is capable of meeting the operational requirements at the right time, there will be increase in the revenue and gains to the firm.

In terms of capital market risks, these are connected with the changes in the level of equity generated by firms through investors based on futures, bonds and securities (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). There can be various tactics and strategic developments in terms of improving the currency risk management of firms. They also seek the return they receive through such investments. Thus, banks have to offer them an adequate interest rate that will attract them in investment terms. There is a rise in the operational motives and increments in the level of gains in business. There are impacts of operational practices, which are performed by banks in having inappropriate administration of operational practices.

Term deposits will be adequate in terms of generating an adequate amount of revenue. Term deposits or short-term loans will be beneficial in terms of having higher revenue and easy recovery of funds. Consumer-borrowed funds in the short-term will have higher interest rates charged on them, which help the banks to gain appropriate revenue and better collection. It will help the business in adequate financial governance in terms of executing the inflation rates, tax advantages, security or volatility, flexibility or liquidity, growth and income, and the desire to leave an estate and ease of management (Maxfield et al., 2018). However, as per analysing the objectives of banks, which are mainly focused and based on improving the funds and number of consumers the current ratio of institutions, has to be adequate and appropriate which enables them to meet the short-term solvency (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017).

Additionally, it can be said that there is the potential for higher revenue generation by banking institutions if they facilitate term deposits. The short-term period loans will be helpful as there will be lower taxation rates charged on the gains. In addition, there could be an increase in revenue or funds for the business, resulting in fruitful gains (Sharofiddin et al., 2018). From an economic point of view, there will be higher security, as the banks will have quick returns on their granted funds. Thus, such factors will have higher revenue generation.

5.5 Theme 5: Satisfaction through interest rate charges on borrowed money

There are various short-term investment options through which a business can acquire adequate gains and achieve effective operational analysis, including bank fixed deposits that benefit the banking organisation in terms of having appropriate liquidity, tenures, quick returns, as well as taxation benefits. Investors have faced a dilemma of whether to make investment in long-term as well as short-term operations. There have been increments in the gains and revenue of banks, which can be effective in uplifting the level of revenue retained by the business. In short-term investment, there are mutual benefits to banks and consumers. They will receive a quick response to the applied transactional process and acquiring funds. Banking businesses have analysed the rates of making payments to their shareholders based on their invested money in the bank. They make enough money to pay their employees and maintaining the buildings to run operations in the firm. They can gather appropriate amounts of money or have revenue using several sources such as by charging interest on the funds they lend to individuals or corporations. This is the main purpose of banking and the main source of acquiring revenue. Based on such lending and facilitating borrowing, these businesses are able to have higher gains and profitability. They can also achieve gains through charging fees on the services they offer to consumers, such as transactional charges for inter-banking operations.

In addition, they can also make money through the traditional financial instruments on which they make operations in the financial market. To market the ownership of banks in the proportionate manner, various investors will make investment to have appropriate acquisition of funds. Therefore, banks also make investment in various other corporations and banks in terms of receiving favourable returns on their invested money. Through such sources, banks will have appropriate market share and a satisfactory amount of capital in the business. It is identified that long-term loan many times converted in to NPA. Such kind of things affect banks' balance sheets. Therefore, encouraging the consumers to undertake short-term borrowing will be helpful to the banking industries in terms of having higher monetary circulation as well as earning through the interest received by them. The biggest advantage of lending a short-term loan is that there is a lower risk of having bad debt and fraud in financial aspects. The interest rate of return in short-term borrowings are comparatively higher than the long-term borrowings made by banks. Thus, there are higher chances of having high revenue and gains through the operational practices. The short-term borrowings benefit from low risk and higher return. Moreover, in relation to such

benefits, it can be said that there are comparatively higher revenue and gains as obtained by banks. There has been preparation of various informal and formal process by the banks, which are required for managing the risks. Therefore, the changes in interest rates will affect the economy and society.

It can also be said that there is a need for making adequate operational analysis and determination of the fruitful practices that have to be governed and managed by professionals (Taguchi et al., 2015). Implementing a financial consumer protection scheme would be useful for retaining the trust and loyalty of consumers of banking services. This includes several areas that should be considered by banking professionals such as an institutional framework, regulation and legal influences. These can result in positive increments and a rise in the operational level of business that would assist in the development of good governance and management of operations. There will be influences of various consumer disclosure, which deliver information regarding the transactional practices performed by banks in a certain period (Tabit and Moussir, 2016). Clear information regarding operational practices will help in reliable auditing of all accounts. Thus, the chances of funds being manipulated would be reduced, enhancing the consumer relationship and financial governance in the firm (Kwan, 2018). Similarly, these effective management practices would help to reward buyers for their investment and interest rate allowances for their funds (Bobokhonov et al., 2017). On the other hand, to mitigate the banking and interest rates risks, it is necessary to improve organisational performance. Thus, the appointment of qualified and talented workforce for such practices would be adequate and helpful to the firm in retaining the targeted goals at the right time.

Various issues have arisen due to protecting the consumers from financial that which are connected with the financial structure of Tajikistan's commercial banks (Schnabl, 2017). Therefore, there is a need for clear responsibilities and capacity of the firm in dealing with the financial obstacles. There have been negative impacts of improper execution of banking operation, which might bring hurdles and can damage the consumer relationship. If an investor feels safe and secure regarding their invested funds, then they are more interested in making investment in the industry. This requires appropriate cover and protection from external impacts on their investments (Khordehfrush et al., 2015). The National Bank of Tajikistan has been making efforts to design new policies and frameworks for banking personnel. There will be analysis over legality of power and resources, which are to be used in performing the banking tasks (Sharofiddin et al., 2018).

Proper monetary administration and protection will be adequate in guiding the business for having adequate cooperation and coordination to improve the mechanisms and financial regulations for improving capacity in dealing with an effective financial sector.

Alongside all this, the firm must have an effective dispute resolution system to receive consumer feedback and make appropriate changes to the operational practices (Taguchi et al., 2015). This will be helpful in determining any risk and loopholes that the banking firm has in its operations. Thus, managerial professionals would be able to draft a new strategy and techniques to overcome such issues (Bobokhonov et al., 2017). Moreover, such an approach will enhance the capabilities of the firm in mitigating the challenges and improving the financial stability for the long-term operational practices. Various operational as well as financial risks involved in the operational practices of the banking organisation. Therefore, to mitigate such risks, there it is necessary to develop a separate risk management system. The risks can be related to the credit risk, market risk, operational risk, etc. thus, to meet such obstacles there will be necessary increments and development of plans which will be helpful in governing the tasks and operations in the firm. Training and development of banking professionals with reference to meeting the challenges need to be adequate, as there can be necessary increment in the operational practices and governance of the operations (Redivision of the banking market going on in Tajikistan, 2017). Professionals will have effective solution to each issue and that will help in governing in financial aspects of firm.

Moreover, according to the multivariate test carried out to analyse and detect the variables, there is no relationship between the interest rate and sales revenue of commercial banks in Tajikistan. The significance value of the data set was 0.520, 0.050, 0.367 and 0.520. The majority of outcomes demonstrates to accept null hypothesis. Through this observation, it can be said that there is no influence of changes incurred in interest rates over the sales of commercial banks.

For developing the SME's or entrepreneurs in small areas with granting them lower rate loans (Tabit and Moussir, 2016). Thus, such grants help the locality in terms of having adequate growth and development that results in beneficiary gains. It results in a rise in the flexibility and liquidity in the economy, which will help to govern the individual risks, knowledge and confidence management. There will be consideration of long-term borrowers. On the other hand, it has been analysed here that the credit union grants will reflect negatively in terms of reducing market value

of banks (Taguchi, Sahoo and Nataraj, 2015). Thus, banks will facilitate the lower interest rates to provide appropriated funds to the small-scale industries.

There is ineffective and inadequate utilization of funds with lower returns by banks, which results in a reduction in the revenue or capital stability in firms and this leads to a reduction in the brand value in the capital market. As a result of such impacts, there will be adverse market conditions that damage the economy (Thanh et al., 2017). In the commercial banks of Tajikistan, the main motive is to grant adequate loans and borrowings to the small-scale industries, which will bring them higher returns, and adequate gains as a social responsibility (Khordehfrosh, et al., 2015). Along with this, it will affect the economy, as banks will not have a sufficient amount of funds in their reserves, which can lead to financial crisis. There are higher corporate taxes which are payable by banks in terms of revenue gathered by banks for in appropriate business administration.

It is necessary for banking organisations to be concentrated towards enhancing the profitability and revenue gains through operational efficiencies. Therefore, lending the funds and having revenue through interest rates will be adequate techniques in attaining business goals and making appropriate efforts to generate revenue and make adequate gains through operational efficiency of the firm. The main motive of the banking industry is to attract a large number of borrowers or investors from which they can earn revenue through charging interest on such funds. Therefore, banks or other financial institutions, with a motive to retain higher revenue and to compete effectively in the market, have designed various terms and policies. The differences in the market value and rate of return affect the chances of having adverse market conditions for such firms through fluctuations in the NPV of future cash flows. The higher interest rate risk will negatively affect or threaten the earnings, liquidity and solvency of banking firms (Bobokhonov et al., 2017). In addition, there are impacts of various issues in the interest level risks such as non-offsetting effects on the assets, liabilities and derivatives of the organisation. However, the material risks will have negative impacts on rising the issues and affecting the financial institution for insecure and inadequate operational analysis (Maxfield, Wang and de Sousa, 2018). It is on the other side, it is known as the best sources for generating profits and having appropriate gains that will help the organisation to retain adequate gains. It is necessary for businesses to have appropriate risk management systems that will have positive impacts on managing the issues and risks relevant with the financial operations (Sharofiddin et al., 2018).

There are several basic risks which need to be managed, such as yield curve risks which belong to changing rate relationship between different maturities of same index that have adverse impacts on income and economic value of the firm (Mandilaras, 2015). However, this curve will reflect the adequate analysis and outcomes based in the capabilities of firm in mitigating the risks at the right time. Therefore, the main motive of the industry is based on managing the marketability and share value in the capital markets, which will bring them large numbers of investors who are keen to make appropriate investments in the business. The charges levied by commercial banks as interest rates will be adequate and helpful in terms of uplifting the operational gains and managing the operational analysis. In banking, organisations there are various creditors and debtors and relevant accounts, which have to be kept in the books. Thus, the transactional entries of each accounts in a periodical basis need to be made (Kwan, 2018). This will be a great method for removing all obstacles and issues, which in turn will be helpful for overcoming with the manipulation and material risks.

However, regular auditing of the bank accounts will be the best method for preventing the business from any material and financial risks (Martin et al., 2018). According to the findings based on the question that was put to the banking professionals at commercial banks, the majority of respondents said they agreed that their banks have effective risk management systems that help them to manage financial stability as the changes in interest rates did not concern (Schnabl, 2017). Thus, the changes in governmental plans and policies, as well as risks associated, in the business will have negative as well as positive influences due to changes made in operational analysis and management of various industrial activities.

5.6 Conclusion

On the basis of this chapter, it can be said that the outcomes and opinion of various individuals and the analysis made of the secondary research have been combined to ascertain the research issues. The regression and correlations analysis of all five variables have determined that there is no mean significant relationship between sales revenue in commercial banks and interest rates in Tajikistan. However, the findings show an R-value of 0.180 that is 18.0% of the data is related to each other. Similarly, the significance value is 0.186 which is higher than 0.05. This demonstrates that these variables are not correlated with each other, as there is no relationship between these variables.

On the other hand, in terms of considering the impacts of derivatives which ascertains that they can impacts on limiting the downside earning exposures, increases yield, preserve higher earning potential and reduces income/ capital volatility. This will be a great source for banking institutions in generating an adequate amount of capital funds (Tabit and Moussir, 2016). Moreover, it will affect the large portion of both sides of the balance sheet such as assets and liabilities through limiting interest rates risk. Thus, the accentuated capital structure will have an impact on the management of debts and the solvency of business, which will help consumers to have appropriate rates charges over their borrowings. Reciprocally, it will affect the rise in consumer retention and commercial activities of banks (Thanh et al., 2017). Every banking and financial institution has backup plans which helps them to mitigate the challenges and risks. There are several risks, which create obstacles in the organisational performance of the business (Ahmed, 2018). It can be relevant with the interest rates changes impacts over capital banking operations that creates hurdles in the growth and operational practices (Bayat et al., 2015). However, major number of responses are in favor of this statement that banking institutions in Tajikistan have effective process for mitigating risks. In analysing the reviews of the professionals, form different commercial banks in Tajikistan on which they have various process and approaches, which have helped them in overcoming all the risks associated in the business. However, there are several techniques, which have been impacted by the banking professionals such as buying interest rates futures (Maxfield, Wang and de Sousa, 2018). Thus, purchasing shares on the interest rates that includes government bonds and interest rates futures. Therefore, it enables the banks in lock in hedging their portfolios as well as lock in a certain interest rate. Besides this, the purchase of shares will bring best returns that will result in adequate gains and raises the operational efficiency.

To mitigate the risks there are further options that can be considered by the banking professionals or investors, such as selling long-term bonds. Therefore, there are various individual investors, which hedge against rising interest rates by selling bonds in the market (Khordehfrosh et al., 2015). However, the prices only fall as per the rise in yields, which are particularly in, bonds that have a long maturity and low coupon rates. Thus, long-term bonds of futures will have lower interest rates, which due to the longer duration a firm has to make payment to an individual. Thus, this time duration advantage will help investors to retain their profits for a longer period (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017). Thus, selling such bonds will bring profits to the firm in a required time. On the other side, buying a floating rate and high yield bonds hedge against increasing their portfolio

from long- to short terms (Sharofiddin et al., 2018). This includes floating rate bonds and high yield bonds. Thus, these are the strategies and techniques, which are usually governed and considered by banking professionals in terms of overcoming challenges and mitigating the risks associated with banking operations.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.0 Introduction

In this final chapter of the thesis, the research aim and objectives are restated and based on the analysis of the findings, the conclusions are drawn. Finally, a recommendations section is provided. In this chapter aim, objectives and findings of the study are given and explained in detail. While formulating conclusion in a systematic way from varied sources, information is gathered and then its contribution to knowledge in terms of theory, methodology and practice is explained. In addition, further research areas are also suggested in the report in respect of interest rates and banks. The limitations of this study and opportunities for future research are discussed in the subsequent sections. Personal experience that has been observed during the research process is also explained.

6.1 Review of Research Aim and Objectives

Aim

- The aim is to analyse the impact of the variation in interest rate in commercial banks in Tajikistan after accession to the WTO. A case study on commercial banks of Tajikistan

Objectives

- To study the current condition of interest rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan.
- To examine with theory, models and analysis in order to investigate the fluctuation of interest rate.
- To analyse the impact of interest rate liberalisation in the financial system of Tajikistan.
- To compare the interest rate and liberalisation of Tajikistan with its neighbouring nations.

These objectives was attained through primary and secondary data sources, which in turn assist to improve the results. It is conducted through the mentioned sources because with the help of primary study, scholar conducted survey questionnaire and interviews in which respondents provide valid results and this in turn leads to meet the define aim. While through secondary data sources, theories were used which in turn leads to answer research questions. It was observed from findings that there is an impact of variation and interest rate in commercial banks of Tajikistan. From the analysis of the data, it can be concluded that interest rates on deposits are very low and

interest rates charged on bank loan are high. The outcomes derived from this research are summarised and consists of several parts, including the overall conclusion of the research, the contribution of the research, as well as a set of recommendations for banking professionals of commercial banks in Tajikistan, with respect to making revolutionary changes in banking practices. To improve the potential and banking efficiency in the economy there will be several suggestions put forward to them. This chapter will have effective information regarding the analysis and findings of researchers with respect to meet the concrete evidence.

There has been ascertainment of effective information regarding the banking system and government plans to develop the banking system in Tajikistan. The problems and issues, which are faced by professionals in the industry, need to be resolved and managed in an effective manner. This chapter will also consist the information regarding the favourable suggestion, which are to be presented among the professionals to resolve the interest rate relevant obstacles as well as techniques to overcome with them. There will be recommendation and analysis over the contribution of researcher and professionals in the completion of this study.

6.2 Outcome of hypothesis tested

In terms of testing the hypothesis of this research, it has been found that there is no significant difference between the interest rate and revenue earned by the banks. This means that when interest rates are changed, there is no significant change in the revenue earned by the firm. To analyse the impacts of variations in the interest rate changes in the commercial banks of Tajikistan after impacts of accession of WTO on which study will highlight all the relevant facts and obstacles. Thus, there had been examination over the obstacles and issues, which were being involved into practices and have affected the operations in banking system. Therefore, the aim of report is for reaching to all aspects and issues which being faced due to changes incurred in the interest rates in commercial banks. It has been analysed here that commercial bank makes changes in the interest rates, which are in relation with meeting the competition among market, increasing the financial stability, liquidity as well as attracting the large number of stakeholders to the firm.

The government in Tajikistan makes various plans regarding revolutionary changes in the economic conditions which will help in governing the operational activities of banks in respect of improving GDP ratio, inflation control and raising the currency value in the international market. Thus, such planning and operational needs reforms in banking practices. Increments in the interest rates will have an impact on the operational tendency and performance, which will be helpful in

governing the tasks and managing the business issues. Main concerns and planning of the government in terms of meeting the goals as well as reaching to the appropriate solution which will be effective and adequate in analysing the current situation of the nation as well as the financial changes in the international market. However, as per analysing the objectives of the research projects on which it can be said that, the current study and the market conditions which will be effective in analysing the interest rates in the commercial banks of Tajikistan with an approach towards meeting the goals and making appropriate ascertainment of the operations.

In accordance with the proposed theories, models and analysis for investigating the reasons behind variations in the interest rate which have had addressed the issues faced by professionals at commercial banks in Tajikistan. Therefore, the study has been based on considering the risks and issues in the banking practices while making transaction entries as well as in generating revenue. The interest rate charges, fees and various relevant transactional charges are the prime sources through which a banking entity have become able to gather the relevant amount of funds, which have been reflecting the positive responses with impacts to have appropriate gains and analysis over the database. To improve the operational efficiencies in the banking system on which governance and policy making are the prime concern which are has to be acknowledged by professionals.

After the accession of WTO, there has been increment in liberalised banking and financial operations in the commercial banks. It was a revolutionary change in operational practices, which have impacted on governing the tasks and managing the operations at the right time. The study sets out to examine the degree to which theoretical underpinnings of the McKinnon and Shaw framework manifest in the economy and further to examine the contribution of financial liberalisation to economic growth. In addition, this period encompasses the pre-reform era, which signifies financial repression and includes post reform era that is indicative of financial liberalisation. Prior to applying formal econometric methodology, it is important to ascertain the behaviour of the data using descriptive statistical tests and simple correlation. Co integration allows analysis into the existence of a long run stable relationship between various pertinent variables such as financial development proxies, financial liberalisation proxies, interest rate, savings, growth and investment. Analysis over such figures will be adequate for reaching to the final solutions and suggesting to the professionals at commercial banks in Tajikistan.

Thus, the outcomes determined that there have been huge impacts and variation incurred due to changes have been made in the operational activities and the interest rates of the banks. There will be influences of various consumer disclosure, which brings information regarding the transactional practices performed by banks in a certain period. A clear information regarding the operational practices will help in making reliable auditing of all accounts. Thus, the chances of having manipulation in funds will be reduced which accentuate the better consumer relationship and financial governance in the firm. Thus, buyers will have effective trust as pert having secured funds for operation.

6.3 Contribution to Knowledge

6.3.1 Theoretical Contribution

The interest rate fluctuations observed are time to time analysed from the perspectives of commercial banks in Tajikistan. The operational activities of commercial banks are increased up to a major extent because of fluctuation in the interest rate in effective manner. The framework has provided with reference to finance and growth. McKinnon and Shaw developed this framework for identifying enhancing growth effects made by financial liberalisation with contrast to financial repression. They presented the argument financial sector of the country can effectively raise savings volume, quality and quantity of investment in the best manner possible. It can be analysed that this theoretical framework has contributed in assessing effect on operational activities of commercial banks in Tajikistan and as to how such fluctuations lead to affect operational efficiencies up to a major extent. Moreover, it can be said that if interest rate fluctuation is reduced in the economy, financial sector may boom which will be beneficial for the economy in effective manner. Moreover, role of financial sector is to enhance the flow of savings by properly creating incentives.

Present research study indicates that for accomplishing higher amount of savings and increase in rates of investment, abolishing interest rate ceilings is required. It is then advised for giving up seignories by formulating adequate inflationary monetary policies in the best manner possible. It can be analysed that real interest rate must rise to market clearing values and as a result, increment in savings will be attained in effective manner. The significant factor behind the theory is that temporary higher growth rates are being accomplished in it. Other developing countries follow policy advice given by McKinnon and Shaw which results in accomplishing significant

elevation in growth rates and as a result, equilibrium is achieved between high and moderate real interest rates. It has been predicted that financial liberalisation would lead to reduction or slowdown of economic growth.

The financial repression has been major focus of McKinnon and Shaw as they have argued that this policy leads to diminishing economic growth of the country in the end. This is evident from the fact that reduction in funds volume are attained which are available for investment purpose. This means that investment is not injected and as a result, financial institutions cannot perform adequately leading to hampering their economic growth up to a high extent. This is the fact that was observed in the research study carried earlier. Present research study goes one step ahead and indicate that low rate of interest on saving account motivate people less to deposit cash in bank. Instead, people prefer to make investment but many times, they lose money in doing so. Thus, investment reduced in the nation economy and due to this reason, banks must increase interest rate so that people can be motivated to deposit more money with commercial banks. It can be ascertained that if the government of Tajikistan is not able to collect tax revenue, it then imposes financial repression measure as an implicit tax on the financial sector. It can be assessed that financial repression is severe form of restriction of financial and is adopted by government when tax-raising power is low. Reserve and obligations of holdings of government bonds help concerned authorities for effectively diverting savings to public sector at low costs. The commercial banking sector is adequate for it as it becomes difficult for extracting seignories from bond and equity market.

Scholar also used the different theories such as interest rate parity, which helps to meet the defined aim. It analyses the relationship between the interest rate and currency exchange rates, which is different for all every country. In the case of Tajikistan, there is a need to apply the theory, which in turn leads to attain the defined objectives. On the other hand, the investigator to ensure that the research is termed authentic also used neo-classical theory. With the help of the mentioned theories, scholar analysed the fluctuation rate within a country.

6.3.2 Empirical Contribution

With the help of the current research, scholar discussed the impact of interest rates on commercial banks in Tajikistan in multiple ways. Hence, it is observed by the scholar that interest rates greatly affect people's saving habits and spending patterns. Thus, frequent changes need to

be made in the monetary policy of the nation. In the past, many studies were carried out on the impact of interest rates on commercial banks in Tajikistan (Mushtaq and Siddiqui, 2017; Khakimova, Solehzoda and Fasehzoda, 2018; Mogilevskii and Asadov, 2018). Such findings were not demonstrated in other research papers published on the same topic. In this research, the relationship between interest rates and revenue earned by banks has been identified, which has not previously been tested in any research paper. The findings indicated that there is no significant difference between the variables.

In addition to this, with the help of the present study, scholar also contributed in meeting the defined aim and answer the research questions as well. Further, it is also analysed by the researcher that findings clearly reflected that when the interest rate of the country fluctuate, there is a direct impact upon bank, which will affect the overall spending of the banks.

6.3.3 Practical Contribution

The practices are being implemented show that the government of Tajikistan has joined the WTO. The interest rate fluctuations in the country affects the commercial banking sector to a major extent. It can be said that financial liberalisation has been applied, which provides clarity that reforms will be attained in the banking sector, and stabilization would be accomplished in a better manner. This does not mean letting go all of control, but includes a process of easing off control of market forces quite effectively. This will initiate and influence Tajikistan's economy, which has previously been tightly controlled by the government and where is efficiencies are needed.

On the other hand, statistical techniques have been applied which provides clarity that operations of commercial banks are affected due to major fluctuations in interest rates and need to be controlled in a better manner. This means that interest rates should be stabilised in a timely manner so that operations are not affected, and profits could be generated by maximising customer satisfaction in the best manner possible. Tajikistan's accession to the WTO by will be beneficial for correcting interest rate fluctuation and contribute stability in the financial market. This means that commercial banks will be able to enhance inflationary measures and as a result, operational activities will be enhanced in a better manner. Moreover, it can be said that firms are required to provide efficiencies in a better manner. By adhering to the WTO accession rules, the commercial banking sector will be able to attain efficiency, as interest rate fluctuations will be handled in a better manner.

It can be said that financial liberalisation is beneficial for the firm, as restrictions on financial markets and financial institutions are reduced or even eliminated. Moreover, it can be said that banking firms will be able to enhance their position in the end and as a result, efficiencies will be gained in an effective manner. The resultant factor would be fruitful for the firm, as it will be able to attain control over its operational activities and would potentially be able to serve to customers with ease. Liberalisation would be fruitful for the overall economy of Tajikistan and will initiate healthy growth in the banking sector and as such, efficiencies will be gained. Commercial banks will be able to accomplish efficiency, and customers would be served with better and superior services in an effective manner. Thus, it can be said that after accession to the WTO, Tajikistan's economy will rise.

Overall, it is stated that scholar put their 100% contribution in order to make the entire research successful. With the help of primary study, it is analysed that most respondents answered in favour of the alternative hypothesis, which in turn assisted to meet the defined aim and answer the research questions as well. Further, the study also provided an opportunity which in turn leads to gain enough knowledge regarding the interest rate and how it impact upon the overall banks and people life style. Hence, through both primary and secondary data sources, scholar reflected own practical contribution and as a result, outcomes were generated in better manner.

6.4 Recommendations

Tajikistan has been facing various economic issues, of which interest rate fluctuation is a prime concern of the government. It affects the GDP rate, inflation and creates poor financial stability that has increased the price of commodities. Various recommendations are made to the professionals of commercial banks in Tajikistan in relation to improving banking efficiencies and managing the operational practices to ensure effective execution of banking operations.

Issues of banks losing potential consumers have risen in the past few years on which it is required to introduce new and strategic plans to the public, which will help them in governing the operations. It will also be beneficial to the buyers to have faithful reliability over banking operations so that they will feel secure regarding the funds invested by them in the banks. In accordance with the various banking aspects, it can be said that there are several challenges and obstacles, which will be summative to professionals in meeting the targets and managing the obstacles to overcome the issues. The researcher in terms of improving the commercial banking

system in Tajikistan presents several suggestions. This research project has assessed various issues, which are being faced by banking industries in respect with the fluctuation in operational practices. There are challenges that affect the banking operations on which interest rates fluctuation are the prime concerns and obstacles stated in the market.

Mitigating banking challenges and improving the banking efficiencies will be effective in analysing the issues and meeting targets at the right time. There is a need for strategic planning, which will develop policies and frameworks for achieving operational targets and the expansion of industrial operations. However, with respect to the obstacles there are several recommendations, which will be helpful to the banking professionals. These are set out as follows:

- There must be control and establishment of the regulatory authorities stated in country as well as development of various aspects. Therefore, it is necessary that professionals be attentive towards changing governmental plans and policies that will assist them in overcoming the operational challenges. It has been found that changing plans will also assist professionals in making revolutionary changes in the interest rates, which have been properly analysed in this research. Government plans and policies must be acknowledged and as a result, fluctuations may be determined and mitigated to a major extent.
- There have been plans and revolutionary changes that have been considered by the banking professionals in terms of other economic factors such as taxation, exchange rates as well as various socio-economic plans, which will help in, bring stability to the economy. In accordance with such variations, there will be an indirect impact on the banking policies and procedures of undertaking operational practices in the market. As the findings suggest, this will help to minimize the interest rate fluctuations and a result, firms may be able to attain efficiency, and the economy may become stable.
- There must be use of effective promotional techniques in terms of communicating the interest rates offered by the business with respect to meeting the targets in the right way. According to the research findings, disclosing items to stakeholders enhances the level of transparency concerning financial performance of the company. The disclosure of the financial statement and banking performance to stakeholders will provide them with appropriate information regarding the performance and the profitability of the banking industry and increase their faith and interest in the organisation.

- It is necessary that banking professionals implement a separate risk management system in their banking operations that will mitigate the various external and internal risks to the business. However, there are several obstacles, which need to be met by professionals with respect to attaining the goals and meeting the targets at the right time. In accordance with the research findings, by implementing a risk management system, the interest rate risk can be mitigated quite effectively and thus, economic stability can be accomplished.
- Risks associated with the credit, market, finance and operations need to be accomplished by the banking professionals which will be helpful in terms of developing policies and frameworks to eliminate such issues. The risks can be reduced but cannot be eliminated in nature. Thus, it is recommended that professionals develop techniques to ensure they are well prepared and attentive to overcome such factors and obstacles.
- There must be improvements to the technical operations of the business, such as software that is used in inter-banking transactions. The software applications should be simple and easy so that they can be easily accessed by consumers and they will feel safe in transacting funds.
- Ensuring proper security and prevention from cybercrime will help to create trust and loyalty among the potential investors in banking firms. It will be adequate in monitoring the database and managing the operations through such implementation.
- Determining the appropriate rate of interest charged on the services offered by the banking industry in respect of retaining a proper amount of revenue. Thus, consumers will be satisfied with the banking activities, policies and schemes offered which will retain their trust and faith in the organisation for making adequate ascertainment of the data to be analysed for performing the research in the markets.
- Installation of appropriate anti-virus software and regular auditing of banking operations will be adequate in managing the obstacles and management of the financial status of the organisation in society. It will help banking professionals in terms of protecting confidential information from unlawful and misrepresented information stated in the business.

6.5 Limitations recognised in the research

In the process of conducting the research study on the challenges that commercial banks in Tajikistan faced. There are several challenges faced by the researcher such as selection of relevant sources, pressure from respondents who wanted to withdraw from the survey, data collection as well as analysis to bring the accurate outcomes among the professionals in commercial banks of Tajikistan. In order to examine the study financial market challenges researcher faced some difficulties to get 150 questionnaires and 8 interviews completed accurately. All the respondent who were participating during data collection most of them were not completely honest, because they were afraid that someone would know or they will be fired. Although, despite the fact that I explained that this is confidential information and no one will know their details. After a while, many of them still sent an email to me in order not to participate.

6.6 Recommendations for future research

As ascertainment of the outcomes will be effective and attentive to make better operational analysis over database. In the present research, qualitative and quantitative techniques have been used for collecting information and analysing the outcomes. SPSS and thematic analysis has been used by researcher in analysing the opinions of selected respondents on which it can be said that, there must be implication of alternative techniques to tests the hypothesis. The question which were asked to the professionals instead of primary analysis there must be collection of some real and relevant data. It includes economic elements such as GDP rates, inflation rates as well as interest rates among the banking practices in Tajikistan.

6.7 Personal Reflection

During research study, I learnt a lot about ways in which research should be carried out. First, I read various articles and journals and identified the main issues that are observed in the current period. Subsequently, the research aim and objectives were prepared, and I reviewed a wide range of journals and in order to prepare the literature review section. It was a very tough task to conduct the literature review because varied authors said different things on the same topic. Finally, I carried out data analysis by using statistical methods and non-statistical methods and prepared the recommendations section. During the research, my data analysis skills improved.

Prior to this research, I did not have knowledge of Chi-square, correlation and regression analysis. While doing this project, I tried to understand these methods thoroughly. Hence, I developed a broad understanding of techniques and their assumptions, and this assisted me greatly in interpreting the research findings in a better way.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Questionnaire

Demographic questions:

Question 1: Gender

- Male
- Female

Question 2: Age as per below listed group:

- A. 20-29
- B. 30-39
- C. 40-49
- D. 50-59
- E. Above 60

Question 3: Language you speak and understand?

- A. English
- B. Arabic
- C. Urdu
- D. Russian

Question 4: How qualified are you?

- A. Doctorate in any field
- B. Post graduate degree
- C. Diploma
- D. Graduate

Question 5: Period of organizational occupied land or building?

- A. 2-5 years
- B. 5-8 years
- C. 8-10 years
- D. More than 10 years

Likert Scale Questions:

- 1 = Strongly agree
- 2 = Agree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Disagree
- 5 = Strongly Disagree

S. No.	Questions	1	2	3	4	5	Total
1	Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	55	35	30	20	10	150
2	Are the online operations performed by your bank quite satisfactory?	62	38	25	15	10	150
3	Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	50	40	30	20	10	150
4	Is your bank's asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	46	34	32	28	10	150
5	Do you believe that vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	62	38	25	15	10	150

Appendix B: Interview Questions

Question 1: What are your opinions towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates?

Question 2: How do you find that your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates?

Question 3: As per your opinion, what are the cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan?

Question 4: What are the general factors which are relevant with cost of loans?

Question 5: Which are the inflation factors that affect lending rate determination?

Question 6: According to you, what are the impacts of banking industry competition that possess variations in lending rates of commercial banks?

Question 7: What are the types of interest rate practices in your bank?

Question 8: According to you, what are the main features of interbank clearing and settlement system? Do they have any influences as per changing lending rates?

Question 9: How interest rates are determined in Tajikistan? Is there any rate which are administratively set?

Question 10: Do you believe that there are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates?

Appendix C: Interview Transcripts

Interview 1:

Questions	Answers
Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates	Well as I have analysed, I think liberalisation is the term where most of the private industries or sectors were being banned by government. Thus, it creates obstacles in their performance and operational growth. Impact of governmental plans and policies are mainly affecting the banking sector in country.
Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates	I believe that in analysing the answers of various professionals which were being asked these questions that have represented the adequate determination of the facts. Thus, in this case, there have been influences of various factors which distract in banking operations that affect the overall operational activities.
Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan	I can say that in analysing the factor which affect lending rates in banks are generally relevant with expenses and operational variations. However, there have been various determinants which create obstacles in analysing the data base and abounded banking operations as with affecting lending rates.
Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans	I think it has been analysed here that there are various general factors which will affect the cost of loan in an industry. It creates the obstacles in the banking operations of the commercial banks as if the bank borrows funds which is not capable of meeting such costs in the future. Thus, these are the debts which create issues in the survival of such financial institution.
Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination	I believe that in accordance with analysing factors which influence the interest rates in a country. Therefore, impacts of inflation rate fluctuation in a nation will have positive as well as negative impacts on the lending rates.
Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks	I believe that there are impacts of raising competition in the nation which will affect operational policies for banks. During the global financial crisis when in motive of enhancing the sales in banks for meeting the market competition, bankers have facilitated the loans on lower interest rates. Thus, due to

	such impacts, there have been changes in their lending rates for meeting challenges in the market.
Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank	Well I can say that, bank borrows funds from other banks that will result in uplifting the operational aspects of the banks. Thus, the variations in inter-bank transactions there have been various changes and variation which brings them gains and losses on the same respect.
Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.	I think in terms of analysing the payment system in Tajikistan where the main emphasis of the government had been payable on the realization and financing operation performed in the country.
Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set	Well, it has been consistency of various factors which will have impacts on identifying the interest rates in Tajikistan. It comprised of various classification policies which have been based on various activities such as bank's classification as well as of Tajikistan's classification theory.
Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates.	I think government in Tajikistan have huge implications of policies which create obstacles in the banking industry. The main motive of economist in a country which is basically determination of appropriate sources to rise the currency value as well as reduction in the inflation rate.

Interview 2:

Questions	Answers
Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates	The changes in taxation, rate of exchange as well as interest rates in operations are mainly affecting operational practices of private banks. I believe that such influences have uplifted level of competition among banking firms as well as which impacts lending rates.
Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates	I believe that it mainly affects the sales growth, efficiency as well as preference of industry. The rise in interest rates which have impacts on reducing public borrowings as well as increases the debts of industry.
Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan	I have analysed that it mainly includes the merger and acquisition of small banking units, intensity of capital exertion by creditors in

	operational administration, policies for enhancing risk reduction arrangements.
Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans	The viability as well as capacity of firm in terms of financial structure will define effective cost-efficient factors to improve business operations.
Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination	Inflation in general terms is known as rise in prices of commodities which is relevant with issues such as dependency as well as poor currency rate of nation.
Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks	Thus, due to some impacts, there was no money left in the banks as well as in circulation.
Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank	There have been various kinds of financing activities which are needed to be done with the motive of making appropriate changes and operations that will lead in managing the operational analysis.
Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.	In relation with ascertaining the inter-bank clearing or credit settlements, there are several processes. This includes principle of reliability, acceleration of settlement transmission and expediency.
Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set	It can be said that it is based on current interest rate structure which will help in making proper analysis of the activities.
Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates.	Government mainly creates policies relevant with interest rates, taxation, report and import duties which were analysed for balancing the current operations of country.

Interview 3:

Questions	Answers
Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates.	The main motive of these banks is based on retaining higher profitability as well as higher consumer index. This will help them in retaining appropriate growth in sales or revenue.
Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates.	There are various plans and policies which were being stated by the government such as monetary policies, taxation, economic changes, etc.
Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan.	There have been influences of various cost factors and the economic elements which affect lending rates. It includes the monetary policies,

	relationship with other nations, GDP and inflation rates.
Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans	In respect with granting the loans among corporation as well as individual which will have impacts on raising the funds of organisation. Moreover, borrowing a certain amount of loan will require the payments of such borrowed amount in a required period.
Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination	In this approach, there has been various issues such as dependency of Tajikistan over other nations in terms of obtaining the natural resources. These create reduction in the currency value as compared with other nation which in turn accelerates inflation rate.
Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks	People at that time have made investment in real state which results in reducing the monetary circulation in countries. Therefore, it brings rise to the inflation states, reduction in GDP as well as GFC impacted in economy.
Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank	There are generally simple and compound interest rates which have been charged against the amount of loan granted to a person.
Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.	Such analysis helps the banking organisations in terms of having adequate operational analysis and management of various approaches. However, the advantages of such transnational process are like banks charge fewer rates in clearing any account or making profitable rise in the operational aspects.
Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set	There has been administration over controlling the interest rates as well as appropriate wealth management.
Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates.	Frequent changes in the operations of banking firm which have affected policies as well.

Interview 4:

Questions	Answers
Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates	The deregulatory authorities stated in country have made huge impacts on changing operational variations as well as on development of various aspects.
Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates	The operational aspect of commercial banks is mainly relevant with providing better banking services to investors. Thus, the changing rates

	will affect the loan amount granted by banks as well as the terms for borrowing the amount.
Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan	Thus, such factors have negative as well as positive impacts on country which bound the economists in analysing the current scenario and planning for improving the internal environment.
Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans	Controlling the costs of lending the amount which is incorporated with several factors such as executing the interest rates, preparedness for emergency condition, economic stability, analysing the fiscal performance of the nation as well as ascertaining the debts.
Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination	Impacts of rising the interest rates or lending rates among commercial banks. It comprises of various factors such as fractional-reserve banking, quantity theory of money, interest rates, loan, inflation and savings, quantity theory of money and federal open market committee.
Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks	Tajikistan has been engaged in various financial obstacles as there is higher competition as well as rise in inflation results in enhancing the interest rates.
Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank	On the basis of such interest rates, they have higher earnings and revenue for development of various operational practices. In particular, due to the accelerated inflation rate as compared to the expected decrease, as well as the appreciation of the exchange rate.
Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.	There will be rise in the operational efficiencies of the banks which in turn will be helpful for managing the transactional obstacles.
Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set	In respect to manage the operational demands in the market. Thus, in analysing the obstacles there can be influences for adjusting the terms and risks associates with business operations.
Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates.	As per analysing the impacts of GFC attacks in the country, there has been rise in the inflation rates, unemployment and several unfavourable economic rates which have affected operations of firm.

Interview 5:

Questions	Answers
Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates	As per considering the banking preferences, there will be higher concerns relevant with generating profits as well as reducing costs implied in each banking activity. It has analysed that in October 2008, there was a total debt of US\$700 million on the cotton sector which are extremely funded in consideration of pledges and guarantees by National Bank of Tajikistan.
Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates	Through such sources the banks will have appropriate market share and satisfactory amount of capital in the business. therefore, encouraging the consumers to make short term borrowing will be helpful to the banking industries in terms of having higher monetary circulation as well as earning through interest received by them.
Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan	The growth rate in Tajikistan is not so appropriate which states that small and medium sized industries are not capable of retaining the higher revenue as compared with the multinational industries.
Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans	These are the factors which are needed to be considered by the government and professionals at banks for making fruitful policies and operational development in the work culture.
Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination	The biggest advantage of lending the short-term loan is that, there will be lower risks of having bad debts and frauds in financial aspects.
Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks	Competition in banking sector has also affected poor mechanism in management and operations of firm. The impacts of such rising competition in the operational activities of the banking industry have negativity affected operations of the firm.
Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank	In the latter case, the situation of enterprises that produce goods destined for export deteriorates, as their competitiveness in the world market falls. Exporting enterprises are forced to adjust to the new condition increase efficiency, sales growth of products inside the country.

Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.	There has been consideration of “contracts of services on interbank settlements”, the banks stated in country transit funds from one branch to another.
Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set	The interest rate of return in short-term borrowings are comparatively higher than the long-term borrowings made by banks. Thus, there are higher chances of having high revenue and gains through the operational practices.
Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates.	There have been various reforms and changes in the operational analysis and determination of accurate interest rates.

Interview 6:

Questions	Answers
Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates	these was the initiative which have been taken by bank in context with promoting the agriculture sector in country. Thus, on which the creditor was ought to receive the securities as compensation.
Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates	The short-term borrowings are benefited with the low risk and higher return. Moreover, in relationship with such benefits it can be said that there are comparatively higher revenue and gains as obtained by banks.
Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan	It is due to dependency of this nation on other nations. The domestic strength is not appropriate in retaining appropriate development in the economy of Tajikistan. Instability in the current account of country which will be managed through balancing the payments and trades.
Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans	It will have prolonged to improve the browning tendency as well as lending capacity of the bank.
Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination	Ascertainment of the national growth with considering such factors will help in uplifting the economic conditions as well as bringing favourable gains to the nation.

Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks	The rise in competition in the banking sector will bring reduction in the interest but on the other side, it will affect the poor monetary circulation in the environment.
Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank	There has been preparation of various informal and formal process by the banks which are required for managing the risks. Therefore, the changes in interest rates will affect the economy and society.
Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.	The impact of banking status and condition which have impacts among the consumers as they usually go for the banks which have higher revenue and turnover in a period.
Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set	Thus, which reflects that it will be profitable to make investment in such bank. On the other side, the status and image of banks will have risen expectations among the buyers.
Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates.	They have to be effective in terms of offering the relevant services among professionals which in turn will be useful for generating appropriate capital gains. Thus, adequate interest rates will also be accentuating to firm in having extra and fruitful returns which will enhance strength of organisation in mitigating the financial risks.

Interview 7:

Questions	Answers
Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates	In this case, debts have been owned by investors in financing cotton sector in the economy. Thus, in 2009, the government of Tajikistan was continuing to facilitate the funds in agricultural sector with the help of commercial banks without restricting of limiting the borrowings to cotton growing. Moreover, there had been various steps which were taken by NBT with references to liberalise the export of cotton.
Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates	Moreover, the financial inclusion will ascertain the small banking units to make trade practices in the market. It is because their terms and consideration for operating the banking practices are appropriate and liberal for the borrowers.

Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan	Raising the level of export's income with the imports. These are the accounting factors which are affecting the economy and which will reversely affect the interest rates of the nation.
Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans	By luring the consumers as per offering, them the higher interest on their invested amount of funds in the banks will help the banks in generating appropriate equity.
Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination	Adversely, it will affect the number of borrowers in the firm. Thus, the higher rates will also affect their capacity for making returns to the bank. Moreover. In that manner there will reduction in the number of consumers to entity.
Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks	Countries like Tajikistan will have various obstacles which will result in inappropriate internal management which will affect economic activities in country.
Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank	On the other side, the challenges and competition among banking businesses have been a challenging aspect which will affect the lending operations of the firm. Therefore, the rise in competition level also increase the interest rates
Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.	It encourages banking professionals for retaining the higher earnings and revenue from the external professionals which in turn attentive towards generating higher profits.
Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set	There have been various senior citizens which were being facilitated with the pension scheme presented by government on the basis of their services and efforts made in jobs. Thus, the level of job done by them as well as the level of efforts made by them have been converted into the revenue payable by the government throughout their life
Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates	Along with them there will be beneficiary from their family which are a dependent person such as their wives or children as per asking the professionals that how satisfy their consumers with the pension schemes offered by their bank

Interview 8:

Questions	Answers
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<p>Theme 1: Your opinion towards impacts of liberalisation on commercial bank lending rates</p>	<p>Therefore, in Tajikistan commercial banks have several operational activities which are benefitting the buyers with securing their funds as mentioned in their bank accounts. Thus, it has been believed by the professionals which are operating the banking activities in the commercial banks of Tajikistan believes that they are offering appropriate pension schemes to their consumers and they are satisfied with the banking policies and regulation in this approach</p>
<p>Theme 2: How do you find your bank have influences due to commercial bank lending rates</p>	<p>The government as well as commercial banks are capable of meeting the requirement of senior citizens in terms of benefiting them with pension services.</p>
<p>Theme 3: The cost factors that affect determination of lending rates in commercial banks in Tajikistan</p>	<p>There have been various other operations which are being awarded among the senior such as terms deposits, fixed deposits, borrowing scheme as well as special interest rates on their invested fund in organization</p>
<p>Theme 4: The general factors which are relevant with the cost of loans</p>	<p>There will be benefits and adequate rise in the gains which can make beneficiary improvements in the business.</p>
<p>Theme 5: The inflation factors, that affect lending rate determination</p>	<p>there have been various social insurance claims have been made by people with respect to their applied bonds, funds, and the finance ministry central treasury bonds.</p>
<p>Theme 6: The impacts of banking industry competition that poses variations in the lending rates of commercial banks</p>	<p>The impact of banking status and condition which have impacts among the consumers as they usually go for the banks which have higher revenue and turnover in a period</p>
<p>Theme 7: The type of interest rate practices in your bank</p>	<p>Thus, which reflects that it will be profitable to make investment in such bank. On the other side, the status and image of banks will have risen expectations among the buyers.</p>
<p>Theme 8: The main feature of interbank clearing and settlement system. They have any influences as per changing lending rates.</p>	<p>Therefore, they have to be effective in terms of offering the relevant services among professionals which in turn will be useful for generating appropriate capital gains.</p>
<p>Theme 9: The process for interest rates determination in Tajikistan and identification of rates which are administratively set</p>	<p>adequate interest rates will also be accentuating to firm in having extra and fruitful returns which will enhance strength of organisation in mitigating the financial risks.</p>

Theme 10: There are influences of the governmental policies in making changes in commercial bank lending rates

the financial inclusion will ascertain the small banking units to make trade practices in the market. It is because their terms and consideration for operating the banking practices are appropriate and liberal for the borrowers.

Appendix D: Frequency Analysis:

		Statistics										
		Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	Are the online operations performed by your bank is satisfactory?	Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	Does the pension schemes award by your bank is satisfactory among consumers?	Does your bank have any separate risk management system?	Does your bank offer satisfactory interest rates charges on the borrowed money?	Did your bank offer term deposits with respect to make appropriate revenue?	Do you believe that, vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	Does your organization have any material risk relevant with interest rate risk?	Does your bank have a formal process in mitigating this interest rate risk?
N	Valid	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.29	2.15	2.33	2.48	2.33	2.15	2.29	2.48	2.15	2.29	2.33
Median		2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Mode		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Std. Deviation		1.277	1.252	1.251	1.283	1.251	1.252	1.277	1.283	1.252	1.277	1.251
Variance		1.631	1.567	1.566	1.647	1.566	1.567	1.631	1.647	1.567	1.631	1.566
Range		4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Percentiles	25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	50	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
	75	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.00

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?	2.29	1.277	150
Are the online operations performed by your bank quite satisfactory?	2.15	1.252	150
Do you feel safe while making transactional operations?	2.33	1.251	150
Is your banks asset liability management units play main role in addressing the issues?	2.48	1.283	150
Do the pension schemes awarded by your bank are satisfactory among consumers?	2.33	1.251	150
Does your bank have any separate risk management system?	2.15	1.252	150
Does your bank offer satisfactory interest rate charges on the borrowed money?	2.29	1.277	150
Did your bank offer term deposits with respect to make appropriate revenue?	2.48	1.283	150
Do you believe that vulnerability of a credit union's financial condition in adverse market movements?	2.15	1.252	150
Does your organization have any material risk relevant with interest rate risk?	2.29	1.277	150
Does your bank have a formal process in mitigating this interest rate risk?	2.33	1.251	150

Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: Does your bank facilitate the appropriate interest rate in deposits?

Parameter	B	Std. Error	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval		Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
Intercept	2.800	.395	7.088	.000	2.019	3.581	.257	7.088	1.000
[Did your bank offer term deposits with respect to make appropriate revenue =1]	-.126	.436	-.289	.773	-.988	.735	.001	.289	.060
[Did your bank offer term deposits with respect to make appropriate revenue = 2]	-.653	.449	1.453	.148	1.541	.235	.014	1.453	.303
[Did your bank offer term deposits with respect to make appropriate revenue =3]	-.644	.453	1.422	.157	1.538	.251	.014	1.422	.293
[Did your bank offer term deposits with respect to make appropriate revenue =4]	-.979	.460	2.126	.035	1.888	-.069	.030	2.126	.561
[Did your bank offer term deposits with respect to make appropriate revenue =5]	0 ^a

a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

b. Computed using alpha = .05